

A GENERATIVE PHONOLOGY OF EDO (BINI)

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BY

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DEDICATION

To the memory of my mother

who left too soon.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to describe the phonological system of the Edo (Bini) language within the framework of generative grammar.

Chapter I discusses the distinctive feature framework employed in the study. A number of multivalued features for consonants and vowels are proposed mainly following Williamson (1976), Ladefoged (1971, 1975) and Lindau (1975). Two new multivalued features - tone and boundary - are also proposed. Some conventions, mostly those proposed by Williamson (1976), for stating simultaneous, sequential, and alternative values of the same multivalued feature within a single segment are also introduced.

Chapter II states the lexical and phonetic redundancies revealed by the Edo (Bini) language. The lexical redundancies are stated by means of morpheme structure conditions made up of segment structure conditions (SqSCs) and sequence structure conditions (SqSCs). The phonetic redundancies are stated by means of surface phonetic constraints (Shibatani 1973).

Chapter III analyses the general phonological processes which operate in the language. The processes discussed are nasalization, vowel assimilation and contraction and tonology. In the tonology section the language is analysed as having two basic tones, high and low, each of which has a downstepped variant arising from the deletion of a preceding low tone. The general tone rules are then introduced.

Chapter IV describes the underlying phonological representation of the sentence constituents as a prelude to the analysis of the grammatically conditioned phonological processes. In the verb phrase it is shown that every affirmative verbal construction obligatorily contains a subject concord marker. The structure of auxiliary markers and verb stems are also discussed. The structure of negative verbal constructions is described, and the verbal constructions are exemplified.

Chapter V, which is the last chapter, analyses the grammatically conditioned phonological processes. It is shown that some tone rules - low tone raising and high tone lowering - have to have access to the derivational history of their inputs. At the end the exceptions to

some of the rules encountered in the work are treated. It is postulated that the deviant behaviour of some vowels, especially e and o, is a reflection of their historical origins. Some exceptional cases cannot, however, be explained within the scope of our present knowledge.

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INTRODUCTION

0.1. The Edo (Bini) Language0.1.1. Location and Nomenclature

The Edo (Bini) language belongs to the Edo branch of Kwa. It is classified by Elugbe (1973) as belonging to the North Central sub-group of Edo. The Edo group is in turn a branch of Kwa of Niger-Congo. The closest neighbours of the Edo group are Yoruba to the west, Igbo to the east and Igala to the north, all of which are also Kwa languages.

The Edo (Bini) language is spoken in the Benin West and Benin East Divisions of the Bendel (formerly Midwestern) State of Nigeria. The population of the area was given as 430,000 by the 1963 census.

The language is usually referred to in the literature as either Bini or Edo. But the latter term, Edo, is also used as a generic name for the predominant language group in the Bendel State. In order to resolve the ambiguity resulting from the "multiple interpretation of the scope

of reference of Edo as a linguistic label"¹, it was decided at a conference on Edo orthography held at the University of Lagos in May 1974 to refer to the language spoken in the two Benin divisions as Edo (Bini).

Edo (Bini) is a largely homogeneous language. However, some dialectal varieties exist in some border communities such as Oza, Usen, Eho and Iyekorhionvbon. These dialects have not been studied by the present writer and are, therefore, generally not taken into account in this work.

0.1.2. Data

The variety of Edo (Bini) studied here may be called the standard or common form. Within this form two types of varieties can be identified. The first variety is determined by the tempo at which an utterance is being performed while the second variety is the result of idiolectal differences.

Speech tempo is determined by extra-linguistic factors such as the mood of the speaker, the occasion of the speech and the audience to whom the speech is

1. Cf. Midwestern State Ministry of Education (1974:1).

addressed. Two types of tempo can be clearly identified - the rapid and the slow tempo. In rapid speech certain segments which are present in slow speech are sometimes elided. For example, the word for "head" is ùhùvbù in slow speech but ùhùũ in rapid speech. Similarly, the word for "clock" is égógó in slow speech but éógó in rapid speech.²

A good example of idiolectal differences is the occurrence of the sound r ([ɹ]). For the majority of speakers of Edo (Bini) this sound has gone to zero while it is still retained in the speech of some other speakers.

Whenever differences such as those just described are observed we generally choose the forms which we

2. Wescott (1965) who was the first to observe tempo differences in Edo (Bini) identifies seven speech tempos in the language. While we agree that more than two speech tempos (possibly three) may be meaningfully distinguished in Edo (Bini), seven speech tempos are, in our opinion, clearly superfluous.

consider to be more basic (i.e. historically older). Thus, for example, although r is not present in all varieties of the standard form of Edo (Bini), we consistently use r in our transcriptions because we regard the variety with r as being more basic in this respect.

Since the present writer is a native speaker of Edo (Bini) he has relied very much on his intuition about the language in eliciting data for analysis in this study. However, data was also elicited from other native speakers both in Benin City and Ibadan at various times and to varying degrees. Most of those who helped in this way have been mentioned in the acknowledgements.

Written works were also a source of data. Such works include Egharevba (1972), O. Ebohon (1974) and I. Osemwegie's unpublished plays Ise and Eyowo.

0.1.3. Previous Studies

Not much work has been done on the description of the Edo (Bini) language. Melzian's (1937) dictionary is the first systematic study of the language. Apart from the very useful grammatical notes and the largely accurate

transcription of items in the body of the dictionary, the introduction contains a very detailed description of the sound system, especially the tonal structure, of the language.

Melzian's second book - Vergleichende Charakteristik des Verbums in Bini - was published in 1942. The present study has not benefitted from this apparently very useful work because we were only able to get parts of the work translated when this study was already nearing completion. There is every evidence that by the time of writing this book Melzian had got what can be considered a very accurate picture (especially considering the time at which he wrote) of the structure of the Edo (Bini) language.

The next serious study of the language is Wescott's three-volume Bini Grammar published between 1962 and 1963. Part I of the grammar is devoted to the phonology of the language. The main problem with Wescott's grammar is that it is not modelled after any particular theory of grammar; as he himself points out, he tried to "mediate between structuralism and traditionalism" (cf. pt. 1, p. 2) in the work. Perhaps essentially as a result of this, no clear

picture of Ẹdo (Bini) phonology emerges from the study. In spite of this, however, the work bears much evidence of Wescott's keen hearing, though not of accurate analysis. (Cf. 3.3.1.2. for a discussion of Wescott's total analysis).

Elugbe's (1973) Ph.D. thesis - A Comparative Edo Phonology - contains a brief discussion of the phonology of Ẹdo (Bini). As a result of the extensive scope of the work (Volume I includes phonological sketches of thirteen Ẹdo languages) and the fact that it is essentially a comparative study, the information on Ẹdo (Bini) phonology is not very detailed. However, Elugbe made a major contribution to the study of Ẹdo (Bini) phonology in his analysis of the tonal system of the language as terraced-level with two tones plus downstep.

Dunn's An Introduction to Bini contains perhaps the largest body of linguistic data on the Ẹdo (Bini) language so far published. It does not, however, offer much by way of analytical insight into the structure of the language, apparently because it is only a pedagogical work designed for the United States Peace Corps learners of the language. (Cf. 3.3.1.3. for a discussion of

Dunn's tonal analysis).

Welmers (1973) presents a brief description of the tonal structure of the language (4.29) and the phenomenon of vowel contraction (2.19). Welmers' tonal analysis is reviewed in detail in 3.3.1.5. of this work.

0.2. Theoretical Framework

0.2.1. The Model

The model of description followed in this study is essentially the Standard Theory of transformational generative grammar as articulated in Chomsky's (1965) Aspects of the Theory of Syntax and Chomsky and Halle's (1968) The Sound Pattern of English (henceforth SPE). The phonological description is based essentially on the version of generative phonology expounded in Stanley's (1967) "Redundancy Rules in Phonology", Postal's (1968) Aspects of Phonological Theory, SPE, and Schane's (1973) Generative Phonology. However, some modifications arising from more recent developments in the theory of generative phonology have been made. These, and detailed discussions of specific aspects of the framework will be incorporated in the body of the work in the

relevant places and as the need arises.

The following is a concise summary of the major aspects of the Standard Theory of transformational grammar; as much as possible, we overlook the controversies connected with different areas of the model.

0.2.2. The Syntactic and Semantic Components

According to the transformational theory, the grammar of a natural language is a system of rules that relates sound to meaning (SPE, p. 3). In the Standard Theory framework, a grammar is made up of three major components - the syntactic, the semantic and the phonological components. The relationship of the components is illustrated in Fig 1. (cf. King 1969:17).

The syntactic component, which is the generative component of a grammar is made up of a Base component and a Transformational component. The base is in turn made up of the base rules and the lexicon.

The base rules generate the basic sentence types of the language together with their structural description. The base rules are of the following type:

Fig. 1. Organisation of a Transformational Generative Grammar.

1. S → NP + VP
 VP → VC (+ NP) (+ ADVB)
 VC → CM + VS
 CM → SCM (+ AM) (+ Su.)
 ADVB → (Prep. Phr.) (Adv.)
 NP → N (+ Q)

(where VC = Verbal Construction; CM = Construction Marker; VS = Verb Stem; SCM = Subject Concord Marker; AM = Auxiliary Marker, Su. = Suffix; ADVB = Adverbial; and Q = Qualifier; cf. Chapter 4).

The lexicon consists of a list of the formatives of the language and the information that characterizes the behaviour of each formative at the syntactic, semantic and phonological levels. For example, the lexical formative èwé (goat) will be described syntactically as a count noun, semantically as animate and non-human, and phonologically as consisting of three segments with their distinctive features. A lexical entry contains only idiosyncratic properties of items. For example, the phonological description in the lexicon must contain just enough information for phonological rules to

determine the phonetic form of an utterance in each context.

The output structure generated by the base is known as the deep structure. The deep structure contains the structural description of a sentence and the lexical items inserted from the lexicon. A highly abbreviated deep structure of the Edo (Bini) sentence

1. òzò 'ghá 'kpòlòwá

"O. is sweeping the house"

is represented in Fig 2.

Fig. 2. Deep structure Representation of the Edo (Bini) Sentence: òzò 'ghá 'kpòlòwá .

The semantic component is a system of rules which assigns semantic interpretation to the deep structure generated by the base.

The transformational rules convert the deep structure into the corresponding surface structure. Transformational rules may add, delete, permute and substitute items.

0.2.3. The Phonological Component

The surface syntactic structure roughly constitutes the input to the phonological component. Only minor adjustments are effected by readjustment rules to prepare the surface structure for entry into the phonological component (cf. SPE: 9ff. and 371-2 for details).

The phonological ^{component} consists of a system of rules which relate the abstract underlying phonological representation (which is like the deep structure of the syntactic component) to the more concrete systematic phonetic representation (which is like the surface structure of the syntactic component). Whenever, in the rest of this work, we talk of underlying and surface

representations without any further qualification, these should be understood to mean the underlying phonological representation and the systematic phonetic representation respectively.

Syntactic information is generally needed for the operation of phonological rules. As this study will reveal, many phonological rules in Edo (Bini) depend on information provided by the syntactic component. For example, the phonological rule converting the (L)H tone pattern on verb stems to a (L)L tone pattern is triggered off by the labelling of a verbal construction as simple imperative in the syntactic component (cf. 4.3.2.3.1.).

In addition to the syntactic information retained in surface structure, any information relevant to a morpheme is carried over from the lexicon. For example, if a lexical item (or part of a lexical item) in a given string is an exception to a particular phonological rule, this information is retained in the underlying phonological representation.

The phonological component is related in a special way to the lexicon through the morpheme structure conditions. The morpheme structure conditions

(henceforth MSCs) state the redundancies which hold at the systematic phonemic level. They match the partially specified dictionary matrix to the fully specified phonological matrix.

There are two types of MSC's - Segment Structure Conditions (SgSCs) and Sequence Structure Conditions (SqSCs) (cf. Stanley 1967). The former add features which follow automatically from other features in the same segment. For example, a SgSC will be required to state the constraint that the half-close vowels, /e, o/, are always non-nasal. SgSCs specify redundant features which may be saved in the lexicon and constraints on the combination of features within phonological segments.

Sequence structure conditions state constraints on the sequence of segments or features which can occur within one morpheme. They therefore add features which follow automatically from other segments within the morpheme. For example, the fact that a noun always begins a vowel in Edo (Bini) is stated by means of a SqSC.

According to Stanley (1967:426ff.), there are three ways in which MSCs can be stated; they can be stated as If - Then Conditions (I-TC), Positive Conditions (PC),

or Negative Conditions (NC). An If-Then Condition is like a transformational rule in that it has two parts - the "If" part which is the structural description of the dictionary matrix to which the condition applies and the "Then" part which is the structural change which is effected. For example, the fact that /e, o/ are redundantly non-nasal in Edo (Bini) is stated by the following If-Then Condition:

$$\begin{array}{r}
 2. \quad I : [2 \text{ height}] \\
 \qquad \qquad \downarrow \downarrow \\
 \quad \quad T : [0 \text{ nasal}]
 \end{array}$$

A Positive Condition is an incompletely specified matrix which states the constraints on permissible sequences of segments. The following is an example of a PC, in Edo (Bini).

$$3. \quad PC: \left[\begin{array}{c} = \\ VS \end{array} CV(V)(CV(V)) = \right]_{VS}$$

This PC states the structure of verb stems. The longest possible verb stem will consist of two consonants and four vowels, two after each consonant.

A Negative Condition states that none of the matrices which meet its specification occurs in the language.

The following example of a Negative Condition is given by Stanley (427). If a language has systematic phonemes $tʃ$, $ʃ$ and $dʒ$ but not $ʒ$, this situation will be described by the Negative Condition 4.

4. NC : ~ $\left[\begin{array}{l} 1 \text{ stricture} \\ 5 \text{ place} \\ 3 \text{ gl. state} \end{array} \right]$

(we have modified Stanley's transcription by using IPA phonetic symbols and distinctive features from the set proposed in chapter I of this work).

Following Shibatani (1973) we have introduced surface phonetic constraints (SPCs) which state redundancies that hold at the phonetic level. It is true that most SPCs can be accounted for indirectly by means of MSCs and P-rules. (P-rules operate on underlying representations to derive permissible surface representations.)

There are however at least two advantages in having SPCs in addition to MSCs and P-rules. Firstly, after stating MSCs we would like to know which of the MSCs also hold at the phonetic level and which ones do not. In a framework that does not permit SPCs this can only be done

in a belated manner since permissible surface representations are usually derived through the interaction of a number of P-rules. But SPCs provide a section in the grammar where permissible phonetic representations can be stated without having to go through all relevant P-rules.

The second advantage of SPCs is that they make the explanation of phonological processes easier. Many P-rules apply to prevent non-permissible phonetic representations. For example SPC 7(2.2.3.) states that VVV sequences are not permitted in phonetic representations in Edo (Bini). The presence of this SPC is clearly the motivation for the P-rule which deletes the consonant *r* of the simple completive suffix and the second person pronoun after C(G)V but not after CVV verb stems (cf. 4.3.2.4.1. and 5.2.1.).

As already pointed out, the phonological rules relate the underlying phonological representation to the surface phonetic representation. We assume that the rules of the phonological component are ordered relative to each other since some rules depend on the prior application of some other rules. Generally, syntactically

motivated rules apply before the phonetically motivated ones.

We have deviated in two major respects from the SPE framework with regard to the application of phonological rules. The first deviation is in permitting rules which can reapply to their own outputs. SPE avoids giving any rule such power by requiring a rule whose structural description is met by more than one segment in a string to apply to all such segments simultaneously (cf. SPE:343-4). However, Irwin Howard (1972) has clearly demonstrated that rules which apply iteratively are required in generative phonology. We also feel that the need for such rules is sufficiently justified in Edo (Bini). We follow Howard's proposals in formulating iterative rules (cf. 3.1.2; 5.1.3.; etc.).

Our second deviation from the SPE framework is in permitting rules which have access to the derivational history, or part of the derivational history, of their inputs. Such rules have been argued for by Kisseberth (1971, 1972a), among others. There is sufficient motivation for such rules in Edo (Bini). (Cf. 3.2.1.1.; 5.1.4.).

0.2.4. Distinctive Features

The MSCs, SPCs and P-rules are usually stated in distinctive feature terms, although in many cases abbreviations are used instead of distinctive features. We allow multivalued distinctive features at both the phonological and the phonetic levels. The set of distinctive features used in this work is presented in Chapter I.

0.3. System of Transcription

Vowels are transcribed with the IPA symbols i, e, ε, a, ɔ, o, u. Actually, only two of these (ε and ɔ which are the equivalents of orthographic ɛ and ɔ) are different from the orthographic symbols. Nasalization is marked with a tilde, ~, placed over the segment that is nasalized. The non-syllabicity of a non-high vowel is indicated by writing ̣ under it; e.g. ègwạ̀. (See below for the convention for indicating the non-syllabicity of high vowels.)

In phonemic transcription, consonants are written with the orthographic symbols as revised in 1974 (cf. Midwestern State Ministry of Education (1974)) while the IPA equivalents of these symbols are used in

phonetic transcription. However, y (IPA j), is retained in both types of transcription. The orthographic symbols, with the exception of the following, are the same as the IPA symbols.

Orthographic	IPA
gh	ɣ
kh	x
vb	v
rh	ʀ (vl. alveolar trill)
rr	r
r	ɺ (tapped alveolar lateral)

y, w, between a consonant and a vowel stand for non-syllabic i and u respectively; e.g. ègwí (tortoise), ògyé (laughter) .

The following consonant symbols are employed in phonetic (but not phonemic) transcriptions: n, ɳ (tapped alveolar nasal, the allophone of ɺ before nasal vowels), ɲ and ŋw .

Tones are marked over vowels as follows:

ṽ high tone

̀ṽ low tone

! before a syllable indicates that the tone of that syllable is a downstep tone. This is the orthographic convention for indicating the position of a deleted low tone since we postulate deleted low tones for all occurrences of downstep in the language.

For quotations from other works, the original transcription is generally modified to agree with that employed in this study, except where otherwise stated.

0.4. Notational Conventions and Abbreviations

The following notational conventions are employed in the work.

/ / slanting lines enclose systematic phonemic representations.

[] square brackets.

(a) enclose bundles of distinctive features

(b) enclose systematic phonetic representations.

(Actually we use slanting lines and square brackets rather sparingly. In citing examples the level of representation of an item is generally clear

from the context in which it occurs.

Also cf. 3.2.).

→ "rewrite as"

e.g. $X \rightarrow Y$ means "Rewrite X as Y" .

/ "in the environment of" and

— the location of the focus of a rule relative to the determinants. E.g. $X \rightarrow Y/Z$ — means "Rewrite X as Y in the environment immediately following Z".

() parentheses enclose optional elements.

Rules abbreviated with parentheses are disjunctively ordered, i.e., the application of one of the rules precludes the application of the other; e.g.

$X \rightarrow Y/Z(W)$ — expands as follows:

(i) $X \rightarrow Y/ZW$ —

(ii) $X \rightarrow Y/Z$ —

When (i) applies, (ii) cannot apply and vice versa.

< > angled brackets express discontinuous dependencies; i.e. they are placed around elements in different parts of a rule which require each others presence.

E.g.
$$\left[\begin{array}{l} 1 \text{ syllabic} \\ \langle 1 \text{ height} \rangle \\ \text{back} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [0 \text{ syllabic}] / \left[\begin{array}{l} 1 \text{ syllabic} \\ \langle 1 \text{ height} \rangle \\ - \text{back} \end{array} \right]$$

This states that for a vowel which is height (close) to become non-syllabic before another vowel with 1 height the two vowels must not agree in backness.

Like parentheses, angled brackets enforce disjunctive ordering.

{ } braces abbreviate sequences of partially similar rules. Rules abbreviated by braces are conjunctively ordered; that is, the application of one does not preclude the application of the other.

α, β etc. variables whose coefficients range over all the possible values of a feature.

0 normally means the absence of a feature; e.g. [0 nasal] = non-nasal. However, with a feature such as stricture where 0 does not mean absence, $\emptyset$ is used to mean the complete absence of a feature (for an explanation of this convention, cf. Williamson 1976:21).

1, 2 etc. mean -1 (minus 1), -2 (minus 2), etc.

- * asterik placed before any element or string shows that the element or string is ungrammatical or deviant.
- = morpheme (or formative) boundary.
- + word boundary
- # phrase boundary
- § Syllable boundary
- indicates the position of a vowel whose quality cannot be determined because of contraction. e.g. vb-òwá (vbV + òwá 'in the house).

The following are some of the abbreviations used in the work. Others will be introduced in the relevant sections.

- C any consonant, i.e. any segment which is [≥ 0 stricture] (any segment which has the value 0 or more of stricture).
- V any vowel, i.e. any segment which is [$\leq \underline{1}$ stricture] (any segment which has the value 1 or less of stricture).
- F any non-tonal feature or combination of features.

- L a segmental low tone; i.e., one which is borne by a segment.
- H a segmental high tone.
- a floating low tone; i.e. one which is not borne by any segment.
- a floating high tone (cf. 0.3.).

CHAPTER I

THE PHONOLOGICAL FEATURES AND SEGMENTS

1.0. Introduction

In this chapter we shall attempt to define the set of distinctive features which are required for a phonological description of the Edo (Bini) language. The distinctive features for consonants and vowels proposed here derive mainly from Williamson's (1976) features for consonants, Lindau's (1975) vowel features and Ladefoged's (1971, 1975) features for consonants and vowels. We also propose multivalued features to account for tone and boundary. At the end a fully specified matrix of the phonological segments of Edo (Bini) is provided.

1.1. Functions of distinctive features

As is generally accepted by practitioners of generative phonology, we regard distinctive features as performing two essential functions; namely, to classify the distinctive sounds of a language by specifying the contrasts between them and to specify

the phonetic properties of the sounds of the language by defining the features in terms of some intrinsic phonetic properties.

Deriving from these basic functions of distinctive features are two other functions. The first is that distinctive features make possible the definition of natural classes of sounds; any grouping of sounds which share some feature or features constitute a natural class whereas sounds which share no feature cannot constitute a natural class. In this way, expected natural patterns of sounds can be distinguished from unexpected (i.e. unnatural) ones. For example, the fact that the grouping /p b t d k g/ is more natural than /p b f w l ε/ is evident from the fact that all members of the former group share the same value of stricture (i.e. [2 stricture]) whereas the members of the latter share no value of stricture (or any other feature).

The second other function of distinctive features is that describing phonological processes in terms of them also makes possible an explanation of such processes.

For example, a rule such as 1:

$$1. \quad [\underline{\leq} \underline{1} \text{ strict.}] \rightarrow [1 \text{ nasal}] / \left[\begin{array}{l} (20) \text{ strict.} \\ 1 \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] -$$

makes easier an explanation of the process of vowel nasalization in Edo (Bini) than 2:

$$2. \quad \left[\begin{array}{c} i \\ e \\ \epsilon \\ a \\ \text{ɔ} \\ o \\ u \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{ĩ} \\ \text{ē} \\ \text{ē} \\ \text{ã} \\ \text{õ} \\ \text{õ} \\ \text{ũ} \end{array} \right] / [m] -$$

In setting up distinctive features, therefore, we should prefer those features which while accounting for the phonetic facts also facilitate the explanation of phonological processes.

1.2. Multivalued Distinctive Features

The SPE framework permits only binary distinctive features at the systematic phonemic level. However, a number of proposals for having multivalued distinctive features within the framework of generative phonology -

notably Contreras (1969), Ladefoged (1971, 1975), Lindau (1975) and Williamson (1976) - have been made since the publication of SPE.

Of all the proposals for having multivalued distinctive features that we are familiar with Williamson's is the only one that has explicitly spelled out certain universal conditions under which it is preferable to set up multivalued features. These are:

1. If the plus values of two 'binary' features cannot co-occur, the possibility should be examined that they constitute part of a single multivalued feature (p. 4.).

(This means that vowel height, for instance, which is accounted for by two binary features high and low in the SPE system, may actually require a single scalar feature).

2. A multivalued feature should be set up where assimilation or weakening, etc., clearly takes place in stages along a scale (p. 5.)

A good example of 2 is found in some sound changes where stops weaken through fricatives to approximants and are sometimes eventually dropped.

As Williamson points out, neither of these two conditions is sufficient by itself; they should always be taken together. For example, though it is not possible to combine the plus values of pharyngal and lateral, we cannot on that account set up these two as values of a single feature. In addition to not being able to combine their plus values, two features should constitute a phonetic scale before they can be combined into a single multivalued feature.

We believe that these conditions proposed by Williamson are sufficient and adequate for assessing proposals for multivalued distinctive features. We shall, therefore, ensure that the multivalued features adopted or proposed in this work satisfy these conditions.

There are at least two advantages in using multivalued distinctive features. The first is that multivalued features account more accurately for phonetic facts. For example, it is far more accurate to represent relationships along a continuous phonetic scale with one multivalued feature rather than several binary features.

The second advantage of multivalued features is the fact that certain redundancies which are stated as restrictions on binary distinctive features are eliminated. For example, if we were to account for vowel height with the SPE features high and low, we would require a special redundancy rule to prevent the plus values of the two features from co-occurring, whereas this is not necessary with a multivalued feature for vowel height.

1.3. Conventions for Specifying Distinctive features

Williamson (1976) also proposes certain conventions for specifying the distinctive features of segments in a way to account most accurately for the phonetic facts of their production. We shall draw attention to these conventions here and also introduce one other convention which we have found necessary to adopt in this work.

In the past more than one value of the same feature could not be specified in a single segment. This was the case even with Ladefoged's multivalued features. As a result, phenomena such as double articulation and

nasality were accounted for in an ad hoc manner. For example, SPE (311) proposes to treat doubly articulated labial-velars either as labials with extreme velarization or as velars with extreme labialization, thus making no distinction between secondary and double articulations. Even Ladefoged (1975: 262) treats double articulations as the interaction of two features, place and labial, which wrongly implies that all double articulations consist of a labial articulation and one other.¹

To avoid the type of ad hoc feature specifications just mentioned Williamson proposes that the specification of more than one value of a feature in a segment be allowed in generative phonology. In this way we can account for double articulations by specifying two simultaneous values of place. The simultaneity of the articulation is shown by placing the two values of the feature within parentheses. Thus, for example, kp and gb will be [(39)]'place] (cf. 1.4.1.2. for the values of place).

1. Williamson (1976: 23) cites the Swedish alveolar-palatal/velar fricative mentioned by Abercrombie (1967: 64-5) as an example of a doubly articulated sound which does not involve a labial articulation.

Extending this convention, we can account for nasal and lateral articulations as involving two simultaneous values of stricture - a primary stop articulation and an additional approximant articulation which allows air to escape freely either through the nose or over the sides of the ^tongue. A nasalized lateral will then be specified for three simultaneous values of stricture. Thus *m* and *l* will be [(20) stricture] while [*l̃*] will be [(200) stricture].

Two or more values of the same feature may also occur sequentially, as in the production of affricates. In order to capture this fact more accurately, Williamson also proposes that the specification of two or more values of the same features sequentially be allowed. This is done by writing the values one after the other. Thus the affricates *tʃ* and *dʒ* will be [21 stricture]. As pointed out by Williamson, this convention eliminates the need for all features which are basically devices for expressing sequence, such as the SPE delayed release and Ladegoged's ^fprenasalized.

Where two or more values of a feature are specified sequentially in a segment, the presence and absence of

another co-occurring feature coinciding with the different aspects of the sequentially occurring feature will be stated below or above that aspect of the sequentially occurring feature with which they coincide. Thus a stop with nasal plosion, such as $[b^N]$, will be specified for the features strictures and nasal as follows:

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} 2(20) \text{ stricture} \\ 0 \ 1 \ \text{nasal} \end{array} \right]$$

This shows that nasality occurs only in the release stage in this segment (cf. Williamson p. 44.).

In some phonological rules we will have to state two (or more) alternative values of the same feature within a single segment. We adopt the convention of stating this by writing a comma between the two values of the feature; e.g. [2, 3 high] means either [2 high] or [3 high] (cf. 3.1.3.).

To clarify the conventions for stating the different types of articulation in terms of the features place and stricture, we reproduce Table 1 from Williamson (Table 13, p. 52).

TABLE 1POSSIBLE TYPES OF ARTICULATION

	Simple	Double	Additional	Sequential	Secondary
Stricture	A	A	(AB)	AB	AB
Place	X	(XY)	X	X	XY

A, B, represent any values of stricture

X, Y, represent any values of place

Parentheses represent simultaneous articulation.

Obviously, these conventions allow us to account for the phonetic facts of a language more accurately. To take a small example, Ladefoged (1975: 263) says that since **l** behaves like a stop in some languages (such as Luganda) and like an approximant in some others (such as **English**), we sometimes have to classify it as [+ stop] and at other times as [- stop]. This is a rather inconsistent way to treat a sound which is produced in the same way all the time. This problem would not arise if we follow the conventions just outlined, by which a lateral is always specified as [(20) stricture], a specification which captures its simultaneous stop and approximant characteristics.

1.4. The Features

We shall now define the features which we have selected as necessary for a phonological description of Edo (Bini). Features which have no relevance for Edo (Bini) phonology are not discussed. The features are treated under four headings - features for consonants, features for vowels, tone features and boundary feature. This division is not meant to be rigid since vowel and consonant features sometimes overlap.

1.4.1. Features for Consonants ,

1.4.1.1. Stricture

Stricture is a scalar feature which accounts for the degree of approximation of the articulators. It has six values:

- 2 Stop
- 1 Fricative
- 0 Approximant
- 1 (i.e. -1) close vowel
- 2 (i.e. -2) non-close vowel
- ∅ zero (absence of any stricture)

Extending the stricture scale to vowel articulations allows us to account for the assimilation of vowels to consonants in stricture (and vice versa) in a natural way. For example, Williamson (1976: 11-17) gives ↓jɔ examples of non-close vowels becoming close in the environment of consonants, and she interprets this as the assimilation of the vowels to the consonants in stricture. Only two values of stricture (i.e. 1 and 2) account for vowels because so far there is no evidence that more than these two are needed to account for the movement of vowels along the stricture scale (cf. Williamson 1976: 21).

The zero value of stricture will be useful in specifying floating tones; these will be specified as

[∅ stricture
 α tone]

Since in Edo (Bini) only vowels can be syllabic, it will often be sufficient to specify vowels as [α 1 stricture] and ignore the feature syllabic.

As already pointed out, certain sounds will be specified with two values of stricture either simultaneously or sequentially. For example, laterals and

nasals have the simultaneous specification (20), while nasally released plosives are sequentially specified with 2(20).

1.4.1.2. Place

This feature specifies the area along the passive articulator towards which the active articulator makes ~~an~~ an articulatory movement, or where the active/passive distinction cannot be made, the area where the articulation of a sound takes place.

Williamson, partly following the SPE idea of the neutral position, proposes to have the central vowel area as the neutral position for place. She then numbers the values of place from this point positively towards the bilabial region and negatively towards the glottis. Another reason she gives for regarding the central vowel position as the neutral position for place is the fact that "of the three most common places of articulation for consonants (labial, alveolar/dental, velar) it is the velar one, adjacent to the central one, which most commonly weakens or is lost entirely" (p. 31).

However, we are not adopting this concept here since it is still doubtful to us. We shall therefore, following Ladegoged (1971), label the values of this feature from the glottis towards the bilabial region. We, however, follow Williamson's divisions of the passive articulator (except that we exclude the central vowel area).

- 0 glottis (glottal)
- 1 back wall of pharynx (pharyngeal)
- 2 uvular area (post velar, uvular)
- 3 velum (velar)
- 4 hard palate (palatal)
- 5 behind alveolar ridge
(post-alveolar, palato-alveolar)
- 6 alveolar ridge (alveolar)
- 7 behind upper teeth (dental)
- 8 upper teeth (labiodental)
- 9 upper lip (bilabial).

To specify consonant contrasts in Edo (Bini) only six values of place (0, 3, 4, 6, 8, and 9) will be required.

With this feature double articulations will be specified with two simultaneous values of place while secondary articulation will be specified with two sequential values. For example, the labial-velar stops *kp* and *gb* will be specified as [(39) place] while the velarized lateral will be specified as [63 place].

1.4.1.3. Nasal

A nasal sound is one during the production of which air escapes through the nose. This feature is binary:

1 nasal (air escapes completely or partially through the nose)

0 oral

Nasal consonants, nasalized consonants and vowels, and stops produced with nasal plosion or prenasalization will all be specified as [1 nasal].

1.4.1.4. Lateral

A lateral sound is one during the production of which there is a central blockage of the air stream accompanied by simultaneous escape of air over the sides of the tongue.

This feature is also binary:

- 1 lateral
- 0 non-lateral

1.4.1.5. Trill

During the production of a trill the active articulator is held loosely near the passive articulator "so that the flow of air between them sets them in motion, alternately sucking them and blowing them apart"² (cf. Ladefoged 1975 p. 147). This feature is binary:

- 1 trill
- 0 non-trill

There are two trill sounds in Edo (Bini) - the voiced [r] (orthographic rr) and the voiceless [ɾ] (orthographic rh).

1.4.1.6. Length

Williamson (1976: 56ff.), drawing on investigations by Ladefoged, Elugbe,³ Laver and Fajen (among others) has suggested that the basic parameter which distinguishes

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2. Carl Hoffmann has drawn our attention to the fact that this definition is not quite accurate because it is only the active articulator that actually moves.
 3. Elugbe's views on the feature of length are scattered in various publications. He has, however, put these views together in a forthcoming paper - On the wider application of the term 'tap' - in which he also follows Williamson in proposing the feature length.

taps and most other sounds, is length; taps are shorter than most other sounds. We shall, following Williamson, set up the following values of length.

- 1 long consonants and vowels
- 0 normal (trills, stops, fricatives
vowels, etc.)

In Edo (Bini) the tapped lateral [ɺ] (orthographic r) will be [1 length] while the trills [r] and [ɽ], the normal lateral and all other sounds in the language will be [0 length].

1.4.1.7. Glottal State^{4,5}

This feature specifies the various states of the glottis. "The physiological scale corresponding to it is the degree of approximation of the arytenoid

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- 4. This feature has been differently labelled by Ladefoged as glottal stricture (1971: 17) and voice (1975: 261). The name glottal state, first proposed by Williamson (1976), is preferred over glottal stricture because it helps to avoid any confusion with the feature stricture employed in this work.
 - 5. This feature, like stricture and nasal, is rather arbitrarily grouped under features for consonants, just like syllabic (1.4.2.4.) is arbitrarily grouped under vowel features. Actually, all these features characterize both consonants and vowels.

cartilages." (Ladefoged 1975: 261). The distance between the cartilages is greater for voiceless sounds and far less for voiced sounds.

This feature has five values:

- 1 glottal stop
- 2 laryngealized
- 3 voiced
- 4 murmur
- 5 voiceless

Only two values of glottal state, 3 and 5, are required in Edo (Bini).

1.4.2. Vowel Features

SPE distinguishes vowels with the binary features high, low, back, round and tense. The features high and low account for oppositions along the vertical axis of the vowel area and finer distinctions along this axis such as between two non-back high vowels are taken care of by the feature tense; e.g. $i = [+ \text{tense}]$, $\text{ɪ} = [-\text{tense}]$. But as pointed out by Williamson (1976) the fact that the positive values of high and low cannot co-occur is an indication that what we really need is a multivalued scalar feature.

SPE also fails to accurately distinguish central vowels. The usual specification of central vowels as $\left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{back} \\ -\text{round} \end{array} \right]$ (cf. SPE: 176) is inadequate because there are non-central vowels with the same specification. Here again we need a scalar feature to account for all possible oppositions along the horizontal axis of the vowel area.

Lindau (1975), following Ladefoged (1964), among others, has pointed out that there is not a good correspondence between the highest point of the tongue on the vertical and horizontal axes of the vowel area and the way in which corresponding vowels are located on a vowel chart. She then provides evidence to show that acoustic parameters provide better correlates of vowel height and backness.

We shall follow Lindau (1975) and Ladefoged (1975) in defining our vowel features in acoustic terms. Unlike Lindau, however, and like Ladefoged, we retain the traditional labels for vowel height and backness purely for ease of reference.

1.4.2.1. Height

This feature is characterized by the inverse of the frequency of the first formant; low vowels have a relatively low first formant (Lindau 1975: 8; Ladefoged 1975: 265). This feature is labelled F_1 by Lindau.

There are five values of height assigned as follows (cf. Lindau, 1975: 27).

- 0 approximant
- 1 close
- 2 half-close
- 3 half-open
- 4 open

The zero value of height allows us to account for the changes from vowel to approximant. Thus height and stricture interact at the approximant stage, what Williamson (1976: 20) calls the "glide interface".

1.4.2.2. Back

The feature back is characterized by the inverse of the difference between the frequency of the second formant and that of the first formant. (Lindau 1975: 11, Ladefoged 1975: 265). This feature is labelled $F_2 - F_1$

by Lindau.

There are three values of back:

- 1 front
- 2 central
- 3 back

1.4.2.3. Expanded

This feature distinguishes vowels according to variations in the size of the pharynx, as controlled by variation in the position of the root of the tongue and the larynx (Lindau 1975: 16ff.; Ladefoged 1975: 266.⁶ Ladefoged (1975) labels this feature as wide.

Expanded has two values:

- 1 expanded pharynx
- 0 unexpanded pharynx

In Edo (Bini) the vowels i, u, e, o are [1 expanded] while ε, ɔ, a are [0 expanded].

1.4.2.4. Syllabic

Syllabic sounds are sounds which constitute a syllabic peak (SPE: 354). This feature has no articula-

-
6. Although no instrumental investigation of this phenomenon in Edo (Bini) has been undertaken, we impressionistically feel that the mechanism of expanded pharynx is at work in distinguishing the vowels of the language. Another advantage of this feature is that it makes it easier to explain certain phonological processes which are clearly remnants of vowel harmony in the language.

tory or acoustic correlates. It is however essential in capturing the relationship of segments to syllable structure.⁷ In Edo (Bini) only vowels can be syllabic, although vowels may become non-syllabic through the application of some phonological rules. The feature has two values:

- 1 syllabic
- 0 non-syllabic

1.4.3. Tone Features

1.4.3.1. Previous Proposals

Various sets of features for handling tone have been proposed. In this review we shall ignore those features proposed for handling contour tones since we do not recognize underlying contour tones in Edo (Bini).

Gruber (1964)⁸ proposes two features, High and High 2, which can specify four contrastive tone levels.

-
- 7. Williamson (1976: 86) eliminates the feature syllabic in the hope of **integrating** syllable structure into the theoretical framework.
 - 8. We have not been able to see Gruber (1964). This summary of Gruber's proposal is taken from Maddieson (1971) and Fromkin (1972).

Wang (1967) accepts Gruber's High but proposes two additional features in place of High 2 - Central and Mid. This system, unlike Gruber's, can account for five distinctive tone levels. Sampson (1969) replaces Wang's Mid with Low so that he has High, Central and Low.

Maddieson (1971) substitutes the features Raised and Lowered for High and Low. Maddieson's labelling has two advantages -

- (i) it "avoids possible confusion between the features [high] and [low] used to denote tongue height and features for the parameter of pitch" (p. 7) and
- (ii) it also avoids "a possible confusion between names of tones like High, Low, Mid etc. and features for indicating them" (p. 7).

Maddieson introduces a third feature, Extreme, to account for pitch which is "extended further towards the upper or lower limits of the voice range in normal speech" (p. 7). With this feature the Maddieson system can account for five distinctive tone levels.

Halle (1971) relates pitch distinctions to vocal cord stiffness and proposes two binary features - [Stiff Vocal Cords] and [Slack Vocal Cords] to account for three tone levels. The most obvious problem with the Halle features is the fact that there is no way they can distinguish more than three tone levels.

Fromkin (1972: 58) rejects the Maddieson and Halle systems because, according to her, they make wrong markedness predictions with tone systems which have downstep tones. Using either the Maddieson or Halle features the downstep tone (being mid or nearest to mid) will come out as the unmarked tone, which is counter-intuitive. As a result she proposes "that the universal set of Distinctive Features include three features: High, Mid, Low" (p. 60). However, it seems that there is not much justification for rejecting a set of tone features on account of wrong markedness predictions, especially as Fromkin herself has, apparently correctly, suggested that it is not possible to determine a universal unmarked tone since tone systems evolve historically in different ways (p. 60).

1.4.3.2. The Present Proposal

It would appear that what is basically wrong with all the tone feature systems so far proposed is that they account for pitch with binary features. Tone should clearly be treated with a scalar feature. This is the only way to avoid redundancies such as the non-occurrence of the positive values of High and Low or Raised and Lowered. In fact, all pitch levels constitute a continuum from the highest to the lowest pitch.

We, therefore, propose to account for tone with a scalar feature tone. This name is chosen because other names of tone features, such as High and Low or Raised and Lowered, presuppose a neutral position for tone. It also reflects the conventional distinction between tone and pitch; tone being the abstract phonological entity and pitch the concrete phonetic realization of tone.

This feature has a maximum of five values at the systematic phonemic level:

- 1 extra high
- 2 high

- 3 mid
- 4 low
- 5 extra low

(These values of the feature tone are suggested after Maddieson 1971).

Since there are only two contrastive tone levels - high and low - in Edo (Bini), only two values of tone (2 and 4) will need to be specified at the systematic phonemic level.

1.4.4. Boundaries

The underlying phonological representation of an Edo (Bini) utterance consists of two types of units - boundaries and segments. The segments are the consonants, vowels and tones (which may or may not be borne by vowels), while the boundaries are the junctures which operate within and between words. Three types of boundaries can be clearly identified in Edo (Bini). These are the formative (or morpheme) boundary (symbolized =), word boundary (symbolized +) and phrase boundary (symbolized #).

SPE (364-371) accounts for boundaries with the binary features segment, formative boundary and word boundary. But boundaries clearly constitute a continuous scale ranging from the weakest (i.e. formative boundary) to the strongest (i.e. phrase boundary). We therefore propose a multivalued feature, boundary, to account for all boundaries. This feature has the following values:

- 1 formative boundary (FB)
- 2 word boundary (WB)
- 3 phrase boundary (PB)

By the nature of boundaries, a stronger boundary always implies a weaker one but not vice versa. Thus [3 boundary], i.e. phrase boundary, implies [2 boundary] and [1 boundary], while [2 boundary] implies [1 boundary]. Therefore if, for example, both word boundary and formative boundary are affected by a rule, we need to specify only word boundary.

1.4.5. The Value Zero

The value zero (0) has been assigned to features in three different ways. In binary features, such as **nasal** and **lateral**, zero always represents the absence value.

Usually, it is the neutral or more common value of the feature.

In two multivalued scalar features - stricture and length - the zero value is placed in the centre of the scale. It represents the normal or neutral value of length, while it represents the point of interaction (which is in one sense a neutral point) of consonants and vowels along the stricture scale.

In the case of the features height and place, the zero value occurs at one end of the scale. The zero value of height is meant to reflect the relationship between vowels and approximants, just as it does in stricture. But in the case of the feature place, the assignment of a zero value is primarily an ad hoc device for avoiding the two digit number 10 which would have been assigned to the bilabial place of articulation if we labelled from 1 (one). (A two-digit number such as 10 can easily be confused with two co-occurring values of a feature). However, the assignment of zero to the glottal place of articulation has the advantage of reflecting the fact that glottal is different from other places of articulation in that the active/passive

distinction cannot be made there.

1.4.6. Summary of Proposed Features

The features proposed for use in this study are listed below. The relevant section of this chapter where a feature is discussed is indicated in parentheses after each feature.

1. Stricture (1.4.1.1.)

There are six values of stricture:

- 2 stop
- 1 fricative
- 0 approximant
- 1 close vowel
- 2 non-close vowel
- ∅ zero (absence of any stricture)

2. Place (1.4.1.2.)

This feature has ten values:

- 0 glottis (glottal)
- 1 back wall of pharynx (pharyngeal).
- 2 uvular area (post velar, uvular).
- 3 velum (velar)
- 4 hard palate (palatal)

- 5 behind alveolar ridge (post alveolar,
palato-alveolar)
 - 6 alveolar ridge (alveolar)
 - 7 behind upper teeth (dental)
 - 8 upper teeth (labiodental)
 - 9 upper lip (bilabial)
3. Nasal (1.4.1.3.)
- 1 nasal
 - 0 oral
4. Lateral (1.4.1.4.)
- 1 lateral
 - 0 non-lateral
5. Trill (1.4.1.5.)
- 1 trill
 - 0 non-trill
6. Length (1.4.1.6.)
- 1 long consonants and vowels
 - 0 normal (trills, stops, fricatives, etc.)
 - 1 short (taps, lenis sounds)
7. Glottal state (1.4.1.7.)
- 1 glottal stop
 - 2 laryngealized

- 3 voiced
- 4 murmur
- 5 voiceless

8. Height (1.4.2.1.)

- 0 approximant
- 1 close
- 2 half-close
- 3 half-open
- 4 open

9. Back (1.4.2.2.)

- 1 front
- 2 central
- 3 back

10. Expanded (1.4.2.3.)

- 1 expanded pharynx
- 0 unexpanded pharynx

11. Syllabic (1.4.2.4.)

- 1 syllabic
- 0 non-syllabic

12. Tone (1.4.3.2.)

- 1 extra high
- 2 high
- 3 mid
- 4 low
- 5 extra low

13. Boundary (1.4.4.)

- 1 formative boundary (FB)
- 2 word boundary (WB)
- 3 phrase boundary (PB)

1.4.7. Maximally Specified Phonological Segments of Edo (Bini)

Every segment is specified as a single-column matrix of distinctive features. Table II provides a fully specified distinctive feature matrix of the phonological segments of Edo (Bini). Separate matrices are provided for consonants and vowels because essentially different features are required for specifying them. We have provided no matrix for tones since the specification of tones is rather straightforward - a vowel segment is marked as having either 2 tone or 4 tone.

TABLE II
MAXIMALLY SPECIFIED PHONOLOGICAL SEGMENTS OF EDO (BINI)

A: The Consonants

	p	b	t	d	k	g	kp	gb	m	f	v	s	z	x	ɣ	h	l	ɓ	r	ɹ	u	j	w
Stricture	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	(20)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	(20)	(20)	2	2	0	0	0
Place	9	9	6	6	3	3	(39)	(39)	9	8	8	6	6	3	3	0	6	6	6	6	8	4	(39)
Lateral	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Length	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Trill	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Glottal state	5	3	5	3	5	3	5	3	3	5	3	5	3	5	3	5	3	3	3	5	3	3	3
Nasal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Syllabic	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

B: The Vowels

TABLE II

	i	e	ɛ	a	ɔ	o	u	ĩ	ẽ	ã	õ	ũ
Height	1	2	3	4	3	2	1	1	3	4	3	1
Back	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	1	1	2	3	3
Expanded	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
Nasal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
Structure	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>1</u>
Glottal State	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Syllabic	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Length	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

CHAPTER II

LEXICAL AND PHONETIC REDUNDANCIES

2.0. We shall in this chapter attempt to state the lexical and phonetic redundancies revealed by the Edo (Bini) language. Within the generative phonology framework lexical or phonological redundancies are stated by means of morpheme structure conditions (MSCs). Following Shibatani (1973) we introduce surface phonetic constraints (SPCs) to account for redundancies which hold at the phonetic level (cf. 0.2.3). Also following Shibatani we label constraints which hold at both the lexical and the phonetic levels as M/SPCs. However, we group M/SPCs along with MSCs while SPCs proper are treated separately.

The MSCs and SPCs differ from the P-rules in a number of ways. MSCs belong to the lexicon and apply before the phonological representation is reached and SPCs belong to the phonetic level, whereas P-rules relate the underlying phonological representation to the surface phonetic representation. Moreover, MSCs and SPCs can only state which representations are

permissible and which are not; they cannot, like P-rules, add, delete or permute segments. The MSCs and SPCs are also unordered, unlike P-rules.

2.1. The Morpheme Structure Conditions

The MSCs which follow are far fewer than they would have been if we had not employed multivalued distinctive features. The use of multivalued features especially saves on universal segment structure conditions. For instance, most of the redundancies resulting from the SPE place of articulation features are eliminated because we have only one feature which specifies articulatory place (cf. 1.2.).

2.1.1. Segment Structure Conditions

Two types of SgSCs are distinguished - the universal and the language-specific. The former states universal constraints on feature combinations of individual phonemes while the latter states language-specific constraints on feature combinations.

2.1.1.1. Universal SgSC

1. SgSC 1.

I : [(XO) stricture]

↓ ↓

T : [0 trill]

(where X could be naught or 2).

According to this condition, any segment which has 0 as its value, or part of its value, of stricture cannot be a trill.

2. SgSC 2.

I : [1 stricture]

↓ ↓

T : [0 trill]

This condition states that a fricative is always non-trill

2.1.1.2. Language-Specific SgSCs

3. SgSC 3. (M/SPC).

I : [≥ 0 stricture]

↓ ↓

T : [0 syllabic]

This condition states that any segment which has a value of zero or more of stricture (i.e. any consonant) is redundantly non-syllabic. In other words, there are no syllabic consonants in the language.

This constraint holds at both the lexical and phonetic levels.

✓ 4. SgSC 4.

I : [1 syllabic]
 ↓ ↓
 T : [≤ 1 stricture]

Condition ⁴~~3~~ states that all syllabic segments have stricture of 1 or lower value; i.e. they are all vowels.

✓ 5. SgSC 5.

I : [≤ (X0) stricture]
 ↓ ↓
 T : [3 glottal state]

(where X could be naught or 2).

SgSc 4 states that any segment which has zero or lower number as its specification or part of its simultaneous specification of stricture (i.e. vowels,

approximants, laterals and nasals) are redundantly voiced.

6. SgSC 6.

I : [2 height]

T : [0 nasal]

This condition states that the half-close vowels /e/ and /o/ are redundantly non-nasal in the language.

✓ 7. SgSC 7.

I : [1 lateral]

T : [6 place]

Any lateral sound in the language is produced in the alveolar region.

8. SgSC 8.

I : [(20) stricture
1 nasal]

T : [9 place]

The only nasal stop permitted in lexical representations in the language is the bilabial nasal /m/.

9. SgSC 9. (M/SPC).

I : [1 trill]
 ↓ ↓
 T : [6 place]

Any trill in the language is produced in the alveolar region.

10. SgSC 10. (M/SPC).

I : [1 stricture]
 ↓ ↓
 T : [0 lateral]

There are no lateral fricatives in the language.

11. SgSC 11 (M/SPC).

I : [1 stricture]
 ↓ ↓
 T : [0 nasal]

There are no nasal fricatives in the language.

12. SgSC 12.

I : [0 stricture]

↓ ↓

T : [0 nasal]

The language does not have nasal approximants.

13. SgSC 13.

I : [$\geq$ 1 stricture]

↓ ↓

T : [0 length]

This condition states that fricatives and stops have the normal value of length, i.e. they are neither long nor short.

14. SgSC 14.

I : [1 syllabic]

↓ ↓

T : [0 length]

All vowels have the normal value of length; in other words, there are no long or short vowels in the language.

✓ 15. SgSC 15 (M/SPC).

I : [1, 2 height]

↓ ↓

T : [1 expanded]

Any (vowel) segment which is close or half-close is redundantly specified as [1 expanded].

✓ 16. SgSC 16 (M/SPC).

I : [3, 4 height]

↓ ↓

T : [0 expanded]

Any (vowel) segment which is either half-open or open is redundantly unexpanded.

2.1.1.3. Minimally Specified Phonological Segments of Edo (Bini)

The above SgSCs help us to save a number of features in the lexical entries of the phonological segments of the language. Table III reflects the amount of redundancies in the structures of the phonological

TABLE III

MINIMALLY SPECIFIED PHONOLOGICAL SEGMENTS OF EDO (BINI)

A : The Consonants

	p	b	t	d	k	g	kp	gb	m	f	v	s	z	x	y	h	l	ɺ	r	ɹ	u	j	w
Structure	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	(20)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	(20)	(20)	2	2	0	0	0
Place	9	9	6	6	3	3	(39)	(39)		8	8	6	6	3	3	0					8	4	(39)
Lateral	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Length									0								0	1			0	0	0
Trill	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0											1	1			
Glottal State	5	3	5	3	5	3	5	3		5	3	5	3	5	3	5			3	5			
Nasal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1								0	0	0	0			
Syllabic																							

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TABLE III

B : The Vowels

	i	e	ɛ	a	ɔ	o	u	ɪ	ẽ	ã	õ	ũ
Height	1	2	3	4	3	2	1	1	3	4	3	1
Back	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	1	1	2	3	3
Expanded												
Nasal	0		0	0	0		0	1	1	1	1	1
Stricture												
Syllabic												
Glottal State												
Length												

segments. Features which should be saved with respect to particular segments are left unspecified for such segments.

2.1.2. Sequence Structure Conditions (SqSCs)

Two types of SqSCs will be stated - the general SqSCs which state constraints that hold for all lexical formatives and those SqSCs which state constraints that hold for specific lexical categories of formatives.

2.1.2.1. General Sequence Structure Conditions

17. SqSC 1.

$$\text{PC : } \left[\underset{\text{FORM}}{=} X \text{ CV}(V) ((CV)V) = \underset{\text{FORM}}{\quad} \right]$$

(where X = V or Zero)

This PC states the canonical form of Edo (Bini) lexical formatives. An Edo (Bini) lexical formative obligatorily has a CV sequence. If there is only one consonant we can have a sequence of up to three vowels; otherwise we can have no more than two vowels in a sequence.

The following are examples of Edo (Bini) lexical formatives.

dε	"buy"
kpolo	"sweep"
sɔɔ	"tear"
òwá	"house"
ègùàè	"palace"
òghè dè	"plantain"

18. SqSC 2 (M/SPC).

This condition states that if the first vowel in a sequence of two vowels is non-high (i.e. one which has a value of 2 or more of height) then the second vowel

will also be non-high.¹ This constraint holds at both the lexical and phonetic levels.

-
1. There are two words - *ìhòì* "nothing" and *ólóí* "a king's wife" which seem not to obey this constraint. These words are, however, analysed as having underlying final CV syllables. To demonstrate the correctness of this analysis we can compare these words with those which have final vowel sequences with identical tones, such as *ègúí* "tortoise" and *èkhùè* "shame". In words of the latter type the final vowels get converted into a diphthong by the diphthongization rule (cf. 3.2.3.3.), so that *ègúí* becomes *ègwí* and *èkhùè* becomes *èkhwè* phonetically, whereas the final vowels of *ólóí* and *ìhòì* do not get converted into a diphthong.

Thus, for example, when *ólóí* and *ègwí* occur in constructions in which a final nominal high tone changes to a low tone, *ègwí* becomes *ègwì* while *ólóí* becomes *ólóì*. E.g.

1. *ègwí n-ò dèé* "the tortoise that is coming"
2. *ólóí n-ò dèé* "the king's wife who is coming"

The behaviour of *ólóí* exactly parallels that of words with final CV, such as *ùkéké* "stick" in such constructions.

E.g. *ùkéké n-ò kpòlò* "a stick that is big"

The following examples will illustrate:

ékhòè	"mind"
úhàè	"well"
éyáè	"neck"

2.1.2.2. Major Lexical Categories

The MSCs in this section state constraints on the co-occurrence of segments within the nominal and verb morphemes. Items belonging to the other lexical categories are usually similar to nominals and verbs in structure. In the NP the adjectival and pronoun qualifiers are, however, different from nominals in structure while in the VP only the subject concord marker and, of course, the nominal are essentially different from verbs in structure (cf. chapter IV).

2.1.2.2.1. Nominal Sequence Structure Conditions

19. SqSC 3.

$$PC : \left[\begin{array}{l} = VCV(V)((CV)(V))^n = \\ \text{Nom.} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{Nom.} \end{array} \right]$$

This condition states that a nominal has a minimal VCV structure. Theoretically a nominal morpheme can be

of any length although in reality morphemes with more than three consonants are not common.

The following are examples of nominals in Edo (Bini).

òdḗ	"road"
ḡnà	"this one"
àbábè	"witchcraft"
ùgbòlòkò	"bone"
èkpàkpàhúvbàgà	"scorpion"
ìròghàè	(an age grade)
ègùàè	"palace"

20. SqSC 4.

$$I : \left[\begin{array}{l} = [1 \text{ syllabic}] \\ \text{Nom.} \quad \downarrow \downarrow \end{array} \right. X = \left. \begin{array}{l} \\ \text{Nom.} \end{array} \right]$$

T : [0 nasal]

(where X stands for any permissible combination of consonants and vowels).

This condition states that the initial vowel of a nominal is always oral.

followed by one vowel.

Examples:

de	"buy"
kpolo	"sweep"
khũɔvbĩ	"be ill"
fuɔfua	"be white"
rhaa	"steal"

2.2. Surface Phonetic Constraints

SPCs will be discussed under the following headings
 - general morpheme structure, general syllable structure, verb syllable structure, constraints on vowel and consonant sequences, and syllables and tone.

2.2.1. General Morpheme Structure

25. SPC 1.

$$PC : X \left[\begin{array}{l} \leq 1 \text{ strict.} \\ \neq \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{l} \leq 1 \text{ strict.} \\ \neq \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] \left(\left[\begin{array}{l} \leq 1 \text{ strict.} \\ \neq \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] \right) Y$$

(where X and Y stand for any permissible combinations of consonants and vowels).

This constraint states that whenever two or three

vowels (they may or may not be syllabic) occur in a sequence, they must all agree in nasality. The following examples will illustrate.

rhàá	"steal"
khìó	"cork"
rhàá	"open"
ègwàè	"palace"
òrhwáè	"in-law"

2.2.2. General Syllable Structure

26. SPC 2.

PC : $\text{ɕ} (\text{C}(\underline{\text{V}})) \text{V}(\underline{\text{V}}) \text{ɕ}$

This PC states that an Edo (Bini) syllable obligatorily has one syllabic vowel. It can optionally have an initial consonant which may or may not be followed by a non-syllabic vowel, and/or one final non-syllabic vowel. The following examples will illustrate.

ɕ	á	ɕ	dá	ɕ	"state sword"
ɕ	è	ɕ	gwí	ɕ	"tortoise"
ɕ	è	ɕ	gwàè	ɕ	"palace"

27. SPC 3.

NC : - $\text{ʃ } c^{\circ} \underline{v} \text{ } v \text{ } (\underline{v}) \text{ } \text{ʃ}$

This negative condition states that it is not possible to have a syllable which has one or two non-syllabic vowels but no initial consonant. In other words, whenever there is a syllable without a consonant, that syllable must be made up of only one syllabic vowel and no other segment.

By this condition, syllables such as * $\text{ʃ } a\underline{e} \text{ } \text{ʃ}$, * $\text{ʃ } \underline{o}e \text{ } \text{ʃ}$ and * $\text{ʃ } \underline{e}e \text{ } \text{ʃ}$ are ruled out whereas syllables such as $\text{ʃ } kha\underline{e} \text{ } \text{ʃ}$, $\text{ʃ } to\underline{e} \text{ } \text{ʃ}$ and $\text{ʃ } gh\underline{e} \text{ } \text{ʃ}$ are permissible.

2.2.3. Verb Syllable Structure

28. SPC 4.

I : $\left[\begin{array}{l} \text{ʃ} \\ \text{VS} \end{array} \right] \left[\leq 0 \text{ strict.} \right] \left[\begin{array}{l} \leq \frac{1}{\alpha} \text{ strict.} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{l} \leq \frac{1}{\alpha} \text{ strict.} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{array} \right] \text{ʃ} \left[\text{VS} \right]$

↓ ↓

T : $[0 \text{ syllabic}]$

Whenever a verb stem has a sequence of two vowels bearing identical tones occurring within the same syllable, it is the vowel nearer the consonant that is non-syllabic.

This constraint is apparently a result of the simplification of the vowel assimilation rule (PR 7, 3.2.1.) in verb stems by removing the requirement that the rule applies only across word boundary. The fact that some idiolects still have CVV verb stems with non-identical vowels is some piece of evidence that this constraint is quite recent. Thus, for example, Egharevba (1972) has *kpao* "leave" and *yaɲ* (*yãẽ* in our transcription) "own" where the present writer and his informants have *kpàá* and *yáá* (cf. 3.2.1.).

2.2.4. Constraints on Vowel and Consonant Sequences

30. SPC 6.

NC : ~ $\left[\begin{array}{l} 1 \text{ syllabic} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{l} 1 \text{ syllabic} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{array} \right]$

This condition states that sequences of two vowels with identical tones are not permitted in surface representations in the language. Only ideophones are an exception to this constraint.

31. SPC 7.

NC : ~ $[1 \text{ syllabic}] [1 \text{ syllabic}] [1 \text{ syllabic}]$

Sequences of three syllabic vowels are not permitted to occur in phonetic representations in the language. It is not relevant whether or not they bear identical tones.

32. SPC 8.

NC : $\sim C_2$

By this constraint consonant clusters are ruled out in phonetic representations.

2.2.5. Syllables and Tone

33. SPC 9.

I : [1 syllabic]

↓ ↓

T : [≥ 2 tone]

A syllabic vowel must have a value of 2 or more of tone; i.e., every syllabic vowel must bear tone.

CHAPTER III
GENERAL PHONOLOGICAL PROCESSES

3.0. This chapter deals exclusively with those phonological processes which operate independently of specific grammatical constructions. The phonological processes will be examined under three broad headings - nasalization, vowel assimilation and contraction, and tonology. Most of the rules discussed operate both within the word and across word boundary.

3.1. Nasalization

The Edo (Bini) language has underlying nasal consonant and vowel segments. When some oral segments occur in the environment of nasal segments the oral segments are often modified in some way by the nasal segment. We therefore differentiate inherent nasality from nasalization (i.e. derived nasality). We follow here the convention of referring to segments with inherent nasality as nasal segments (i.e. nasal vowels and nasal consonants) and those segments with derived nasality as nasalized segments.

3.1.1. Nasal Segments

In the language oral and nasal vowels contrast, as illustrated by the following examples:

- | | | | | |
|----|--------|--------------|-------|-------------------|
| 1. | /tí/ | "be fat" | /tĩ/ | "fly" |
| 2. | /vé/ | "burst open" | /vĩ/ | "start (of fire)" |
| 3. | /bá/ | "watch" | /bã/ | "peel off" |
| 4. | /kó/ | "plant" | /kõ/ | "be foolish" |
| 5. | /ù tú/ | "you cry" | /ùtũ/ | "mushrrom" |

There are five nasal vowels as opposed to seven oral vowels in the language. The vowels e and o have no nasal counterparts (cf. 3.1.2). Since oral and nasal vowels contrast, and since we cannot find any evidence of phonetically or morphologically conditioned alternation between nasal vowels and a sequence of an oral vowel and a preceding or following nasal consonant, we shall represent the nasal vowels as systematic phonemes, i.e. /ĩ, ã, õ, õ, ã/ .

We also find contrasts between the nasal consonant /m/ and oral consonants:

6. [bũ]	"be plentiful"	[mũ] ¹	"catch"
7. [bã]	"peel off"	[mã]	"mould"
8. [fã]	"release"	[mã]	"mould"
9. [ùvũ]	"hole"	[ùmũ]	"you catch"

The nasal consonant /m/ will, therefore, be represented in our inventory of systematic phonemes.

3.1.2. Vowel Nasalization

The five nasal vowels — ɪ̃, ũ, ẽ, õ, ã, — may be regarded as the nasal counterparts of i, u, ε, ɔ, a, respectively. As already pointed out, the half-close vowels, e and o, have no nasal counterparts. When these latter occur in the same syllable as m, they are only slightly nasalized. Oscillomink tracings of àmé vé "tears" and ìmòsè "beauty" (figs. 3 and 4 respectively) reveal that e and o are not nasalized throughout when they occur after m; the nasalization extends for a relatively short distance following the release of m. This contrasts very sharply with the nasalization of ẽ and õ after m in àmé' s'õ "sign of suffering" and ùm'õ' khã, i.e. [ùm'õ' xã] (a kind of tree) in figs. 5 and 6 respectively. That is why we would say that

1. The nasalization of a vowel which occurs immediately after /m/, though usually predicatable, is here indicated for the purpose of showing the contrast between the oral consonants and /m/. In a systematic phonemic transcription vowel nasalization in this environment will not be marked.

Fig. 2. Oscillomink Tracings of [àmé!vé] "tears"
Showing Slight Nasalization of [e] after /m/

Fig. 3. Oscillomink Tracings of [imɔsɛ] "beauty"
 Showing Slight Nasalization of [ɔ] after /m/

Fig. 4. Oscillomink Tracings of [ám^xé̃:s̃ɔ̃] "sign of suffering" Showing Heavy Nasalization of [é̃] after /m/.

Fig. 5. Oscillomink Tracings of [ùmõ!xã] (a kind of tree) Showing Heavy Nasalization of [õ] after /m/.

the nasalization of e and o can be accounted for by the universal tendency for a vowel to be at least slightly nasalized when it is tautosyllabic with a nasal consonant. We will, therefore, not account for the slight nasalization of these vowels by any language-specific nasalization rule. Rather the vowels will be marked in the lexicon as an exception to the vowel nasalization rule (i.e. PR 2 below. Cf. 2.1. 1.2., SgSC 6).

When e and o have to be heavily nasalized (cf. 3.1.3) they change to [ɛ̃] and [õ]. This can be formulated as PR 1. (i.e. Phonological Rule 1).

PR 1: Nasalization of e and o (N-e-o)

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} 1 \text{ expanded} \\ 2 \text{ height} \\ 1 \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{l} 0 \text{ expanded} \\ 3 \text{ height} \end{array} \right]$$

The other vowels, i, u, ε, ɔ, and a, are usually heavily nasalized when they occur after the nasal consonant m. In fact, it is not possible to distinguish

the nasal vowels from the nasalized vowels by their degree of nasalization. Moreover, if two or more of these vowels occur after the nasal consonant, they will all be nasalized, as the following examples will illustrate.

10. èmà → èmã "pounded yam"
 11. màá → màã "be good"
 12. mèé → mèë "be difficult"
 13. mùá → mùã "multiply"

Vowel nasalization is formulated as an iterative rightward directional rule.²

PR 2: Vowel Nasalization (VN)

V → [1 nasal] / [1 nasal] —

This rule will iterate the nasalization of an oral vowel when it occurs after a nasal sound (but cf. 3.2.2.).

-
2. According to Howard's (1972) directional theory of rule application in phonology, the directionality of a rule is predictable from its formal properties. Normally, a rule applies from the conditioning factor towards the focus of the rule. Simplicity compels us to adopt this formalism in preference to the SPE parentheses-star convention for stating iterative rules (SPE pp. 343-4, 347-8). A statement of PR 2 using the parentheses-star convention would look like this:

V → [1 nasal] / [1 nasal] (V)* —

So far, our treatment of vowel nasalization has glossed over a fundamental problem, namely, how do we determine whether a heavily nasalized vowel which occurs in the environment of a nasal consonant is underlyingly oral or nasal? In other words, how do we know that 10, for example, is underlyingly /èmə/ and not /èmä/? It would appear that there is no way of choosing between /èmə/ and /èmä/ as the underlying form of [èmä]. There is no universal or language-specific evidence that nasal vowels are restricted in their occurrence to the environment of oral consonants. And, as already pointed out, there is no difference in the degree of nasalization between nasal vowels and their nasalized counterparts in the language. In fact, according to Ferguson's assumption 13 (cf. Ferguson 1963 p. 46) the neutralization of nasal vowels with oral vowels usually occurs next to nasal consonants. It therefore appears arbitrary to posit underlying oral vowels after /m/ and to derive the nasalized vowels by a nasalization rule.

However, it can be shown that the solution is not quite as arbitrary as it may appear to be. It is well known that nasal vowels originate from the nasalizing

influence of nasal consonants on contiguous oral vowels (cf. M. Ruhlen 1973, Elugbe and Williamson, forthcoming). Apart from evidence from other Kwa languages presented by Hyman (1972) and Elugbe and Williamson (forthcoming), there is some (rather indirect) evidence in Edo (Bini) to support this hypothesis. In the language nasal vowels never occur initially in words. We know that in words with initial vowels (usually of VCV structure), the V- is historically a prefix, and that in this position no preceding or following tautosyllabic nasal consonant is possible in proto-Edo.³ The fact that $\tilde{V}$ cannot occur

-
3. In Elugbe and Williamson (op. cit.) no VN- or NV- is reconstructed in this position for Proto-Edo and Proto-Ijo. Wherever initial VN- is present in some modern dialects of Ijo it is derived by a metathesis rule from V- CNV; i.e., V-CNV > VN-CV.

Kay Williamson has drawn our attention to the fact that NV- does occur in proto-Niger-Congo. This raises the question of how back in history we can search for the justification of synchronic phonological analysis. We think that historical evidence from the immediate language family (in this case Edo) should be sufficient for this purpose.

in a position where VN or NV is not historically possible confirms the claim that in this language at least all nasal vowels derive from the nasalizing influence of adjacent nasal consonants.

It then follows that wherever we have in Edo (Bini) a nasal or nasalized vowel which is tautosyllabic with a nasal consonant the nasalized vowel started off historically as an oral vowel. Therefore, whenever there is any doubt as to whether V or $\tilde{V}$ should be posited in such an environment the more historically plausible solution (i.e. the positing of an oral vowel) should be preferred. Following from this, we shall postulate that $m\tilde{V}$ sequences in Edo (Bini) are underlying mV .⁴

4. There is one counter-argument against the position adopted here. There is also the fact that some consonants are nasalized before nasal vowels (cf. 3.1.3., 3.1.4.). In other words, in these cases nasalization moves leftwards from the vowel to the consonant. Therefore one might also argue that phonetic $m\tilde{V}$ originated from $C\tilde{V}$ (such as $b\tilde{V}$), where the C has become m through the influence of $\tilde{V}$, and m became phonemicized possibly through the reintroduction of the original C. Elugbe (1973:318) actually postulates this kind of origin for m and mh in some Edo languages; for example he postulates that proto-Edo *bh became m before nasalized vowels in Egeṅe and Úrhobo.

It would appear, therefore, that the truth about the origin of synchronic $m\tilde{V}$ in Edo (Bini) must lie **between** the two possibilities just stated — some $m\tilde{V}$ may have come from original mV while some others may have come from original $C\tilde{V}$. To the extent that these two origins of $m\tilde{V}$ are possible, our decision to derive all $m\tilde{V}$ from mV is still arbitrary.

3.1.3. Non-vowel Nasalization

All oral segments, except *v*, which have zero as their value or part of their value of stricture (cf. 1. 4.1.1. for the feature stricture), namely, *l*, *r* ([*ɭ*]), *y* and *w*, become nasal stops of the corresponding places of articulation when they occur in the same syllable with nasal vowels. When *v* occurs in a similar environment it is only nasalized; it does not become a nasal stop.

The following are examples of the nasalization of these segments:

13. $\text{bũl}^{\acute{\text{c}}}\text{õ}^{\text{5}}$ → $\text{bũn}^{\acute{\text{c}}}\text{õ}$ "break in many pieces"
 14. $\text{rhããr}^{\grave{\text{c}}}\text{è}^{\text{2}}$ → $\text{rhããr}^{\acute{\text{c}}}\text{è}^{\text{2}}$ (i.e. [$\text{rhããñ}^{\acute{\text{c}}}\text{è}^{\text{2}}$]), "opened"
 15. $\text{iyã}^{\acute{\text{c}}}$ → $\text{inã}^{\acute{\text{c}}}$ "yam"
 16. $\text{òw}^{\grave{\text{c}}}\text{è}$ → $\text{òŋw}^{\grave{\text{c}}}\text{è}$ "sun"
 17. $\text{èv}^{\grave{\text{c}}}\text{è}$ → $\text{èv}^{\acute{\text{c}}}\text{è}$ "word"

-
5. The representations to the left of the arrows in 13 and 14 are not the ultimate underlying representations of these words. These only represent an intermediate stage in the derivation of these items from underlying $\text{bũl}^{\acute{\text{c}}}\text{õ}$ and $\text{rhããr}^{\grave{\text{c}}}\text{è}$ just after the nasalization of the final vowels takes place. (cf. 3.1.3.1. below).

In the cases where oral consonants change to nasal stops, we shall analyse this change as taking place in two stages. During the first stage the consonants are nasalized, just like v . This is accounted for by PR 3.

PR 3: Oral Consonant Nasalization (OCN)

[(XO) stricture] $\rightarrow$ [1 nasal] / $\rightarrow$ [1 nasal]

(where X can be naught ($\emptyset$) or 2)

Then the nasalized consonant changes its manner of articulation from pure approximant or lateral to nasal stop but retains its place of articulation.

PR 4: Nasal Stop Formation (NSF)

[(XO) stricture] $\rightarrow$ [(20) stricture]
 [1 nasal] $\rightarrow$ [< 0 lateral >]
 [< 1 lateral >]

$\tilde{v}$ will be marked as an exception to PR 4. Applying PR 3 and PR 4, 13-17 will be derived in the stages shown in 13a-17a .

13a. $b\ddot{u}l\ddot{o}$ $\rightarrow$ $b\ddot{u}\tilde{l}\ddot{o}$ $\rightarrow$ $b\ddot{u}n\ddot{o}$

14a. $rh\ddot{a}\ddot{a}r\ddot{e}$ $\rightarrow$ $rh\ddot{a}\ddot{a}\tilde{r}\ddot{e}$ $\rightarrow$ $rh\ddot{a}\ddot{a}n\ddot{e}$

- 15a. iyá̃ → iyā́ → ɪnā́
 16a. ðwē̃ → ðwḗ → ðŋwḗ
 17a. èṽē̃ → èṽḗ —

3.1.3.1. The Alternation of l and n, and r ([l]) and n

The alternation of l and n, and r and ŋ is particularly interesting because apart from lending support to our analysis of l and n, and r and ŋ as belonging to the same systematic phonemes, it also helps to validate our PR 1 (the nasalization of e and o). There are two grammatical frames in which the members of these pairs alternate - the intensive morpheme and the simple completive morpheme, both of which are attached to verb stems.

The intensive (or plural) form of verbs is derived by adding a CV suffix to a monosyllabic, or disyllabic CVV, verb stem.⁶ The consonant of the suffix is either l or n. We posit an underlying l in this position;

6. However, it is not all such verb stems which can take this suffix. It would appear that the ability to undergo the process of intensive or plural formation is a lexical feature of certain verbs in the language which must be entered for such verbs in the lexicon; i.e. such verbs will be marked [+ intensive] in the lexicon.

this l becomes n in the environment of nasal vowels.

In the vowel position we have o, ɔ, ɔ̃, e, ɛ, ẽ distributed as follows:

- (i) if the stem vowel is high, the suffix vowel is o or ɔ̃, depending on whether the stem vowel is oral or nasal. ɔ̃ then changes to ẽ (cf. PR 1).

18.	fí	"throw"	fíló	"throw repeatedly"
19.	ví	"jump"	vínɔ̃	"jump repeatedly"
20.	wú	"die"	wúló	"die (of many people)"
21.	bũũ	"break"	bũnɔ̃	"break repeatedly"

- (ii) if the stem vowel is low (i.e., [4 height]) the suffix vowel is ɔ or ɔ̃ depending on the nasality of the stem vowel.

Examples:

22.	vá	"break open"	válɔ̃	"break open repeatedly"
23.	vã	"shout"	vãnɔ̃	"shout repeatedly"

(iii) if the stem vowel is neither high nor low (i.e. [2 height] or [3 height]) all its features are copied in the suffix.

24.	gbé	"beat"	gbèlé	"beat repeatedly"
25.	dé	"buy"	dèlé	"buy repeatedly/intensively"
26.	gbě	"write"	gbě̀ně̀	"write intensively/repeatedly"
27.	só	"hit"	sòló	"hit repeatedly"
28.	bó	"build"	bòló	"build repeatedly"
29.	tṵ	"fell"	tṵ̀nṵ̀	"fell repeatedly"

It would appear that the suffix has two basic vowel forms - $\circ$ and $\circ$; the former occurs with stems whose vowels are [1 expanded] (i.e. i, u, e, o) while $\circ$ occurs with stems whose vowels are [0 expanded], (i.e. ϵ , $\circ$, a). These basic vowels assimilate to the front, non-high vowels e and ϵ . However, of the two basic vowels we rather arbitrarily choose $\circ$ as the underlying vowel. One rather weak argument in support of this choice is that $\circ$ occurs with the vowel a which may be considered the neutral vowel in Edo (Bini). It is

neutral because it is neither front nor back and remains unaffected where other vowels assimilate the backness of neighbouring vowels (cf. 5.3.1.2. for examples of backness assimilation).

The phonetic realizations of the suffix vowel will be accounted for by the following rule which is in three parts.

PR 5: Intensive Suffix Vowel Assimilation Rule (ISVA)

(a)

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ 3 \text{ height} \\ 0 \text{ exp.} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} .2 \text{ height} \\ 1 \text{ exp.} \\ \propto \text{ nasal} \end{bmatrix} / + C \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 1 \text{ height} \\ 1 \text{ exp.} \\ \propto \text{ nasal} \end{bmatrix} = [\text{1 lateral}] -$$

|
VS

This rule states that $\circ$ becomes o after stem i and u , and $\tilde{o}$ after stem $\tilde{i}$ and $\tilde{u}$. PR 1 then converts $\tilde{o}$ to $\tilde{\circ}$. (cf. exx. 18 - 21).

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{(b)} \\
 \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{V} \\ 3 \text{ height} \\ 3 \text{ back} \\ 0 \text{ exp.} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{l} 2, 3 \text{ height} \\ \alpha \text{ back} \\ \beta \text{ exp.} \\ \gamma \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] \overset{7}{/} + \underset{\text{VS}}{\text{C}} \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{V} \\ 2, 3 \text{ height} \\ \alpha \text{ back} \\ \beta \text{ exp.} \\ \gamma \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] = [1 \text{ lateral}] -
 \end{array}$$

PR 5 (b) states that $\circ$ completely assimilates the segmental qualities of the stem vowel, if the stem vowel is half-close or half-open. (cf. exx. 24-29).

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{(c)} \\
 \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{V} \\ 3 \text{ height} \\ 3 \text{ back} \\ 0 \text{ exp.} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [1 \text{ nasal}] \overset{7}{/} + \underset{\text{VS}}{\text{C}} \left[\begin{array}{l} 4 \text{ height} \\ 1 \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] = [1 \text{ lateral}] -
 \end{array}$$

This rule states that the suffix $\circ$ becomes $\tilde{\circ}$ if the stem vowel is $\tilde{a}$ (cf. exx. 23).

7. Cf. (1. 3.) for a discussion of this convention for stating two alternative values of a feature within the same segment.

If we take PR 5 along with PR 1, PR 3 and PR 4, 18, 19, 26 and 23, for example, will be derived as follows.

18. PR 5 (a) (ISVA) / fɪlɔ́ /
fɪlɔ́

19. / vɪlɔ́ /
PR 5 (a) (ISVA) vɪlɔ́
PR 1 (N-e-o) vɪlɔ́
PR 3 (OCN) vɪlɔ́
PR 4 (NSF) vɪnɔ́

26. /gbɛ́lɔ́ /
PR 5 (b) (ISVA) gbɛ́lɛ́
PR 3 (OCN) gbɛ́lɛ́
PR 4 (NSF) gbɛ́nɛ́

23. /vǎlɔ́ /
PR 5 (c) (ISVA) vǎlɔ́
PR 3 (OCN) vǎlɔ́
PR 4 (NSF) vǎnɔ́

The conversion of l to n and the derivation of the nasality of the suffix vowel could be accounted for in one of two ways. The first is what is presupposed in the above analysis, namely, that the nasality of the suffix vowel is copied directly from the stem and that l becomes n through the nasalizing influence of the following (and not the preceding) nasalized vowel.

The second is to assume that in all cases nasalization spreads from the stem through the suffix consonant (which becomes n) to the suffix vowel which is underlyingly oral in all cases. By this analysis, 19, 23 and 26, to take just three examples, would be derived in the following stages.

19. v^hí^hl^hó → v^hí^hl^hó → v^hĩ^hl^hó → v^hĩ^hó → v^hĩ^hõ → v^hĩ^hõ
23. v^hǎ^hl^hó → v^hǎ^hl^hó → v^hǎ^hó → v^hǎ^hõ
26. gb^hě^hl^hó → gb^hě^hl^hé → gb^hě^hĩ^hé → gb^hě^hn^hé → gb^hě^hn^hě

There are at least three reasons why we should prefer the first analysis (i.e. copying the nasality of the suffix vowel from the stem, and l becoming n through the influence of the suffix vowel). The first reason is

that it seems natural to expect the nasality of the stem vowel to be copied directly into the suffix vowel since the other features of the suffix vowel are determined partially by the stem vowel.

The second reason is that the nasalization rule would be too powerful if it allowed nasality to spread through a consonant. By such a rule all occurrences of *l* after $\tilde{V}$ would be expected to automatically become *n*, which is contrary to the facts of the language. There are examples in the language of *l* occurring after nasalized vowels. To cite just four examples:

30. é^ˈmí^ˈlá (← /émí^ˈlá/) "cow"
 31. é^ˈmí^ˈlè (← /émí^ˈlè/) "(a kind of red yam)"
 32. è^ˈmó^ˈwè (← /èmó^ˈwè/) (a kind of white yam)
 33. khỹ^ˈũ^ˈlò^ˈkà (← /khỹ^ˈẽ + ù^ˈlò^ˈkà/) "sell corn-cake"

As a matter of fact, all consonants have a blocking effect on the spread of nasalization and most other segmental phonological rules. It would, therefore, be wrong to postulate that nasalization spreads through *l*.

The third reason for postulating that the nasality of the suffix vowel is copied directly from the stem is seen in the change of $\tilde{o}$ to $\tilde{\tilde{o}}$, as in 19. As we have seen, the suffix vowel is o if a high stem vowel is oral and $\tilde{o}$ if it is nasal. We have postulated that at a more abstract level the suffix vowel following such a nasal stem vowel is $\tilde{o}$. This $\tilde{o}$ has to change to $\tilde{\tilde{o}}$ because it is occurring in a position where a heavily nasalized vowel is required (and o cannot be heavily nasalized after a nasal consonant; cf. 3.1.2.). This $\tilde{o}$ is, therefore, different from the partially nasalized o which occurs after a tautosyllabic nasal consonant as in ìmòsè "beauty" and ùmòzò "state" sword, and nòzó ($\leftarrow l\tilde{v} + \text{òzó}$) "which ozo" (cf. 3.2.4.). We see, therefore, that $\tilde{o}$ would not change to $\tilde{\tilde{o}}$ if it was derived through the nasalizing influence of a preceding n .

The derivation of η from r in the simple completive morpheme (as well as in the third person possessive and objective pronoun; cf. 4.2.2.3.2.) is very similar to the derivation of n from l just discussed. The simple completive morpheme is

underlyingly -rè. When it occurs after open and half-open nasal stem-final vowels (i.e. after ã, ě, and õ) it changes to -ṛè (the other forms of the morpheme and a formalization of the rule are presented in 4.3.2.4.). Let the following examples suffice:

34. hããrè → hããrẽ → hããrẽ → [hããṛẽ]⁸ "tilted"

35. khõõrè → khõõrẽ → khõõrẽ → [khõõṛẽ] "fought"

Thus we see that the change of l to n and of r to ṛ in the intensive form of verbs and the simple completive morpheme respectively conclusively demonstrate that l and n on the one hand, and r and ṛ on the other, belong to the same systematic phonemes.

3.1.4. Nasal Release

The stops of Edo (Bini) are the plosives p, b, t, d, k, g, and the doubly articulated sounds kp and gb. When these stops occur preceding nasal vowels, they

8. In citing examples in other sections of this work we shall simply write ṛ as r̃.

are released with nasal plosion.⁹ The following examples will illustrate the nasal release of stops.

36. $\acute{e}b\acute{e}$ → $\acute{e}b^N\acute{e}$ "state sword"
 37. $\acute{s}t\acute{a}$ → $\acute{s}t^N\acute{a}$ "squirrel"
 38. $d\acute{f}$ → $d^N\acute{f}$ "be bold"
 39. $\grave{a}gb\acute{o}$ → $\grave{a}gb^N\acute{o}$ "world"
 40. $\acute{s}kp\acute{á}$ → $\acute{s}kp^N\acute{á}$ "plate"

This phenomenon can be accounted for by the following rule:

PR 6 : Nasal Release (NR)

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} 2 \text{ stricture} \\ 0 \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{l} 2(20) \text{ stricture} \\ 0 \quad 1 \quad \text{nasal} \end{array} \right] / - [1 \text{ nasal}]$$

The rule states that a stop has an additional nasal articulation when it occurs before a nasal vowel.

9. Elugbe (1973:156-58) also observed partial nasal plosion in Edo (Bini).

However, Carl Hoffmann has drawn our attention to the fact that the nasal plosion in Edo (Bini) is quite different from that found in a language like Gwari where nasal plosion results from the influence of a following nasal stop (not nasal vowel). In the latter case the plosion is usually much stronger than in Edo (Bini).

3.2. Vowel Assimilation and Contraction

An Edo (Bini) word must end with at least one vowel (cf. 2.1.2.1. SqSC 1) although not all words begin with a vowel. Often, a word enters into some grammatical relationship with a following word which is vowel-initial. We shall adopt the convention of referring to the final vowel of the first word (i.e. the word to the left) as FV (i.e. Final Vowel) and the initial vowel of the second word as IV (i.e. Initial Vowel). If a word has a complex FV (i.e. if it ends in more than one vowel) we shall label the final vowels from right to left FV_1 , FV_2 , FV_3 (there cannot be more than three final vowels, cf. 2.1.2.1., SqSC 1). If we have a simple FV (i.e. if the word ends in only one vowel) or if only FV_1 is important for a particular discussion, we shall refer to the final vowel simply as FV.

The bringing together of FV and IV can be encountered between two members of a noun phrase or verb phrase. The following are a few examples of this kind of relationship in the noun phrase and the verb phrase (cf. chapter IV for details).

(a) Noun Phrase(i) Noun + ' + Noun¹⁰

44. òwá + ' + ìsé "Isẹ's house"
 "house" "Isẹ"

45. íghó + ' + àmè "Amẹ's money"
 "money" "Amẹ"

(ii) Noun + Numeral

46. èbé + ókpá "one book"
 "book" "one"

47. òwè + éhǎ "six legs"
 "leg" "six"

(b) Verb Phrase

(i) Verb + Noun Object

48. dè + èbé "buy a book"
 "buy" "book"

10. The need to posit floating tones in some collocations will be demonstrated when these are considered in greater detail later (cf. 4.2.2.).

49. gbàló + òkò "wrap a parcel"
 "wrap" "parcel"

(11) Verb + Pronoun Object

50. ghèé + éré "look at him"
 "look at" "him"

51. kpòlò + éré "sweep it"
 "sweep" "it"

In the ensuing discussion we shall consider only the phonological processes which affect segments when two vowels meet across word boundary. As these processes normally involve the interaction of segmental, tonal and syntactic features, we shall consider only straightforward cases (i.e. cases in which tonal changes hardly take place and which are not very much affected by syntactic factors). The entire description will centre around vowels and their tones because these are usually the only elements affected when two words interact; the consonants normally remain stable and those which border the FV and IV tend to block the spread of

phonological processes.

It should also be noted that all applicable phonological rules are deemed to have applied to a word before it collocates with another word. However, apart from representing surface diphthongs all the time, the results of other rules will be indicated only where they are relevant to the particular process under consideration. Thus while we shall always mark the nasalization of an FV after m (as in àm̃) because of its effect on a following IV, we shall normally leave the nasalization of consonants before nasal vowels unmarked.

3.2.1. Vowel Assimilation

When a non-high FV and an IV meet, the FV normally completely assimilates the qualities of the IV. Examples:

52. òwè + éhã → òwèéhã
 "leg" "six" "six legs"

53. ùyè + ógbã → ùyòógbã
 "valley" "thirty" "thirty valleys"

The vowel assimilation rule can be stated as follows:

PR 7: Vowel Assimilation (VA)

$$\left[\begin{array}{c} V \\ \geq 2 \text{ height} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [\alpha F] / X \text{ --- } + \left[\begin{array}{c} V \\ \alpha F \end{array} \right]$$

This rule states that any word-final vowel with a height of 2 or higher value (i.e. any non-high vowel) assimilates completely to an IV. It is important that this rule is constrained to apply only across word boundary because it does not operate word internally (witness — ègbèè "family" ; èyā̃ "neck" etc.; however, cf. 2.2.3., SPC 5).

3.2.1.1. The Vowel Assimilation Rule and Derivational History

When a complex FV whose members are non-high collocates with an IV, both FV₁ and FV₂ assimilate to the IV . E.g.

54. òkhòó + éhã → òkhèéhã
 "evil deed" "six" "six evil deeds"

55. ghèé + ózá → ghòózá
 "look at" "Oza" "look at Oza"

56. khéé + áyi → khàáyi
 "wait for" "Ayi" "wait for Ayi"

57. òkhòó + ' + úyi → òkhùúyi
 "evil deed" "Uyi" "Uyi's evil deed"

Yet, for reasons stated above, our vowel assimilation rule has been constrained to apply only across word boundary, which rules out the assimilation of FV_2 . The assimilation of FV_2 to FV_1 will also have to be constrained to apply only when an FV collocates with an IV. But further, FV_2 will assimilate to FV_1 only if FV_1 is derived by the vowel assimilation rule, PR 7. Thus we will have to build derivational constraints into our formulation of the rule which assimilates FV_2 to FV_1 , in other words this rule must have access to the derivational history of FV_1 .¹¹ We shall formulate this additional vowel assimilation rule as 58:

11. In the Standard Theory of generative phonology, a phonological rule cannot have access to the derivational history of any segment. However, Kisseberth (1971, 1972a), among others, has shown that rules which have access to the derivational history of the input strings have to be permitted in generative phonology. The need for such rules in Edo (Bini) phonology (also cf. 5.1.3. and 5.1.4.) is a further justification of Kisseberth's claims.

$$58. V \rightarrow [\alpha F] / - \left[\begin{array}{c} V \\ \alpha F \end{array} \right] \left. \vphantom{\left[\begin{array}{c} V \\ \alpha F \end{array} \right]} \right\} \text{Derived by PR 7}$$

The two vowel assimilation rules can be collapsed into one:

PR 7 (Revised): Vowel Assimilation (VA)

$$[\geq 2 \text{ height}] \rightarrow [\alpha F] / - \left\{ \begin{array}{l} + \left[\begin{array}{c} V \\ \alpha F \end{array} \right] \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} V \\ \alpha F \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right\} \text{(a)}$$

} Derived by (a)

By this rule 56, for example, will be derived in the following stages:

	(a)	(b)	(c)
56.	khèé + áyi →	khèá + áyi →	khàá + áyi →
	(d)	(e)	
	khàááyi →	khàáyi	

At stage (b) PR 7 (a) applies to assimilate FV_1 to IV, while PR 7 (b) applies at (c) to

assimilate FV_2 to FV_1 . Word boundary is deleted at stage (d) (cf. 3. 2. 7.), and the two tonally and segmentally identical vowels contract at stage (e) (cf. 3.2.3.).

3.2.2. Nasal Assimilation

If FV is nasal, then IV assimilates its nasality.

Examples:

59. èvbě + ókpá → èvběókpá
 "word" "one" "one word"

60. ívĩ + ógbã → ívĩógbã
 "coconut" "thirty" "thirty coconuts"

The nasal assimilation rule does not need to be constrained to apply only across word boundary because it also applies to any sequence of vowels not separated by word boundary. That is why all contiguous vowels in a sequence must agree in nasality (cf. 2.2.1., SPC 1.). Nasal assimilation across word boundary can therefore be accounted for by writing an optional word boundary into the vowel nasalization rule (3.1.2. PR 2).

PR 2 (Revised): Vowel Nasalization (VN)

v → [1 nasal] / [1 nasal] (+) —

3.2.3. Vowel Contraction

Contraction is the process by which two contiguous vowels which are tonally identical are reduced to a single syllabic segment. There are two aspects to vowel contraction; if the two vowels involved are also segmentally identical, one of the vowels is deleted, whereas the two vowels contract into a diphthong if they are not segmentally identical.

3.2.3.1. Vowel Deletion

After the vowel and nasal assimilation rules have applied, FV and IV become identical. As has been said, if the two vowels are also tonally identical, one of them is deleted, so that we have a single vowel segment phonetically. Consider the following examples:

61. ògò + éhã → ògéhã
 "bottle" "six" "six bottles"

62. òwè + ìgbé → òwìgbé
 "leg" "ten" "ten legs"

It ~~is~~ seems reasonable to assume that in going from the underlying representations to the surface representations in 61 and 62 the FV assimilates to the IV, just as in 52-53 and 59, before the two vowels contract into a single segment because of tonal identity. Thus 61 and 62 will be derived as in 61a and 62a:

	(a)		(b)		(c)
61a.	ògó	+	éhã	→	ògééhã → ògéhã ¹²
62a.	òwè	+	ìgbé	→	òwìgbé → òwìgbé

The vowel contraction rule is responsible for the absence (except in ideophones) of any sequence of identical vowels having identical tones (cf. 2.2.4. SPC 6.).

12. We have actually taken two steps together in stage (b); the deletion of word boundary takes place after vowel assimilation and before contraction. Cf. 3.2.7. for the word boundary deletion rule.

We shall formulate this aspect of the vowel contraction rule as PR 8(a):

PR 8: Vowel Contraction (VC)¹³

$$(a) \begin{bmatrix} V \\ \alpha F \\ \beta \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \emptyset / - \begin{bmatrix} V \\ \alpha F \\ \beta \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix}$$

This rule states that the first of two segmentally and tonally identical vowels is deleted.

13. According to SPE (360) contraction rule is stated as a transformational rule; in other words, PR 8 would be formalized, following the SPE convention as follows:

Structural Description (SD):

$$\begin{bmatrix} V \\ \alpha F \\ \beta \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} V \\ \alpha F \\ \beta \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix}$$

1 2

Structural Change (SC):

$$1 \ 2 \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \alpha F \\ \beta \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ \emptyset \end{bmatrix}$$

However, this transformational rule does not achieve anything different from a normal deletion rule; in this case the second segment is deleted. It is therefore much simpler to state the contraction rule as a deletion rule.

In PR 8 (a) we have selected the FV for deletion because it is the one which normally gives up its segmental features (the only feature which the IV assimilates from the FV is nasality).

3.2.3.2. Non-Recoverable Final Vowels

When FV is deleted it becomes difficult on the surface to determine the quality of FV since no trace of it is left after contraction. In many cases, however, it is possible to use the first word in a grammatical frame where it either occurs as the last word in the utterance or is followed by a consonant initial word. For example, we can get the uncontracted form of the first noun in 61 by using it in a question, i.e.

61 (a) šgéhā "six bottles"

(b) inú šgó' nó ? (← flū šgó'ló)

"how many bottles are there?"

An apparently more difficult case is determining the FV of the noun šgho ("thing: possession"). This noun always occurs with a qualifier, which means that it cannot occur utterance-finally. And most of the qualifiers which occur after it are vowel-initial. However, in one case only (that is, when it occurs with the first person possessive pronoun 'vbě), the segmental shape of the FV can be unambiguously determined to be o. Thus we have:

63 (a) óghá'ímè ← óghV + ' + àmè
 "Amè's (thing)"

(b) óghí'ísé ← óghV + ' + ísé
 "Isé's (thing)"

but,

64 (a) óghòvbé ← ógho + `vbé
 "my (thing)"

(b) ègbèvbé ← ègbé + `vbé
 "my body" "body" "my"

Thus we see that though we cannot determine the FV of ógho from 63, it becomes possible in 64 where the FV of the first word is retained in the surface. But we still cannot recover the tone of o because the present surface low tone could have been derived from an underlying high or low tone (cf. 5.1.1.).

However, there are some words which can only occur before vowel-initial words. In such words the FV is permanently irrecoverable. The following are some of such words. The irrecoverable vowel is written simply as V in underlying representations; in surface representations a dash is written in the position of the lost vowel.

65. vbV "at, in"
 ɪ fɿ̀èrhǎ vb-úgbó
 "I cut wood in the farm"
66. dV "what" (question introducer)
 d-èghè n-ò khí ?
 "what time is it ?"
67. `lṽ "that, which, who" (relative introducer)
 òmò n-ò mòsé (← òmó `lṽ ò mòsé)
 "a beautiful child" "child who it beautiful"
68. lṽ "be" (copula)
 This word always occurs with a following ó
 "he, she, it"
 òwá !n-ó (← òwá lṽ ó)
 "house" "be" "it" "it is a house"

3.2.3.3. Diphthongization

If a high FV (i.e. i, u) occurs before a tonally identical but segmentally different IV, the two vowels contract to form a diphthong. However, if the high FV is

not tonally identical with the IV, the FV is retained unassimilated and uncontracted in surface structure.

69. $iví + ókpá \rightarrow iví'ókpá$
 "coconut" "one" "one coconut"

70. $ídù + èné \rightarrow ídw'èné$
 "dove" "four" "four doves"

71. $ìfí + égbā \rightarrow ìfy'ógbā$
 "trap" "thirty" "thirty traps"

The lack of tonal or segmental identity of FV and IV in 69 prevents them from contracting into a single segment or a diphthong. However, since the FV and IV of 70 and 71 are tonally but not segmentally identical, the two vowels contract to form a diphthong.

The process of forming diphthongs from underlying vowel sequences is not restricted to sequences of high vowels followed by another vowel which may or may not be high. A sequence of a non-high vowel followed by another vowel can also become a diphthong if the condition of tonal but not segmental identity is met. The following two examples from the verb phrase will illustrate:

72. ò ghàá + èbé → ò ghàèbé¹⁴
 "he share out book" "he shares out books"

73. ò khèé + òwá → ò khòowá
 "he watch house" "he watches the house"

Moreover, the process of diphthongization¹⁵ does not only apply when two words are brought together; it also applies within words. Thus we have the following:

74. gúé → gwé "be with"

75. khíé → khỹé "sell"

76. àkhiè → àkhyè "mourning"

77. úhàè → úhàè "well"

78. ékhòè → ékhòè "mind"

14. The tonal identity of FV and IV in 72 and 73 is produced by other rules which will be discussed in chapter V.

15. Conventionally diphthongization refers to the process of a single vowel becoming a diphthong, whereas here two vowels contract to form a diphthong. However, we would think that since the two processes bring about the creation of diphthongs, the name diphthongization can appropriately cover them both.

The question may be asked why the surface diphthong in 74-78, for example, have been represented as deriving from sequences of two vowels at a more abstract level. There are at least three reasons why these (and, by implication, all other) diphthongs should be analysed as coming from two vowels at a deeper level of analysis.

In the first place we have just shown that the process of diphthongization is very productive in the language. For example, in 70-73 diphthongs are created from sequences of two tonally but not segmentally identical vowels. By analogy with such cases it seems natural to derive other diphthongs from underlying vowel sequences.

Secondly, in some nouns which are derived by adding a prefix to a verb stem, a disyllabic verb stem consisting of a high vowel and a following non-high vowel often becomes a diphthong after nominalization. Examples:

- | | | | | |
|-----|------|-----------|-------|------------|
| 79. | hiś | "urinate" | àhyó | "urine" |
| 80. | khié | "mourn" | àkhyè | "mourning" |
| 81. | khùé | "bathe" | àkhwé | "bathing" |

In cases such as these the diphthongs in the nouns are clearly derived from the vowel sequences in the verb stems.

A third reason for postulating a diphthongization rule even in cases such as 74-78 is that in the language one does not find a sequence of two identical syllabic vowels bearing identical tones in surface phonetic structure (except in ideophones; cf. 2.2.4. SPC 6). Such a vowel sequence is automatically converted into a single segment by the vowel contraction rule. But if two contiguous tonally identical vowels are not segmentally identical, they are "contracted" into a diphthong. The diphthongization rule should then be seen as a special kind of contraction rule; it does to a sequence of two non-identical vowels bearing identical tones what the vowel contraction rule does to a sequence of identical vowels bearing identical tones namely, convert them into a single segment. Therefore, contraction and diphthongization complement each other in the process of eliminating vowel sequences bearing identical tones in the language. And since vowel sequences with identical tones do not occur within words in the language (apparently as a result of the application of the vowel contraction rule) we should assume with reasonable certainty that the diphthongization rule also applies

in a context free manner.

The diphthongization rule can be seen as a process by which one of two tonally but not segmentally identical vowels loses its syllabicity. In a sequence of two vowels in which the first vowel is high (the second may or may not be high), it is the first (i.e. high) vowel that loses its syllabicity. On the other hand, in a sequence of two non-high vowels it is the second (i.e. final) vowel which becomes non-syllabic. But even in the latter case the vowel which becomes non-syllabic is the relatively higher one. Therefore, what the diphthongization rule does is to deprive the higher of two tonally but not segmentally identical vowels of its syllabicity. Where the two vowels have the same value of height (this happens only with high vowels) then the first vowel loses its syllabicity.

The diphthongization rule is formalized as the second and third parts of the vowel contraction rule:

PR 8:

$$(b) \begin{bmatrix} < n \text{ height} \\ \propto \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow [0 \text{ syll.}] / \begin{bmatrix} n \text{ height} \\ \propto \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(c) \begin{bmatrix} 1 \text{ height} \\ \propto \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow [0 \text{ syllabic}] / \text{---} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \text{ height} \\ \propto \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix}$$

PR 8 (b) states that the higher of two tonally identical vowels (irrespective of whether it is the first or second vowel in the sequence) becomes non-syllabic, while PR 8 (c) states that the first of two tonally identical high vowels becomes non-syllabic. We do not have to include in the rule the information that the two vowels have to be segmentally different because segmentally identical vowels have been taken care of by PR 8 (a).

PR 8 (b) and (c) can be abbreviated as one rule. Taking this second part of the rule along with the (a) part, the vowel contract rule will be formalized as follows:

PR 8: Vowel Contraction (VC)

$$(a) \begin{bmatrix} V \\ \alpha F \\ [\beta \text{ tone}] \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \emptyset / - \begin{bmatrix} V \\ \alpha F \\ [\beta \text{ tone}] \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(b) \begin{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} < n \text{ height} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} l \text{ height} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow [0 \text{ syll.}] / \begin{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n \text{ height} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{bmatrix} \quad (i) \\ -[l \text{ height}] \quad (ii) \end{bmatrix}$$

3.2.3.4. Triphthongs

There are a few words in the language which contain sequences of three vowel segments with one tone, and constituting a syllabic peak. Examples:

82. ègwàè "palace"
 83. ékhwàè (a kind of charm)

We interpret these as deriving from an underlying sequence of three non-identical vowels which bear identical tones. i.e.:

82. (a) ègùàè → ègwàè
 83. (a) èkhùàè → ékhwàè

It is the central vowel segment which is always syllabic while the first and last vowels in the sequence are non-syllabic. Triphthongs are derived by a repeated application of the diphthongization part (i.e. the (b) part) of the vowel contraction rule.

3.2.4. The Deletion of Boundaries

By the time two words involved in assimilation and contraction reach the surface phonetic representation they

have become a single word; they are said together without any internal juncture or boundary. Thus it is clear that word boundary has to be deleted as part of the derivation of these items.

However, the ordering of the word boundary deletion rule relative to the other rules is quite important. In the case of vowel assimilation the word boundary has to be there to trigger it off. Hence, although the FV will assimilate to the IV in 84 the two continuous vowels in 85 and 86 do not assimilate to each other because of the absence of word boundary between them.

84. èghè + ókpá → èghòókpá
 "time" "one" "one time"

85. èyáǎǎ "neck"

86. òwéè "farmer"

But the contraction rule has to follow the deletion of word boundary.

Since morpheme boundary is also deleted under similar conditions, we shall account for the deletion of both word and morpheme boundaries by the same rule - boundary

deletion.

PR 9: Boundary Deletion (BD)

[1, 2 boundary] → ∅

This rule states that a morpheme or word boundary is deleted.

3.3. Tonology

3.3.0. Edo (Bini) as a Tone Language

It is generally agreed that Edo (Bini) is a tone language. The language exploits tone for making lexical and syntactic distinctions. Thus the following minimal pairs of words are distinguished solely by tonal contrasts:

87. (a) òwá "house"
 (b) ówá "market stall"
88. (a) òkpè "palm-wine tapper"
 (b) ókpè "flute"

The following clauses are likewise so distinguished:

89. ò ghá l dé "he will buy"

90. ò ghà dé ... "if he buys ..."

91. ó ghà dē "he would have bought"

The purpose of this section is to examine the general tonological processes at work in the language. Before we present our own analysis we shall review some previous analyses of the tonal structure of the language.

3.3.1. Previous Analyses

The writers who have contributed most to the description of the tonal structure of the language are Melzian (1937, 1942), Wescott (1962), Dunn (1968), Elugbe (1973) and Welmers (1973). It will be found that one thing that all these writers have in common is their observation of the presence of terracing in the tonal system of the language. They differ, however, in the number of underlying tones they posit and in their analyses of the phonetic variants of these tones.

3.3.1.1. Hans Melzian

Hans Melzian, the pioneer of serious linguistic study of the Edo (Bini) language, has made the most detailed description to date of the tonal structure of the

language. His analysis of Edo (Bini) tone can be found in his Bini Dictionary (1937) and Vergleichende Charakteristik des Verbuns im Bini (1942).¹⁶

Melzian observes in the introductory section of the dictionary (pp. xii-xiv) that seven tones-- high, low, mid, rising, falling, rising-falling and falling-rising- are found in the language. His description of these tones can be summarized under the appropriate headings:

- (a) High tone: High tones are lowered after low tones. This lowering is not significant because it is "brought about by assimilation to the preceding low tone". (p. xiii).
- (b) Low tone: A low tone is usually raised before a high tone and between high tones. Melzian implies that successive low tones with intervening high tones are also lowered when he represents the phonetic realization of an utterance with alternating low and high tones as follows:

16. This latter work will not be reviewed here (cf. 0.1.3.).

- (b) He further observes that a low tone is usually falling after a high or mid tone, though there are certain cases in which the low tone is level, and there are instances in which the difference between the falling and level variants is contrastive. He had not quite worked out the conditioning of the two variants but hoped to discuss the phenomenon in some detail in a later grammar.¹⁷
- (c) Mid tone: This tone has three levels conditioned as follows: the first occurs after a high tone, the second after the first mid, and the third after the second mid. The mid tone rarely occurs after a low tone.
- (d) Falling tone: This is a glide from high to low within a single syllable. Some variants fall from the position of the three mid tones.

17. It appears that Vergleichende Charakteristik is the grammar anticipated here.

- (e) Rising tone: A rising tone usually rises from low to mid.

As for the rising-falling and the falling-rising tones, Melzian merely shows how they are indicated in the dictionary without giving any description of their phonetic realization (apparently, they are combinations of the falling and rising tones described above). It would appear that Melzian does not regard these two tones as distinctive in the language.

3.3.1.1.1. Comment on Melzian

It is clear from Melzian's description of Edo (Bini) tone that he had a keen ear. Although we do not get a clear picture of the phonemic tones as opposed to their allophones from his description, this is quite understandable, particularly when we remember that at the time he wrote the concept of the phoneme, especially as applied to tone, was generally still hazy.

We consider Melzian's description of the high and low tones quite accurate and also think that he should be commended for observing the distinction between the falling and the level variants of the low tone (cf. 3.3.2.1.2.).

Melzian's mid tone is clearly the downstepped high tone described in some later analyses and in this work (cf. 3.3.2.1.1.). The three levels of the mid are most probably some of the various levels that occur when downstepped high tones follow each other, as in

92. òzò !ghá !dè !né

"Ozo would have bought already"

Although Melzian claims that the falling and rising tones occur on single syllables, most of the examples of these tones in the dictionary occur on units which we would interpret as disyllabic. For example, we would write the word represented by Melzian as $\acute{\epsilon}b\acute{e}$ [$\downarrow$] ("danger, harm") as $\acute{\epsilon}b\acute{e}\acute{e}$ [$_ \text{ } \downarrow$]. In particular, all the verb stems represented with rising tone in the dictionary are analysed as disyllabic in this study (cf. 4.3.2.3.1.). Moreover, some of the single syllables which Melzian indicates as bearing falling tone bear level high tone in the speech of the present writer and his informants. For example, we have $\grave{a}kp\grave{a}kp\grave{a}v\grave{a}$ [$_ _ \text{ } \downarrow$] instead of Melzian's $akpakpava$ [$\cdot \cdot \downarrow \cdot$] and $\grave{a}l\acute{a}l\grave{b}$ [$_ \text{ } _$] instead of Melzian's $alalo$ [$\cdot \downarrow \cdot$].

3.3.1.2. Roger Wescott

Roger Wescott's analysis of Edo (Bini) tone is presented in Part I of his Bini Grammar published in 1962. According to Wescott the language has six phonemic tones which he illustrates in co-occurrence with the vowel a as follows (p. 52):

93.	(i)	top	á
	(ii)	high	à
	(iii)	mid	ä
	(iv)	low	â
	(v)	flat	ã
	(vi)	bottom	ā

Five of the six tones are said to be level while the low tone exhibits a short downglide from (iv) to (v). Wescott then divides the six tones, "on phonetic and metaphonemic grounds" (p. 53), into two groups - the upper group made up of top, high and mid, and the nether group made up of low, flat and bottom. This division is in turn cross-cut, "on metaphonemic and historical grounds" (p. 53), by the division into the primary group (consisting of top and low) and the derived group (made up of all others).

Wescott also observes that in addition to the lowering of a high tone after one or more low tones and the lowering of a low tone after one or more high tones, a sequence of low tones uninterrupted by high tones also drifts downwards. A sequence of high tones uninterrupted by low tones does not, however, drift downwards (pp. 55-6).

3.3.1.2.1. Comment on Wescott

Wescott's description of Edo (Bini) tone, like that of Melzian, reflects a keen ear. Some good evidence of this is his observation of the lowering of a sequence of low tones (also observed by the present writer, cf. 3.3.2.1.2.) and his perception of six tone levels.

However, in spite of Wescott's keen ear, his analysis exhibits some internal inconsistencies. One clear example of this is the fact that though he derives four of the six tones which he set up from two underlying tones (top and low), he still regards the six tones as phonemic when one would have expected the logical conclusion that the four derived tones are variants of top and low. Another related example of internal inconsistency is Wescott's recognition of so many phonemic tone levels in spite of his having pointed out the phenomenon of downdrift.

3.3.1.3. Ernest Dunn

Ernest Dunn in his (1968) book, An Introduction to Bini - a pedagogical work designed for the United States Peace Corps learners of the language - attempts a brief description of the tonal system of the language in the "Reference Grammar" section.

Dunn recognizes at the phonemic level four tones - high, low, rising and falling. Although he says that several utterances suggested the presence of a mid tone level in the language, he does not posit a mid tone because it is limited in occurrence and distribution. He then speculates that the mid tones probably originated from high tones lowered by preceding low tones which have been lost historically, but he does not pursue this line of reasoning any further.

3.3.1.4. Ben Elugbe

Ben Elugbe and William Welmers, the last two linguists whose analyses of Edo (Bini) tone will be discussed, have presented the clearest and most systematic descriptions of the tonal system of the language so far. Interestingly, both Welmers and Elugbe independently arrived at their analyses of Edo (Bini) as a two tones plus downstep language

at about the same time.¹⁸

Elugbe's analysis is presented in his (1973) thesis, A Comparative Edo Phonology. He demonstrates the relationship between terracing and downstep in the language and sets up only two phonemic tones - high and low. Even though it is not explicitly stated, he seems to favour the derivation of all occurrences of the downstepped high tone from underlying high tones lowered by the influence of deleted low tones, witness his treatment of é'bó as having an underlying HLH tonal structure (p. 174, fn. 1). Ebo

3.3.1.5. William Welmers

Welmers (1973) describes Edo (Bini) as having a terraced-level tonal system with the following tones - high low, and a phonemic downstep. He claims that the tonal system has, however, an unusual feature: in addition to the high and low tones, there are two contrasting downstep levels in clause-final positions. He calls these two levels the large-interval downstep and the small-interval downstep. He says that the two downsteps contrast in the following pair (all examples are from p. 112).

18. Elugbe first presented his analysis of Edo (Bini) tone in a paper entitled "A note on tone in Bini" at the Linguistic seminar in Ibadan in October 1971 while Welmers' book went to press at about that date.

94. (a) èmíó`wó¹⁹ "money" 20
 (b) ighú`hú²¹ "taxes"

Another peculiarity in the Edo (Bini) tonal system noted by Welmers is the occurrence of a glide from high to downstep-high on a single short vowel, e.g.

95. ó ná` `rré `vbá "he was already there"

3.3.1.5.1. Comment on Welmers

There appear to be some peculiarities in the idiolect of Welmers' informant which are not found in the speech of the present writer and his informants. The present writer has been able to cross-check Welmers' examples with one of his informants²² and has found Welmers'

-
19. We are using Welmer's tonal notation in citing his examples (but cf. 0.3.). In Welmers' system ` indicates a large-interval downstep on the following syllable while ^ indicates a small-interval downstep.
20. Welmers' glossing of èmíó`wó as "money" is clearly a mistake. It should be "meat" .
21. Again there is clearly a mistake in Welmers' tone marking of this word because it begins with a high tone (even in the speech of Welmers' informant; cf. fn. 22.) . In other words, 94 (b) ought to be represented as ighú`hú (but see 3.3.1.5.1. for comment on this word).
22. Dr. Eghosa Osagie was one of Welmers' informants and is most likely to be the one Welmers refers to on page 111 as his third (and most recent) informant. He now teaches in the University of Ibadan.

observations about the large-interval and the small-interval downstep to be quite accurate. Contrary to Welmers' observation, however, this distinction is not used contrastively in the speech of the present writer and his informants.

In the "variety" of Edo (Bini) analysed by the present writer, although the interval between a high and a following downstepped high tone is larger in some cases than in others, this difference is predictable. Usually the interval is larger if the downstepped tone is utterance-final and smaller if it is non-final. This, we think, has to do with the lowering of pitch in utterance-final position. Thus in the following example given by Welmers (the tonetic notation is ours):

96. ì dɛ ˈwé [_ - -] "I bought a goat"

the downstep on wé is a large-interval one, but when wé is made to occur non-finally in an utterance, as in 97 (we are using Welmers' notation although the example is ours):

97. ì d'wé ˈhá [- - -] "I bought three
goats"

the downstep on it becomes a small-interval one.²³

In the case of ighú[˘]hú[˘] (ex. 94 (b)), this word is ighú[˘]húvbú[˘] (or ighú[˘]húú[˘] in rapid speech) in the speech of the present writer and those informants with whom the word was checked. The form ighú[˘]hú[˘] seems to be a peculiarity of Dr. Osagie's idiolect. What has apparently happened is that the last syllable of the word has dropped in Dr. Osagie's speech without adjusting the downstep interval.

23. Welmers' example of clause-final small-interval downstep in *ó ná ~ rré*, "if he comes" (p. 112) is not a good one. The clause in which it occurs can only occur as the first part of a conditional sentence, in which position the last word (in this case rre) is said with a pitch slightly higher than normal. In such a case the downstep on the last word is bound to be a small-interval one; at least smaller than if the word were to occur utterance-finally.

In checking this with Dr. Osagie we got him to say the following utterances:

1. *ó ná ~ rré, ì ghá `yó*
"if he comes, I will go"
2. *ì ghá `yó dégh-ó ná `rré*
"I will go if he comes"

(we use Welmers' tonal notation)

It turned out that while in (1) the downstep on rre is a small-interval one and that on yo a large-interval one, the reverse is true for (2). This is accounted for by the position of rre and yo in the sentences (cf. 4.3.2.5.).

3.3.2. The Present Analysis

We shall now present our own analysis of the tonal structure of the language. The analysis will be presented in two parts — a description of the phonemic tones and their variants followed by a formulation of the tone rules required to relate the underlying representation to the surface phonetic representation of tone. As pointed out in 3.0., we shall examine only those tonal phenomena which are not tied to specific grammatical constructions.

3.3.2.1. The Basic Tones and Their Variants²⁴

Two basic tones, high and low, can be identified in the language. These basic tones are used contrastively as in 87-91 above.

24. Most of the observations to be presented in this section have been noted by earlier writers. More specifically, downdrift has been noted in all the analyses reviewed in 3.3.1.; Elugbe and Welmers discuss the downstepped high tone in some detail, while Melzian observed the falling and level variants of the low tone.

The basic tones have a number of variants. Perhaps the most important phenomenon responsible for the variation in the phonetic realizations of the basic tones is downdrift, which is very much in evidence. When two high tones are separated by one or more low tones the second high tone is realized on a slightly lower pitch level than the first. In the same way, when two low tones are separated by one or more high tones the second low tone is realized on a slightly lower pitch level than the first. The lowering of high and low tones can be shown in the highly simplified tonetic marking²⁵ in 98.

98. òwásèlé [- - -] "the leg of a cricket"

A sequence of low tones without an intervening high tone also drifts downwards. However, a sequence of high tones without an intervening low tone does not drift downwards. The pitch lowering from one low tone to an

25. Until we get to 3.3.2.1.2. we shall indicate only the end points of low tones in our tonetic notations since the allophonic variations of the low tone will not concern us till then.

immediately following low tone is normally very small; it is considerably smaller than the difference in pitch level between two low tones separated by one or more high tones. The following examples will illustrate.

99. òghèdè [- - -] "plantain" [- - -]
100. òzùkpògyèvà [- = : : : -] "second-in-command" [- - - - -]

The lowering of high and low tones continues till the end of the tone phrase, so that a tone phrase-final high tone may be as low as, or even lower than, a tone phrase-initial low tone.

It would appear that the lowering of high tones after low tones is the direct result of the downdrifting of low tones. Apparently, the pitch interval in going from a low tone to a following high tone is always about the same. However, since a low tone is lower than a preceding low tone the high tone following the second low tone will have to be lower than the high tone following the first low tone. Thus the high tone is literally pulled down by the lowering of the low tone.

3.3.2.1.1. The Downstepped High Tone

It follows from the above description of downdrift that a high tone or a sequence of high tones in tone phrase-initial position bears the highest pitch in the tone phrase, whereas a high tone occurring after a low tone cannot be as high as a tone phrase-initial high tone or any previous high tone within the same tone phrase.

Very often the low tone which has lowered a high tone is lost in the surface structure. This most commonly happens as a result of the processes of assimilation and contraction which take place across word boundary. The loss of the conditioning low tones gives rise to many surface representations in which a high tone is immediately followed by a lowered high tone.

For example, in 101,

101. /édé + èné/ édé¹né¹ [· - -]

* "crown" "four" "four crowns"

although the surface representation bears three high tones the third high tone is lower than the first two. The lowering of the third high tone has clearly arisen from the influence of the deleted low tone. (Details of the derivation of the lowered high tone will be presented

in 3.3.2.2.).

A lowered high tone is referred to in the literature as a downstepped high tone. A further terminological distinction is often made between a lowered high tone whose conditioning low tone is present in the surface representation and one whose conditioning low tone is not present in the surface. The former is referred to as an automatically downstepped high tone and the latter as a non-automatically downstepped high tone. Usually when the term "downstep" is used without any further qualification it refers to the latter kind only.

3.3.2.1.2. The Variants of the Low Tone

Everywhere except immediately following a high tone a low tone usually ends in a short downglide. When the incidence of the downglide and the phenomenon of downdrift are taken into account, 102-105, for example, will be realized tonetically as indicated in the corresponding square brackets.

102. òwè [] "leg"

103. òghèdè [] "plantain"

104. ɔ̀dà̀yí [- - -] "regent"
 105. ùkéké [- - -] "stick"

The normal variant of a low tone after a high tone is a fall from high to low (i.e. a high fall). The low tone here assimilates to the high tone by becoming more like it. Or, to put it differently, the high tone spreads into the low tone, so that a HL sequence is realized as a HH-L (where H-L represents a fall from high to low within a single syllable).²⁶ This is illustrated by 106 and 107:

106. ízè [- \] "rice"
 107. á̀sèlé [- \ -] "cricket"

If from an underlying sequence of two low tones the first tone is deleted, the second will still be realized as a relatively level tone (with the usual downglide), even if it is now made to occur immediately after a high tone. Let us illustrate with 108 and 109.

26. Cf. 3.3.2.2. for a formalization of the high tone spreading rule.

108. /íghó + ' + òkpè/²⁷ → íghó!kpè [[- - -]
 "money" "palm wine tapper" "palm wine tapper's money"
109. /íghó + ' + ókpè/ → íghókpè [- - \]
 "money" "flute" "money for a flute"

In 108 the low tone is relatively level in the phonetic representation because it is preceded by another low tone in underlying structure, while in 109 the low tone is realized as a high fall because it is preceded by a high tone in both the underlying and phonetic representations.

In both cases the influence of a low tone on a following tone remains even after the low tone has been deleted. Because of this similarity we shall also refer to a low tone which remains relatively level (instead of falling) after a high tone as a downstepped low

27. Cf. 4.2.2.1. for a justification of the floating tones.

tone.^{28,29} The use of this label has the advantage of reflecting the similarity in origin (though not in realization) between the downstepped high tone and the variety of the low tone referred to as downstepped.

3.3.2.2. General Tone Rules

So far we have avoided discussing details of the derivation of the variants of the basic tones. The rules required for deriving the surface representations of tones are being treated separately because they interact with some other non-tonal phonological rules.

-
28. As with the downstepped high tone, a downstepped low tone is indicated in our transcription by a raised exclamation mark '!', before the syllable bearing the downstepped low tone.
29. After we had discovered that low tones, like high tones can be downstepped in Edo (Bini) Kay Williamson drew our attention to the fact that R.G. Armstrong (1968) had reported a similar phenomenon in Yala (Ikom), and Carl Hoffmann also drew our attention to the fact that Ayo Bamgboṣe (1966) had also reported a similar phenomenon (this time only the downstepping of the low tone) in Yoruba.

The tone rules to be examined are high tone spreading, tonal simplification, downdrift and the deletion of the floating low tone³⁰.

3.3.2.2.1. High Tone Spreading

We observed in 3.3.2.1.2. that a high tone spreads into a following low tone, which then becomes H-L. High tone spreading happens whenever a high tone is followed by a low tone, e.g.,

110. èbóò → èbóô "a charm"

111. úyì → úyí "respect"

112. ò rá kpòlò → ò rá kpôlò "he is about to sweep"

We assume that word boundary is deleted (by PR 9, 3.2.7) before the application of high tone spreading. In other words, the phonetic realization of 112 is like that of 113.

113. òwásèlè

in that both of them contain no internal word boundary.

30. We owe very much to Hyman and Schuh's (1974) work on the tone rules which operate in West African languages for the discovery of some of these tone rules in Edo (Bini).

Following conventions established in 1.3. a high fall on a single syllable (i.e. H-L) is specified sequentially as [24 tone]. The high tone spreading rule is formalized as PR 10:

PR 10: High Tone Spreading (HTS)

[4 tone] → [24 tone] / [2 tone] —

3.3.2.2.2. Tonal Simplification

A high fall which is utterance-final is normally retained in phonetic representations. However, when a high fall which is borne by the second vowel in a sequence is followed by another syllable, the high fall gets simplified to a plain high tone followed by a floating low tone. Thus in going from the underlying representation to the surface representation in 114

114. èbóò + `nó → èbó ! nó

"charm" "be it" "it is a charm"

We posit the following stages:

(a) (b) (c)

èbóò + `nó → èbóô + `nó → èbóó + `nó →

(d) (e)

èbó `+` nó → èbó ``nó`

At stage (b) the final low tone of èbóò becomes a H-L through tone spreading; and this H-L is simplified at (c). The two final vowels, óó, then contract into a single segment (by the vowel contraction rule). At stage (e) the word boundary is deleted. After the application of the downdrift rules the floating low tones will be deleted (cf. 3.3.2.2.3. and 3.3.2.2.4.).

Another example of the application of the tonal simplification rule can be seen in 115.

	(a)		(b)		(c)
115.	èbé	+	èné	→	èbéèné → èbééné →
	(d)		(e)		
	èbéé`né	→	èbé`né		

Word boundary is deleted at (b) while the high tone spreading rule applies at (c). The H-L is then simplified at (d) thus creating the proper input to the contraction rule whose effect is seen at (e).

The tonal simplification rule is formalized as PR 11:

PR 11: Tonal Simplification (TS)

$$[24 \text{ tone}] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{l} 1 \text{ syll.} \\ 2 \text{ tone} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{l} \emptyset \text{ strict.} \\ 4 \text{ tone} \end{array} \right] / [1 \text{ syll.}] - (+)X [1 \text{ syll.}]$$

(where X = zero or a consonant)

This rule states that a H-L tone which is immediately preceded by a syllabic segment (i.e. vowel) becomes a high tone followed by a floating low tone if it is followed by another syllable. Word boundary may or may not intervene between the H-L tone and the following syllable.

3.3.2.2.3. The Downdrift Rules

Before presenting the downdrift rules it is necessary to draw attention to some of our observations in 3.3.2.1.2. It was pointed out there that everywhere, except immediately after a high tone, a low tone ends in a short downglide. It would appear that the incidence of the downglide does not affect the relative pitch levels of low and high tones. It does seem then that we can overlook the downglide in assigning pitch values to low tones.

It was also pointed out that a sequence of low tones also drifts downwards but that the difference in pitch between two successive low tones is very minute. It appears that we can also simplify our tonetic representations by ignoring this minute pitch difference between successive low tones and assign the same value to all low tones in a sequence.

We should also recall that the realization of the low tone which occurs immediately after a high tone is different from the realisation of the low tone in other environments; after a high tone a low tone is realized as a high fall. We represent a high fall by specifying two sequential values of tone - i.e. as [24 tone] (cf. 3.3.2.2.1.).

In assigning pitch values to tones, pitches are assigned higher numbers as they descend phonetically; in other words an increase in the number of a pitch actually means a decrease in (or lowering of) the actual pitch level. Since we are assuming that a low tone is three pitches lower than a high tone, a low tone after a high tone will be specified as [(n + 3) pitch] (where n is the pitch value of the immediately preceding high tone). A high fall is then represented as [n (n + 3) pitch]. We can then revise the high tone spreading rule in terms of tonetic pitch realizations as follows:

PR 10 (Revised): High Tone Spreading (HTS)

$$[4 \text{ tone}] \rightarrow [n (n + 3) \text{ pitch}]^{31} / \left[\begin{array}{l} 2 \text{ tone} \\ n \text{ pitch} \end{array} \right] -$$

31. Pitch is not a feature; it only stands for the tonetic value of a tone.

When another low tone occurs after a low tone which is realized as a high fall, its pitch level is about the same as the end point of the high fall. If the high fall gets deleted, the following low tone retains its relatively level pitch (in which case we say it is downstepped; cf. 3.3.2.1.2.).

Finally, it should be pointed out that the assignment of pitch values is quite arbitrary. There is no way of determining, for instance, by how many pitches a phrase initial low tone is lower than a phrase-initial high tone. The pitch levels assigned are therefore designed to reflect relative pitch levels and no more.

We can now go on to formulate the downdrift rules. Our formalization is a modification of one which was once presented by Kay Williamson.³² The Williamson formalization is itself modelled on that of Schachter and Fromkin (1968).

We account for downdrift by means of two sets of rules - initial pitch assignment (IPA) and downdrift (DD).

32. The formalization referred to here was presented by Kay Williamson in a generative phonology class in 1972.

PR 12: Initial Pitch Assignment (IPA)

(a) [2 tone] → [1 pitch] / # —

(b) [4 tone] → [3 pitch]³³ / # —

PR 12 (a) assigns pitch 1 (i.e., the highest possible pitch in a tone phrase) to a phrase-initial high tone while 12 (b) assigns pitch 3 to a phrase-initial low tone. These rules represent the fact that an initial high tone is the absolutely highest high tone, while an initial low tone is the absolutely highest low tone, in a phrase.

PR 13: Downdrift (DD)(a) [2 tone] → [(n-2) pitch] / $\begin{bmatrix} 4 \text{ tone} \\ n \text{ pitch} \end{bmatrix}$ —(b) [4 tone] → [(n+3) pitch] / $\begin{bmatrix} 2 \text{ tone} \\ n \text{ pitch} \end{bmatrix}$ —(c) [x tone] → [n pitch] / $\begin{bmatrix} x \text{ tone} \\ n \text{ pitch} \end{bmatrix}$ —

33. Although we regard a low tone as going down by three pitch levels after a high tone, an initial low tone is represented as being only two pitch levels lower than an initial high tone, because in utterance initial position a low tone tends to be slightly higher than usual.

PR 13 (a) states that a high tone is two pitch levels higher (i.e. 2 pitch numbers lower) than a preceding low tone, 13 (b) states that a low tone goes down by three pitch levels after a high tone, while 13 (c) states that a high or low tone is assigned the same pitch value as an immediately preceding high or low tone. In the case of a low tone following a high fall, the value of the low tone should be taken to be the end point of the high fall.

It is obvious that PR 12 must be ordered before PR 13.

3.3.2.2.4. The Deletion of the Floating Low tone

To derive the correct tonetic representations of utterances, we shall need a rule to delete any floating low tone which remains after the application of the downdrift rules. The floating low tone deletion rule has to be ordered after the downdrift rules because of the effect a floating low tone has on the tonetic realization of a following tone.

The floating low tone deletion rule is formalized as PR 14:

PR 14: Floating Low Tone Deletion (FLTD)

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \emptyset \text{ stricture} \\ 4 \text{ tone} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \emptyset$$

3.3.2.2.5. Sample Derivations

The following sample derivations will illustrate the application of the downdrift rules and the floating low tone deletion rule. We assume that all other rules have applied before these rules.

116. ǝ ghí ! gbèlávbé !wé !hyá !né

"when he had already killed all the goats"

will be derived as follows:

	/	ǝ	ghí	'	gbè	lá	vbé	'	wé	'	hyá	'	né /
1. IPA		3											
2. DD			1			2	2		3		4		5
				14	4			25		36			47
3. FLD				∅				∅		∅			∅
TR		3	1		4	2	2		3		4		5

(Tonic Representation)

117. úyì ghá!á bŭníhỹō !fỹó!tò nō wú nō!dē
 "Uyi was breaking the claws of the giant rat which died yesterday" .

	/	ú	yì	ghá	á	bŭ	ní	hỹō	fỹó	tò	nō	wú	nō	dē/
1. IPA		1												
2. DD				2	3	4	4	5			6	6	7	
		14		25	36		47	58	8		69	710	10	
3. FLD				∅			∅	∅					∅	
TR		1	14	2	3	36	4	4	5	8	6	6	7	10

(Tonetic Representation)

CHAPTER IV

THE STRUCTURE OF THE SENTENCE CONSTITUENTS

4.0. To be able to analyse the phonological processes which are grammatically conditioned it is essential to first determine the structure of the constituents of the sentence, i.e. the noun phrase and the verb phrase. The aim of this chapter is, therefore, to describe the underlying phonological representation (which is roughly the same as the surface syntactic representation) of the sentence constituents in Edo (Bini). We shall, however, give a survey of the overall structure of the sentence before describing the constituents in greater detail.

4.1. The Sentence

The Edo (Bini) sentence can be broadly divided into three types - the simple sentence, the complex sentence and the compound sentence. A simple sentence is one which has only one main verb (i.e. one which contains no serial verbs) and no embedded sentence or sentences. A complex sentence is made up of two or more main verbs and/or one or more embedded sentences, and a compound sentence is made up of two or more

simple sentences joined by a coordinating conjunction.
The following examples will illustrate.

A. Simple Sentence

1. àmè ghá !kpòlò
"Amẹ is sweeping"
2. Ozó !rhèrhé rré
"Ozo came early"

B. Complex Sentence

3. òwà n-òzò !bóè mósé
"the house which O. built is beautiful"
4. ò ghá !rhié èmyó!wó nà ré
"he will eat this meat"
(literally, "he will take this meat and eat
(it)").

C. Compound Sentence

5. òzò vb-á!mè ghà !rré
"Ozo and Amẹ will come"
6. ò ghá !vió ògó kèvb-èbé
"he will take (away) bottles and books"

In the ensuing description only those sentences which
are simple (in the sense just described) in surface

syntactic structure (even though they may be complex in deep syntactic structure) will be considered. For example, in a noun phrase which is made up of a head and a qualifier, the qualifier can often be derived from an underlying sentence. Thus 7, for example,

7. òwá + * + òzó (òwó!zó)

"Ozo's house"

can be derived from one of the following deep structures, among others.

7(a) òwá nṽ òzó !bṣ=rè

"the house which Ozo built"

(b) òwá nV òzó !yé

"the house in which Ozo lives"

But since we are considering only the surface structure of the sentence constituents, any sentence in which 5 occurs will be treated as a simple sentence if it is not complex in some other way.

4.1.1. The Simple Sentence

4.1.1.1. Types of Simple Sentence

Three main types of simple sentence - declarative, emphatic and question - occur in Edo (Bini). The following sentences illustrate the sentence types.

8. Declarative

isé . !dé òwá "Isẹ is buying a house"

9. Emphatic

isé ò dé òwá "It is Isẹ who is buying a house"

10. Question

d-èvbin n-isé !dé? "what is Isẹ buying?"

Since the declarative sentence is the basic sentence type in the sense that the other types are derived by modifying the declarative type, we shall consider the structure of declarative sentences only. However, the other sentence types will be used to throw light on our analysis of the constituents of the simple declarative sentence whenever the need arises.

4.1.1.2. The Simple Declarative Sentence

A simple declarative sentence has two obligatory constituents - the noun phrase (NP) and the verb phrase (VP). The structure of these sentence constituents will be discussed in detail in 4.2. and 4.3. The following examples will illustrate the NP and VP.

11. òzó !ghá !kpolo "O. is sweeping"
 "Ozo" "sweep"
 NP VP
12. òzó !gbé úgbó èsé!sé "O. farms very well"
 "Ozo" "make farm very well"
 NP VP
13. ópyà òzó ! dé ! yí òyè "Ozo's cutlass fell into
 "cutlass O" "fall into ditch" a ditch"
 NP VP

4.2. The Noun Phrase

4.2.1. The Structure of the Noun Phrase

A noun phrase is made up of an obligatory head (H) followed by one or more optional qualifiers (Q). In some cases a floating tone is present between the head and the qualifier. Where the floating tone is not analyseable as the initial "segment" of the qualifier, it is regarded as a linker which links the head and the qualifier. Therefore the floating tone and the qualifier proper can be regarded as together constituting the qualifier construction. The following are examples of noun phrases (cf. 4.2.2.1. for a

justification of the floating tones).

14. òwè + òkpá "one leg"

"leg" "one"

(H) (Q)

15. ègbé + `hyá "all the body"

"body" "all"

(H) (Q)

16. òwá + • + ísé "Isẹ's house"

"house" "Isẹ"

(H) (Q)

Only nominals can function in the head position in a noun phrase whereas elements belonging to as many as four different grammatical categories can function in the qualifier position.

4.2.1.1. Nominals

The two defining characteristics of the nominals of Èdo (Bini) are the fact that they have a minimal VCV morpheme structure (cf. 2.1.2.2.1., SqSC. 3) and their ability to function as the head of a noun phrase. The nominals can be sub-classified into nouns, pronominals and demonstrative nominals. The underlined items

in the following sentences are examples of nominals:

17. Òzó ! ghá ! kpòlò "Ozo is sweeping".

Noun

18. ónìf ! kpòlò "that (one) is big"

Dem. Nom. (i.e. Demonstrative Nominal)

19. mú ónìf "carry that one".

Dem. Nom.

20. írà gwàlò émilá "they are looking for a cow".

Pronominal Noun

4.2.1.1.1. Nouns

Nouns are the only nominals which can be followed by other nominals (including nouns) as qualifiers.

E.g.

21. òwá + ' + òzó → òwózó "Ozo's house"

"house" "Ozo"

Noun Noun

22. òwè + ' + ònà → òwó'·nà "this one's leg"

"leg" "this (one)"

Noun Dem. Nom.

(cf. òwè + ' nà → òwèénà; 4.2.2.2.)

23. òwá + • + irà → òwírà "their house"
 "house" "their"
 Noun Pronominal (cf. 4.2.2.3.)

The phonological behaviour of a noun when it collocates with other nouns depends to a large extent on its segmental and tonal structure. We shall therefore illustrate the possible shapes of nouns, grouping them according to their behaviour when they collocate with other words (cf. Chapter V). The nouns can be grouped, according to their syllable structures, into two — **disyllabic and polysyllabic.**

Disyllabic Nouns

Disyllabic nouns can, in turn, be divided into two groups — those with simple FV and those with complex FV (i.e. diphthong). The possible tonal shapes of disyllabic nouns are LL, LH, HH, HD (high-downstepped high), and HL. However, we have no example of disyllabic nouns with complex FV which have HD tonal structure. The following examples will illustrate the shapes of disyllabic nouns.

(a) Simple FV

òwè	"leg"
òwá	"house"
úgbó	"farm"
é!bó	"white man; the English language"
ókpè	"flute"

(b) Complex FV

èyǎē	"albino"
ògyé	"laughter"
ékhwé	"garden egg"
ékhòḡ	"mind"

Polysyllabic Nouns

The polysyllabic nouns can also be subdivided into those with simple FV and those with complex FV. The polysyllabic nouns can bear any possible combination of tones, but they can be further subdivided according to their final tonal shapes. Those with simple FV can be subclassified as follows: final high tone, final HLL, final HL and all-low tone pattern. Those with complex FV can be subdivided into those with final LH and those with final HL. The following

examples will illustrate:

(a) Simple FV

(i) Final High Tone

éǵǵó	"clock"
èkpékpésýé	"duck"
èdèdè	"old woman"

(ii) Final HLL

úkpòkpò	"staff; stick"
ènikhùkhù	"pigeon"
lmi!ná	"dream"
ùkpóló!vòè	"fatness; bigness"

(iii) Final HL

àbábè	"witchcraft"
íghú!húvbù	"tax"

(iv) All-low Tone Pattern

àkòbè	"iron trap"
ùghàlètò	"head tie"
òzùkpògyèvà	"second-in-command"

(b) Complex FV

(i) Final LH

ðkhòó	"evil deed"
ðmùhèé	"beginning"
áhùá	"hawk"

(ii) Final HL

èkóò	"belly"
èyáè	"neck"
ówéè	"broom"

4.2.1.1.2. The Demonstrative Nominals

There are two demonstrative nominals in the language - ðnà (this one) and ðníf (that one). They can be pluralized as ènà and éníf respectively. The demonstrative nominals can function both as the head of a noun phrase (as in 18 and 19) and as noun phrase qualifiers (as in 22).

4.2.1.1.3. The Pronominal

The pronominal is the only nominal which can be inflected both for person and number. It also has different phonological shapes when functioning as the subject of a sentence and as an object or a possessive qualifier. The following is the paradigm of the

subject pronominal.

	<u>Singular</u>		<u>Plural</u>	
24.				
1p.	ímè	'I'	ímà	"we"
2p.	úwè	'you'	úwà	"you"
3p. human	írè	'he, she'	írà	"they"
non-human	èré	'it'		

The singular forms of the subject pronominal can only occur in emphatic sentences. In non-emphatic sentences the subject pronoun is used (cf. 4.3.2.1.1.).

The pronominal has the following paradigm when functioning as object or possessive qualifier (cf. 4.2.1.2.1.).

	<u>Singular</u>		<u>plural</u>	
25.				
1.	ímè	"me/my"	ímà	"us/our"
2p.	úwè	"you/your"	úwà	"you/your"
3p.	írè	"him/his"	írà	"them/their"

As with the subject pronominal, the singular forms of the object/possessive pronominal can only occur in emphatic sentences.

4.2.1.2. Non-nominal Qualifiers

Apart from nominals, items belonging to the categories of pronoun, numeral and adjective can also function in the qualifier position in a noun phrase.

4.2.1.2.1. The Pronoun

The pronoun has a possessive function in qualifier position. We therefore refer to the qualifier pronoun as a possessive pronoun.

The possessive pronoun can be inflected for person but not number. Only the pronominal can occur in the plural (cf. 4.2.1.1.; 4.2.1.1.3.). The following is the paradigm of the possessive pronoun in the language:

26.	1p.	vbě	"my"
	2p.	rùé	"your"
	3p.	ŵrè	"his, hers, its"

The object pronoun is very similar to the possessive pronoun, the only differences being the tone pattern of the 3p., i.e. ŵrè (cf. 4.3.1.), and the fact that the floating low tones which occur with the 1p. and 2p. object pronouns are the initial segments of those pronouns; i.e. the 1p. and 2p. object pronouns are

`vbé and `rùé respectively (cf. 4.2.2.3.1.).

4.2.1.2.2. Numerals

There are two types of numeral qualifiers - the cardinal and the ordinal numeral qualifiers. The following are examples of each type.

27. Cardinal numerals

(i)	ókpá	"one"
(ii)	èhá	"three"
(iii)	ìgbé	"ten"

28. Ordinal numerals

(i)	òkàrò	"first"
(ii)	ógyèhà	"third"
(iii)	ógyìgbè	"tenth"

All numerals, whether of the ordinal or cardinal type, begin with a vowel. All cardinal numerals except ókpá (one) éhá (six) and ógbá (thirty) begin with a low tone vowel, while all ordinal numerals, except òkàrò (first), begin with a high tone morpheme, ógy- .

An ordinal numeral qualifier can relate to its head in one of two ways - it either occurs directly after the head, like all other qualifiers, or it is

preceded by the relative introducer `lV̄.

Examples:

29. èbé + ógyèhà "the third book"

30. èbé + `lV̄ + ógyèhà "the book which is third;
the third book".

When the ordinal numeral is preceded by a relative introducer the entire construction is a relative clause. We shall, therefore, not discuss that type of structure any further.

4.2.1.2.3. Adjectival Qualifiers

There are five adjectival qualifiers in the language. These are:

31.	'nà	"this"
	'níf	"that"
	'dǎ	"bad"
	'kèkǎ	"ordinary, only"
	'hyá	"all"

Of these, the first two perform a demonstrative function, the next two are attributive and the last is a quantifier.

4.2.2. Noun Phrase Constructions

We have a noun phrase construction when a noun occurs with any one of the four possible qualifier types. In all but one case we name a noun phrase construction after the type of qualifier present in the construction. Thus we have the possessive pronoun construction, the numeral construction and the adjectival construction. In the case of the construction involving nominal qualifiers we adopt the label associative construction.¹

In all but the numeral construction there is evidence that there is in the underlying phonological representation some element between the head and the qualifier which is either not fully realized or which takes on additional features in the phonetic representation.² We shall, therefore, attempt to determine the actual underlying phonological representations of the various noun phrase constructions.

We shall consider the collocation of object pronouns with verbs along with the possessive pronoun construction because of the similarities which these

-
1. To the best of our knowledge the name associative construction was first used to describe this kind of structure by Welmers (1963).
 2. Cf. 4.2.1. for a further differentiation among floating tones that occur between the head and the qualifier.

two structures have in common.

4.2.2.1. The Associative Construction

The associative construction always involves two nominals. The head is always a noun while the qualifier can be any nominal. In this construction there is evidence that a floating high tone occurs between the two nominals involved. Thus when the two nominals to the left of the colons in 32-34 are "associated" they are realized phonetically as the corresponding representations to the right of the colons.

32. òwè ; òsà : òwó!sà

"leg" "chimpanzee" "a chimpanzee's leg"

33. àmè ; èhyě : ámé!hyě

"water" "pepper" "solution of pepper in water"

34. òwè ; ònà : òwó!nà

"leg" "this one" "this one's leg"

The high tone resulting from the "association" of FV and IV can only be explained by positing a floating high tone between the two words. Thus 32(a) - 34(a) will be the underlying representations of 32-34.

32(a) òwè + ' + òsà

33(a) àmè + ' + èh̄ȳé

34(a) òwè + ' + ònà

4.2.2.2. The Adjectival Construction

Every adjectival qualifier has to be represented with an initial floating tone. The positing of floating tones is the only way we can explain the resulting phonetic representations when the nouns in 35-37 are qualified by the adjectives which follow them.

35. (a) íghó : íghó nà
 "money" "this money"

(b) òwè : òwèé' nà
 "leg" "this leg"

36. (a) ùkpó : ùkpó dǎ
 "year" "a bad year"

(b) ètè : ètèédǎ
 "sore" "a bad sore"

37. (a) èkì : èkì hyá
 "market" "the entire market"

(b) òdè : òdè ! hyá
 "road, "all roads"
 say"

Two reasons can be adduced for analysing the floating tones in this construction, unlike that in the associative construction, as constituting the initial "segments" of the adjectival qualifiers.

The first reason is that without initial floating tones all the adjectival qualifiers would be consonant-initial. But it would appear that these qualifiers were historically vowel-initial, like most other qualifiers (e.g. nominals and numerals). The initial floating tones can then be seen as deriving from the deletion of the initial vowels of these qualifiers.

The second reason is that two floating tones, high and low, occur in the adjectival construction. It is not likely that two different tones mark the same construction.

The adjectival qualifiers are therefore represented underlyingly as follows: 'dā, kəkā, 'nà, 'nini and 'hyá (cf. 4.2.1.2.3.).

4.2.2.3. The Possessive Pronoun Construction *

4.2.2.3.1. The Construction floating Low Tone

When a possessive pronoun qualifies a noun the final high tone of the noun changes to low. Thus we have the

following:

38. ówá : ówàvbé
 "market stall" "my market stall"

39. òwá : òwà vbé
 "house" "my house"

40. ásèlé : ásèlè rùé.
 "cricket" "your cricket"

41. ègbé : ègbèéré
 "body" "his body"

We, therefore, posit a floating low tone in order to account for the lowering of the final high tone of the noun. There is, however, a problem in determining whether the floating low tone is a marker of the possessive pronoun construction as a whole or whether it is, like the floating tones of the adjectival qualifiers, the initial "segment" of the pronoun qualifier.

Since the first and second person pronoun qualifiers would be consonant-initial without the floating low tone, it would appear natural to regard the floating

tone as the initial "segment" of the qualifier (cf. 4.2.2.2. for a similar argument). The snag about treating the floating low tone as such is the fact that a final nominal high tone is also lowered before the third person pronoun qualifier which has a VCV structure (cf. exx. 41.). Could it be that the third person pronoun historically has a $\dot{V}VC\dot{V}$ structure? This is quite unlikely in view of the fact that vowel sequences are not permitted in word initial positions synchronically or diachronically.³

It would appear that the structure of the object pronoun can throw some light on the structure of the possessive pronoun qualifier. As noted in 4.2.1.2.1., the object pronoun is very similar in structure to the possessive pronoun qualifier, the essential difference being that the third person object pronoun has a low-low tone pattern (i.e. $\dot{V}r\grave{e}$) while the third person qualifier pronoun has a high-low tone pattern. As in the possessive pronoun construction, the first and second person object pronouns also have a lowering effect on the final high tone of a preceding verb in non-simple completive constructions (cf. 4.3.1.). E.g.

3. One piece historical evidence is that Elugbe (1973) does not reconstruct-initial vowel sequences for proto-Edo. For the synchronic constraint on initial vowel sequences, cf. 2.1.2.2.1., SqSC 5.

42. gbé : gbè vbé
 "beat" "beat me"
43. kòkó : kòkò rùé
 "feed" "feed you"

But, unlike in the possessive pronoun construction, the final high tone of a verb is not lowered before the third person object pronoun; e.g.

44. gbé : gbéré (←gbé + èrè)
 "beat" "beat him"
45. kòkó : kòkére (←kòkó + èrè)
 "feed" "feed him"

Thus, although we have to posit a floating low tone when a verb occurs with the first and second person object pronouns, we do not need to posit a floating low tone when a verb collocates with the third person object pronoun. When we consider this situation along with the fact that no floating tones need to be posited when verbs occur with noun objects, we have to postulate that the floating low tone which lowers the final high tone of a verb occurs as the initial "segment" of the pronoun.

This analysis of the structure of the object pronoun confirms our earlier conjecture that, although the first and second person pronoun qualifiers can be treated as having an initial low tone segment, the same cannot hold for the third person qualifier. It would then appear that the lowering of the final high tone of a noun brought about by the initial floating low tone of the first and second person possessive pronouns has been generalized to cover final nominal high tones before the third person possessive pronoun qualifier. The floating low tone has, therefore, become a marker of the possessive pronoun construction. Following from this, we shall represent 38-41 as having 38(a) to 41(a) as their underlying phonological representations.

38. (a) ówá + ' + vbé́

39 (a) òwá + ' + vbé́

40 (a) ásèlè + ' + rùé

41 (a) ègbé + ' + éré

4.2.2.3.2. The IV of the 3p. Pronoun

A further problem in determining the underlying representations of possessive pronouns has to do with the phonological shape of the initial vowel of the third pronoun.

The third person possessive pronoun manifests three different phonological shapes - *érè*, *órè*, and *árè* (these have the nasalized counterparts *éřè*, *óřè* and *ářè* respectively, depending on the nasality of the FV). Thus when the nouns to the left of the arrows in 46-52 are qualified by the third person possessive pronoun we have the realizations to the right of the arrow:

46.	<i>èsi + ' + 3p.</i>	$\rightarrow$	<i>èsiérè</i>	"his pig"
47.	<i>òtù + ' + 3p.</i>	$\rightarrow$	<i>òtùérè</i>	"his age group"
48.	<i>èbé + ' + 3p.</i>	$\rightarrow$	<i>èbèérè</i>	"his book"
49.	<i>úgbó + ' + 3p.</i>	$\rightarrow$	<i>úgbèérè</i>	"his farm"
50.	<i>ízè + ' + 3p.</i>	$\rightarrow$	<i>ízòórè</i>	"his rice"
51.	<i>ézó + ' + 3p.</i>	$\rightarrow$	<i>ézòórè</i>	"his case"
52.	<i>òwá + ' + 3p.</i>	$\rightarrow$	<i>òwàárè</i>	"his house"

The surface representations of the third person possessive pronoun are distributed as follows:

- (i) *érè* after FVs *i*, *u*, *e* and *o*.
- (ii) *órè* after FVs *ɛ* and *ɔ*
- (iii) *árè* after FV *a*.

It would appear at a first glance that we could postulate *érè* as the underlying representation of this pronoun because it has the widest distribution, occurring

after four of the seven oral vowels. We could then derive the other surface representations ʒrè and árè by a rule which changes IV ɛ to ɔ after FVs ɛ and ɔ , and to a after FV a .

However, if we did this we would not be able to account for the change from ɛ to ɔ after FV ɛ and ɔ in any natural way; the change cannot be treated as an assimilation of height or backness. Moreover, with underlying érè we would have to postulate contradictory assimilation rules in 48 and 49 on the one hand, and 50 and 51 on the other; in the former pair the assimilation rule would be regressive while it would be progressive in the latter.

In the face of all this it would appear that the only option left is to regard the initial vowel of the third person possessive pronoun as a high tone incompletely specified vowel segment. Since all the three realizations of the initial vowel (i.e. ɛ , ɔ and a) are non-high and unexpanded, the vowel can be specified for the features height and expanded only; i.e.

0	expanded
23	height

The IV of the third person object pronoun behaves in exactly the same way as that of the third person possessive pronoun qualifier as far as vowel quality goes. E.g.

- | | | | |
|-----|------------|---|---------------|
| 53. | vú | : | vwéré |
| | "pull" | | "pull it" |
| 54. | fi | : | fyéré |
| | "shoot at" | | "shoot at it" |
| 55. | gbé | : | gbéré |
| | "beat" | | "beat him" |
| 56. | kòkó | : | kòkére |
| | "feed" | | "feed him" |
| 57. | dé | : | dóre |
| | "buy" | | "buy it" |
| 58. | sòs | : | sòsrè |
| | "tear" | | "tear it" |
| 59. | ká | : | káre |
| | "count" | | "count it" |

Therefore, the IV of both the third person object and qualifier pronouns will be derived in exactly the same way.

To derive the surface form of the IV of the third person pronoun (both object and qualifier) we will require two rules; the first will specify the quality of the IV according to the FV, and the second, the vowel assimilation rule (PR 7), will assimilate the FV to the IV. The rule which specifies the IV according to the FV can be formalized as PR 15.

PR 15: 3p IV Quality

This rule states that the initial vowel of a third person pronoun is realized as ϵ when it occurs after FV i , e , u and o , as $\circ$ after FV ϵ and $\circ$, and as a after FV a . Following the application of the rule which shifts the floating low tone on to the FV (cf. 5.1.1.) and this rule, the underlying forms in 46-52 will be re-represented as 46 (a) - 52 (a).

- 46 (a) èsi + éré
 47 (a) òtù + éré
 48 (a) èbè + éré
 49 (a) úgbò + éré
 50 (a) ízè + óré
 51 (a) ézò + óré
 52 (a) òwà + áré

After the application of PR 15, the vowel assimilation rule, PR 7 (cf. 3.2.2.) applies to assimilate the FV to the IV, and by the vowel nasalization rule PR 2 (cf. 3.2.2.) the IV assimilates the nasality of the FV where the latter is nasal. The nasalization of -re in the third person pronoun is derived as in 3.1.3.1. First, the nasality of the IV is copied into the final vowel e by PR 5 (c) and $\tilde{e}$ becomes $\tilde{\epsilon}$ by PR1, while r changes to [ɾ] by PR 3 and PR 4 (cf. 3.1.3.). The following examples will illustrate the result of the application of these rules.

60. èdí + ' + éré → èdíéřě
 "palm nut" "his palm nut"
61. èvbě + ' + óré → èvbòóřě
 "word" "his word"

X

62. $\text{isà} + \text{á r è} \rightarrow \text{isàár è}$

We shall illustrate the application of these rules by going through all the stages in the derivation of 60.

60 (a) $\overset{(a)}{\text{èdì} + \text{Vr è}} \rightarrow \overset{(b)}{\text{èdì} + \text{Vr è}} \rightarrow \overset{(c)}{\text{èdì} + \text{ér è}} \rightarrow$
 $\overset{(d)}{\text{èdì} + \text{ẽr è}} \rightarrow \overset{(e)}{\text{èdì} + \text{ẽr ẽ}} \rightarrow \overset{(f)}{\text{èdì} + \text{ẽr ẽ}} \rightarrow$
 $\overset{(g)}{\text{èdì} + \text{ẽr ẽ}} \rightarrow \overset{(h)}{\text{èdì} + \text{ẽr ẽ}} \rightarrow \overset{(i)}{[\text{èdìẽr ẽ}]}$

At stage (b) the floating low tone shifts on to the FV and replaces its tone. The 3p. quality rule applies at (c) while the vowel nasalization rule applies at (d). Then the nasality of the IV, ẽ, is copied into the final vowel of the pronoun at (e) by PR 5 (c). At (f) ẽ changes to ẽ by PR1. At (g) r is nasalized by PR 3 while ẽ changes to ẽ by PR 4 at (h). Finally, word boundary is deleted at (i).

4.3. The Verb Phrase

4.3.0. The Structure of the Verb Phrase

A verb phrase consists of an obligatory verbal construction (VC) and two optional elements — the noun phrase and the adverbial (ADV B).

An adverbial is made up of a prepositional phrase (Prep. Phr.) and/or an adverb (Adv.). When a prepositional phrase and an adverb occur together in a sentence the prepositional phrase usually precedes the adverb. (For the structure of the NP, see 4.2.1.).

The following sentences will illustrate the structure of the verb phrase as so far elicited.

63. Isé !rhèrhé !kpòlò

NP VC

"Isẹ swept early"

64. Isé !rhèrhé !kpòlò òwá

NP VC NP

"Isẹ swept the house early"

65. òzó !dé yí ùyè èsé!sé

NP VC Prep.Phr. Adv.

"Ozo really fell into the ditch"

In the rest of this section only the verbal construction and the object pronoun will be further discussed.

4.3.1. The Object Pronoun

We noted in 4.2.1.2.1. and 4.2.2.3. that the differences in the phonological qualifier and the object pronoun reside (i) in the tonal structure of the third person pronoun and (ii) in the initial "segments" of the first and second person pronouns.

We shall here demonstrate that the tonal structure of the object pronoun can be unambiguously determined to be LL. There is a grammatical frame in which the underlying tonal structures of most noun phrase constituents are retained in the phonetic representation. The grammatical frame is a WH question beginning with vbV ("what, where") and ending with yí. When a noun or pronoun occurs in the object position in such a sentence, its lexical tonal structure is retained in the phonetic representation. We shall illustrate with the following examples, using the nominals and the third person pronoun given to the left of the colons.

66. ðsà : vb-ðó mú ðsà á yí? (→ vbðó mwðsàá yí?)
chimpanzee
"what is catching the chimpanzee?"
67. èbé : vb-àá mú èbé yí? (→ vbàá múèbé yí?)
"book" "where does one keep the book?"
68. úgbó : vb-àá mú ugbó yí? (→ vbàá múgbó yí?)
"farm" "where does one make a farm?"
69. ùwà : vb-ðó mú ùwà á yí? (→ vbðó mùwàá yí?)
"you (pl.)" "what is catching you (pl.)?"
70. V̀rè : vb-àá mú èrè é yí? (→ vbàá m̀wèr̀èé yí?)
"where does one put it?"
71. Vrè : vb-ðó gbé èrè é yí? (→ vbðó gbèrèé yí?)
"what is beating him?"

The underlying tonal structure of the third person object pronoun should therefore be LL.

4.3.2. The Verbal Construction

There are two types of verbal constructions - affirmative and negative. The essential difference between affirmative and negative verbal constructions is the presence of a negator and a sentence-final low

tone vowel in the latter. We shall therefore describe the structure of affirmative verbal constructions in detail and then highlight those aspects in which the negative verbal constructions are different. Finally we shall provide a list of the verbal constructions so far identified, listing the negative constructions after the affirmative ones.

4.3.2.0. The Constituents of the Verbal Construction

In Edo (Bini) a verb can be made to express the continuity, completeness, priority, manner, etc. of an action by selecting, or failing to select, an auxiliary marker (AM) to occur with it, as well as by effecting some tonal changes on the subject concord marker (SCM). In one instance, a suffix (Su.) is also added to the verb stem (VS). Each such unique modification of a verb stem is what we regard as a verbal construction. The underlined items in the following sentences are examples of verbal constructions:

72. Present continuous

òzó ! ghá !rhùlé "Ozo is running"

73. Simple completive

òzò ! lèé=rè "Ozo escaped"

74. Anticipative

ú tè rré, ì ghá ! mwègbé

"before you come, I will be ready"

We shall regard those elements which can uniquely modify a verb stem as together constituting the construction marker (CM). A verbal construction is thus obligatorily made up of the construction marker and the verb stem. The subject concord marker is the only obligatory element in the construction marker. The construction suffix occurs only in the simple completive construction while the auxiliary marker occurs in all but a few constructions.

The structure of verbal constructions can be specified by the subject of phrase structure rules in 75:

75. VC → CM + VS

CM → SCM (+ AM) (+ Su.)

We shall now describe each of the constituents of the verbal construction. (cf. 4.3.3. for a list of the verbal constructions).

4.3.2.1. The Subject Concord Marker

4.3.2.1.1. Evidence for the Subject Concord Marker

In most sentences there is clear evidence of some underlying element between a nominal subject and a following auxiliary marker, or verb stem where there is no AM. In the following examples,

76. àmè ghà kpòlò ...

"if Amẹ sweeps ..."

77. àmèé ghà kpòlò

"Amẹ would have swept"

although there is ostensibly no element occurring between àmè and ghà in 76, there is the high tone vowel, é, in 77.

Most cases are, however, not as clear as 77. In a few cases there is no trace in the phonetic representation of any underlying element while, in the majority of cases, only tonal evidence points to the occurrence of some segment in the position between the noun phrase and the verb phrase. In this regard, consider the following:

78. òzò !kpòlò "Ozo sweeps"
 79. úgbò !rá kpòlò "Ugbo is about to sweep"
 80. ùzì ! gbé "Uzi dances"

From what we know of the phenomenon of downstep, 78-80 should, at a deeper level of analysis, be represented with floating tones in the positions where downstep occurs; i.e.

- 78 (a) òzò `kpòlò
 79 (a) úgbò `rá kpòlò
 80 (a) ùzì `gbé

It seems natural to postulate, especially by analogy with 76, that at a still deeper level of analysis the floating tones of 77 (a) - 79 (a) are borne by segments which have been deleted.

When the noun subjects in 78(a) - 80(a) are replaced by "pronouns", the "pronouns" bear the tones which are postulated as floating when the sentences have noun subjects.

- 78 (b) ò kpòlò "he sweeps"
 79 (b) ò rá kpòlò "he is about to sweep"
 80 (b) ò gbé "he dances"

In the same way, 81 (a) will be replaced by 81 (b):

81 (a) ègwí 'ghà wú "the tortoise would have died"

(b) ɔ ghà wú "he would have died"

Could it then be that ɔ is the element which occurs between the noun and the predicate in 78 (a) - 81 (a)?

In other words, could we expect 81 (a), for example, to be represented as 81 (c) at a deeper level of analysis?

81 (c) ègwí ɔ ghà wú

As a matter of fact, 81 (c) actually occurs as an emphatic sentence meaning "it is the tortoise who should have died". In this position (i.e. as in 81 (c)), ɔ is clearly a subject concord marker which relates the NP and VP. It appears that the fully specified form of the subject concord marker occurs obligatorily in emphatic sentences, as the following examples will further illustrate:

82. àmɔ́ ghà rré (← àmè ɔ ghà rré)

"It is Amẹ who should have come"

83. òzó ghà rré (← òzó ɔ ghà rré)

"It is Ozo who should have come"

In non-emphatic sentences, such as 78-80, the segmental features of the subject concord marker are deleted leaving their tones floating.⁴

4.3.2.1.2. The Subject Concord Marker versus the Subject Pronoun

If the $\circ$ of 81 (c) is clearly a subject concord marker, what about the occurrences of $\circ$ in 78 (b) - 80 (b)? As we have seen, they bear the same tones which are postulated as floating in the position where we would posit an SCM. Moreover, the tonal alternations which $\circ$ undergoes are very crucial in distinguishing verbal constructions. For instance, the only difference between 84 and 85 lies in the tone of $\circ$:

84. ð ghà rré ... "if he comes ..."

85. ɔ ghà rré ... "he would have come"

4. Although emphatic and non-emphatic sentences have similar deep structures, the emphatic sentences contain a dummy EMPH which blocks the deletion of the SCM. Where the subject NP of the emphatic sentence ends in a non-high and non-low vowel, the vowel is assimilated by the vowel assimilation rule PR7 (3.2.1.), as in 82 and 83. In the case of a final nominal low vowel, it is the SCM which assimilates to it, e.g. ðsàá ghà dé (it is the chimpanzee which should have fallen).

In non-emphatic sentences the SCM segment is deleted, although its floating tone is then segmentalized under certain conditions (cf. 4.3.2.1.4.)

It would then appear that *o* is also a subject concord marker in 78 (b) - 81 (b) and in 84 and 85. The element *o* belongs to the following paradigm:

- i* - 1st pers. sg.
- u* - 2nd pers. sg.
- o* - 3rd pers. sg.
- i* - 3rd pers. pl. (used in relative constructions only)
- a* - indefinite pers.

However, if we were to recognize all instances of *o* and, of course, all the other members of the paradigm as subject concord markers, this would imply that there are no subject pronouns in the language. This would be a serious claim to make, especially in view of the fact that other valid personal pronouns - namely the object and the possessive pronouns - have to be recognized in the language (cf. 4.2.1.2.1.; 4.2.2.3. and 4.3.1.).

The following examples will further illustrate the object and possessive pronouns:

86. (a) àmè tié òzó "Amẹ is calling Ozo"
 (b) àmè tié èrè "Amẹ is calling him"

(c) àmè tlié `rùé "Amè is calling you"

87. (a) èbé úyi `nó "it is Uyi's book"

(b) èbé `érè `nó "it is his book"

(c) èbé `rùé `nó "it is your book"

The underlined items in the (b) and (c) sentences are personal pronouns which substitute for the underlined nouns in the (a) sentences. In 86 èrè and `rùé are third and second person object pronouns respectively, substituting for òzò. Similarly, érè and `rùé in 84 are respectively third and second person singular possessive pronouns substituting for úyi.

Since the language clearly makes use of personal pronouns of the object and possessive types, it is quite unlikely that it should not make use of personal pronouns of the subject type. In other words, we ought to be able to substitute subject pronouns in place of noun subjects just as we do for object and possessor nouns. This is the more to be expected because semantically the *o* in 78 (b) - 81 (b) is as valid a noun substitute as the object and possessive pronouns of 83 and 84.

There is, however, an essential difference

between the subject pronoun and the subject concord marker. While the subject pronoun is a substitute which replaces a noun that has been previously mentioned, the subject concord marker is an element which occurs obligatorily between a noun subject and the predicate.⁵ In which case a pronoun, like the noun it replaces, occurs immediately to the left of a subject concord marker. The subject concord marker then gets deleted after the pronoun, as happens after a noun subject.

It is not quite clear whether the subject pronoun has inherent tone. It would be reasonable to expect that **it** bears inherent tone like the other pronouns. But since there is no way of determining its actual tone, we will assume, for simplicity, that the subject pronoun is toneless. The tone it bears in surface structure is derived through the shifting of the floating SCM tone on to it. For example, 78 (b) will be derived as in 88.

(a)	(b)	(c)
88. ðzó ð kpòlò →	ɔ ð kpòlò →	ɔ `kpòlò →
(d)		
ð kpòlò.		

At stage (b) ɔ replaces ðzó by pronominalization, at

5. For a detailed discussion of the difference between an SCM and the pronoun, cf. Bamgboṣe (1972) and Ingram (1971).

(c) the vowel features of the SCM are deleted leaving the tone floating, and at (d) the floating SCM tone shifts on to the subject pronoun (cf. 4.3.2.1.4. for the formalization of the SCM segment deletion rule).

4.3.2.1.3. The Shape of the Subject Concord Marker

So far we have encountered only ɔ as a subject concord marker. Since ɔ is identical in shape with the third person singular subject pronoun, one could be tempted to think that the SCM will have the same paradigm as the subject pronoun. We should, therefore, find out whether the SCM exhibits other phonological shapes. Since, as we have seen, the fully specified form of the SCM occurs obligatorily in emphatic sentences, we can find out the shape or shapes of the SCM in emphatic sentences with the pronominals imè , ùwè and iré .

Thus in 89-91

89. $\text{imè } \acute{\text{ɔ}} \text{ ghà rré } (\rightarrow \text{im}^{\acute{\text{ɔ}}}\acute{\text{ɔ}} \text{ ghà rré})$

"it is I who should have come"

90. $\text{ùwè } \acute{\text{ɔ}} \text{ ghà rré } (\rightarrow \text{ùw}^{\acute{\text{ɔ}}}\acute{\text{ɔ}} \text{ ghà rré})$

"it is you who should have come"

91. ɪrē ɔ ghà rré (→ ɪrṣṣ ghà rré)

"it is he who should have come"

we find that ɔ occurs with the first, second and third person pronominal. Nor is it possible to have, for example, 92 in place of 89.

92. ɪmè í ghà rré

I lp SCM

Neither can the SCM be inflected for number because ɔ is used even after plural subjects; e.g.

93. òzó vbV àmè ɔ ghà rré

(→ òzó vbá ! mḃḃ ghà rré)

"it is Ozo and Amẹ who would have come"

94. ɪrà ɔ ghà rré (→ ɪràǎ ghà rré)

"it is they who would have come"

There is, therefore, only one subject concord marker, ɔ, in the language. The paradigm in 4.3.2.1.2. is, therefore, that of the subject pronoun only.

4.3.2.1.4. Derivation of the Subject Concord Marker

In 4.3.2.1.1. we showed that the vowel features of the SCM are deleted, leaving the tone floating, when

the SCM occurs with a subject NP. We shall now further examine the process by which the underlying representation of the SCM is related to its phonetic realizations in the environment of a subject NP. The rules which follow apply only to non-emphatic sentences (cf. 4.3.2.1.1, especially fn. 4, for a reference to the derivation of the phonetic realizations when the SCM occurs with subject NPs in emphatic sentences).

4.3.2.1.4.1. The Deletion of the SCM Segment

When the SCM occurs after an NP, its vowel features are deleted. This can be formalized as PR16.

PR16: SCM Segment Deletion (SCMSD)

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \leq \underline{1} \text{ structure} \\ \propto \text{ tone} \\ \text{SCM} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow [\emptyset \text{ structure}] / \text{NP} + \text{---}$$

By this rule 95-98 will have the following intermediate stages in their derivation.

95. òzó ò ghà rré → òzó `ghà rré

"if Ozo comes"

96. àmè 3 ghà rré → àmè 'ghà rré

"Amẹ would have come"

97. òzò ɔ ghà rré → òzò ' ghà rré

"Ozo would have come"

98. àmè ò ghà rré → àmè ' ghà rré

"if Amẹ comes"

4.3.2.1.4.2. Tonal Segmentalization

After the deletion of the SCM segment the SCM floating tone is segmentalized, that is, it acquires the segmental (or vowel) features of the FV of the preceding NP. Thus 95 - 98 will have the following representations after the application of the tonal segmentalization rule.

95. (a) òzò ò ghà rré

96. (a) àmè é ghà rré

97. (a) òzò ó ghà rré

98. (a) àmè è ghà rré

The tonal segmentalization rule is formalized as PR 17.

PR 17: Tonal Segmentalization (R Seg.)

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \emptyset \text{ stricture} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{l} V \\ \beta F \end{array} \right] / \left[\begin{array}{l} V \\ \beta F \\ \text{NP} \end{array} \right] + -$$

After the application of this rule 95 (a) will undergo further modifications by the application of high tone spreading (b), tonal simplification (c) and vowel contraction (d), in that order.

	(a)	.	(b)	.
95 (a)	òzó	ò	ghà	rré →
	òzóó		ghà	rré →
	(c)	.	(d)	
	ozóó	`	ghà	rré →
	òzó	`	ghà	rré.

The downdrift rules and the floating low tone deletion rule will further apply to produce the final surface form: òzó !ghà kpòlò. cf. 3.2.3. and 3.3.2.2. for the formalization of these rules).

The vowel contraction rule will further apply to 97 (a) and 98 (a).

It may appear clumsy that we delete the vowel features of the SCM only to segmentalized its tone, instead of postulating that the SCM segment assimilates the FV before it is deleted in some cases. However, this alternate analysis would yield the wrong result in all cases. Take 98, for example.

	(a)	.	(b)	.	(c)
98.	àmè	ò	ghà	rré →	àmò
	àmò	ò	ghà	rré →	●àmò
			ghà	rré	

The only way we could derive the correct output, going by this analysis, is to assume that vowel assimilation is progressive; in which case, stage (b) of 98 would be àmè è ghà rré. However, vowel assimilation is normally regressive in the language, and there is no reason why the derivation of the SCM should be an exception.

4.3.2.2. The Auxiliary Marker

An auxiliary marker usually occurs between the subject concord marker and the verb stem. It occurs in all constructions **except** the simple habitual, the simple completive and the simple imperative.

Auxiliary markers are generally either monosyllabic or disyllabic in their phonetic representations. The only exceptions are kàkàbó (marker of the habitual intensive construction) and ká!kàbó or kàká!bó (markers of the completive intensive construction).

The majority of auxiliary markers occur in pairs which oppose incomplete (usually habitual or continuous) action with completive action. In pairs which reflect this kind of opposition, the AM which marks habitual action usually bears a plain high or a plain low tone, the AM which marks continuous action a LH tone pattern

and the marker of completive action a H ` tone pattern (i.e. a high tone followed by a floating low tone).

Examples:

99. Completive Unfulfilled Conditional (kpá`)

àmè kpá` rré, í ghà ghòghó

"if Ame had come, I would have been happy"

100. Habitual Unfulfilled Conditional (kpá)

àmè kpá rré, í ghà ghòghó

"if A. were in the habit of coming, I would have been happy"

101. Completive Concessive (rhé`)

ò rhé` dé, t-ó mú òkàrò

"even though he fell, he still came first"

102. Continuous Concessive

ò rhèé dóló, ìkpòlò ò hòó

"even though he is scrubbing (the floor), it is sweeping that he wants."

Given what we know about the interaction of tone rules and the structure of vowel sequences, we shall postulate that those auxiliary markers which have a H ` tone pattern were originally disyllabic words with two final identical vowels bearing a HL tone pattern. Thus,

kpá' should be kpáà and rhé' should be rhéè at a more abstract level. These final vowel sequences got reduced to a single vowel with a high tone followed by a floating low tone through the application of the tone spreading, tonal simplification and vowel contraction rules as a result of their occurrence before other words, usually verb stems (cf. 3.2.3. and 3.3.2.2.). Let us illustrate with kpá' .

99 (a) kpáà → kpáá → kpáá' → kpá' .

Synchronically, the original final vowel cannot occur in surface representations because auxiliary markers are always followed by at least one other word.

Therefore, in representing the structure of verbal constructions, we shall represent such auxiliary markers as having a CV' structure, since the final vowel never occurs in surface representations.

4.3.2.3. The Verb Stem

By definition a verbal construction must contain a verb stem. A verb stem can be either monosyllabic or disyllabic and always begins with a consonant (cf. 2.1.2.2.2. and 2.2.2.).

4.3.2.3.1. The Tonal Structure of Verb Stems

Edo (Bini) verb stems have been differently analysed as having lexical tone (Melzian 1937) and as exhibiting purely grammatical tone (Wescott 1963: 146-7; Brugbe 1973: 171). Melzian (1937: xii) says that

There are many pairs of verbs differentiated by a combination of vowel length and intonation, one type having a shorter vowel and a high tone in the imperfective form, the other, a longer vowel and a rising tone, e.g. ma [·] "to fit", ma [↗] "to be good".

Melzian seems to think that the tonal difference is more basic than that of length in pairs of verbs such as the above, hence he consistently represents them by showing only the tonal difference.

However, as neither vowel length nor rising tone is known to be independently distinctive in the language (i.e. there is no evidence of distinctive vowel length not accompanied by contour tone, and vice versa), we interpret the long vowel in ma [↗] as a sequence of two vowels bearing a low tone followed by a high tone. That verb stems of the màá type are not monosyllabic (but rather disyllabic) is borne out by the fact that they behave differently from monosyllabic verb stems when they are followed by the simple completive

suffix (4.3.2.4.) and when followed by noun and pronoun objects (chapter V, especially 5.3.2.). We see, therefore, that there is no real basis for contrasting high tone and rising tone in verb stems.

As a matter of fact, since we cannot elicit any minimal tonal contrasts on verb stems independently of their grammatical contexts, we have no basis for representing tone on verb stems in the lexicon.

We are, in effect, in agreement with the conclusion reached by Wescott and Elugbe that Edo (Bini) verb stems exhibit exclusively grammatical tone. We therefore postulate that, although Edo (Bini) verb stems do not have tonal representation in the lexicon, they acquire tonal representation at the syntactic level. Therefore, verb stems obligatorily have tonal representation at the systematic phonemic level.⁶

Verb stems have the tone pattern (L)H (i.e. H if monosyllabic and LH if disyllabic) in the phonetic representation (also see 4.3.2.3.2.). However, in the simple imperative construction, a rule, PR 18, applies to change the high tone to low tone.

6. However, we are not sure exactly how the tones are assigned at the syntactic level. All that we feel sure about at the moment is that verb stems are tonally empty in the lexicon and that they have tonal representation in underlying phonological structure.

PR 18: Simple Imperative High Tone Lowering (SIHHL)

Examples:

103. kpòlò → kpòlò "sweep"

104. wà gbé → wà gbè "you (pl.) dance"

4.3.2.3.2. Classification of Verb Stems

We **classify** verbs stems into two groups according to the structure of the final syllable. As we shall see, the structure of the final syllable of a verb stem is very essential in determining what phonological rules will apply when the verb stem collocates with an object (cf. chapter V, especially 5.1.7. and 5.3.2.) or when the simple completive suffix occurs with it (cf. 4.3.2.4.).

The first group of verb stems is made up of all verb stems which end in a C(G)V syllable (where G means a glide or a non-syllabic vowel), in other words a syllable which has a CV or a CGV structure. Such verb stems may be monosyllabic or disyllabic. Examples of such verb stems are dé "buy", gyé "laugh", lèlé "follow" and lwèlwe "wither".

The second group consists of all the disyllabic verb stems which have a CVV structure, i.e., their final syllable consists of V alone. Examples of such verb stems are khèé "wait for" khié "clean (smth.)", etc.

We shall henceforth refer to the first group as C(G)V verb stems and the latter as CVV verb stems.

4.3.2.4. The Simple Completive Suffix

In the simple completive construction (cf. 4.3.3., exx. 6) a construction suffix -rè obligatorily occurs with the verb stem. The phonetic shape of the suffix depends on the type of verb stem (i.e. whether C(G)V or CVV, cf. 4.3.2.3.2.) with which it occurs, as the following examples will illustrate:

105 (a) bí=rè : òzó !bíl "Ozo vomited"
"vomited"

(b) wíl=rè : èbé !wílírl "a book is lost"
"is (was) lost"

(c) dí=rè : ò díí "he is bold"
"is/was bold"

106 (a) dé=rè : àmè déè "Amẹ fell"
"fell"

(b) yèé=rè : àmè yèéré "Amẹ remembered"
"remembered"

- 107 (a) wú=rè : ò wúù "he died"
"died"
- (b) búù=rè : èrhá !búùrù "the stick broke"
"broke"
- (c) kùú=rè : òzó !kùúrù "Ozo played"
"played"
- 108 (a) kpòlò=rè : àmè kpòlòò "Amẹ swept"
"swept"
- (b) rhòò=rè : òzò !rhòórò "Ozo blasphemed"
"blasphemed"
- (c) só=rè : àmè sóò "Amẹ shouted"
"shouted"
- 109 (a) gyé=rè : ò gyéè "he laughed"
"laughed"
- (b) lèé=rè : òzó !lèérè "Ozo escaped"
"escaped"
- (c) rěé=rè : ò rěérě "he knew"
"knew"
- 110 (a) kòlò=rè : ò kòlòè "he plucked"
"plucked"
- (b) nǒǒ=rè : éwéré !nǒǒrě "Ẹwerẹ asked"
"asked"

(c) t[́]s=rè : òzò !t[́]sè "Ozo lived long"
"lived long"

111 (a) ká=rè : ò káè "he counted"
"counted"

(b) sǎǎ=rè : ò sǎǎrè "he jumped"
"jumped"

(c) tǎ=rè : ò tǎè "he is tall"
"is/was tall"

The surface representation of the suffix is derived by two main rules - the first deletes the consonant of the suffix after C(G)V verb stems while the second assimilates the suffix vowel to some stem vowels.

4.3.2.4.1. Deletion of the Simple Completive Suffix Consonant

When the simple completive suffix occurs with a C(G)V verb stem, its consonant is deleted. This is what happens in all the (a) examples in 105 - 111. The consonant is, however, retained after CVV verb stems such as those in the (b) examples. The rule which deletes r can be roughly formulated as follows (but cf. 5.2.1.):

PR 19: r Deletion (RD)

$$r \rightarrow \emptyset \quad /C(G)V = \text{---}V$$

└ SCS

4.3.2.4.2. The Assimilation of the Simple
Completive Suffix Vowel

The simple completive suffix vowel *e* completely assimilates to final stem vowels which are [l expanded]- i.e. *i*, *ĩ*, *u*, *ũ*, *e* and *o*. This is formalized as PR 20.

PR 20: Simple Completive Suffix Assimilation (SCSA)

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} V \\ 1 \text{ exp.} \\ 2 \text{ height} \end{array} \right] \xrightarrow{\text{SCS}} \left[\begin{array}{l} \alpha \text{ back} \\ \beta \text{ height} \\ \gamma \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] / \left[\begin{array}{l} V \\ 1 \text{ exp.} \\ \alpha \text{ back} \\ \beta \text{ height} \\ \gamma \text{ nasal} \end{array} \right] = ((1 \text{ lateral}))-$$

After assimilating the nasality of the stem vowel, the suffix vowel further changes to $\tilde{e}$ by PR 1 (cf. 3.1.2. and 3.1.3.1.). The consonant r, in those cases where it is not deleted, is nasalized by PR 3 and then becomes the corresponding nasal stop (actually a tapped lateral nasal) by PR 4 (cf. 3.1.3. for PR 3 and PR 4).

By these rules, the surface forms of the verbs in 105 (b), 107 (b), and 111 (a) and (b), for example, will be derived in the following stages:

- 105 (b) wif=rè → wif=r̃ → wífir̃
 107 (b) bũú=rè → bũú=rũ → bũú=r̃ũ → bũú=ɲũ → bũúɲũ
 111 (a) ká=rè → ká=r̃ → káè
 111 (b) sãã=rè → sãã=r̃ → sãã=r̃ → sãã=r̃ẽ → sãã=ɲẽ → sããɲẽ

4.3.2.4.3. Deletion of the Simple Completive Suffix

Whenever another word or morpheme follows a verb in the simple completive construction, the simple completive suffix is deleted. Two examples will suffice to illustrate this:

- (i) the negative construction morpheme $\tilde{V}$, which normally occurs at the end of a clause that is negated, always completely assimilates to the last vowel of the clause (cf. 4.3.2.7.).

When this morpheme occurs immediately after the verb in the simple completive construction it assimilates to the stem vowel and not the suffix vowel. Thus we have the following.

112 (a) ɔ́ dɛ́=è "he bought"

(b) ɔ́ má dɛ́=è=V̇ → ɔ́ má dɛ̀è "he did not buy."

113. (a) ɔ́ ká=è "it got dried"

(b) ɔ́ má ká=è=V → ɔ́ má káà "it did not get dried"

(ii) When an object pronoun occurs immediately following a verb in the simple completive construction, the simple completive suffix is dropped. E.g.

114. ɔ́ ká=è + `vbē → ɔ́ ká!vbē "he counted me"

These two examples clearly show that the simple completive suffix is deleted when another word immediately follows the verb.

There is some evidence that the tone of the simple completive suffix is deleted along with the segments. If a floating low tone were present when a verb in the simple completive construction collocates with an object, a high IV would be downstepped, which is not the case. E.g.

115. (ɔ̃) kɔ̃lɔ̃=è + ékhwé → (ɔ̃) kɔ̃lékhwé

"plucked" "garden egg" "(he) plucked garden eggs"

There is no difference between the phonetic output in 115 and the phonetic output when the verb is used in a non-simple-completive construction, as in 116.

116. (ɔ̃) kɔ̃lɔ̃ + ékhwé → (ɔ̃) kɔ̃lékhwé "(he) plucks garden eggs"

The simple completive suffix deletion rule can then be formulated as PR 21.

PR 21: Simple Completive Suffix Deletion (SCSD)

rè → ∅ / VS = - +
FORM,

This rule states that the simple completive suffix -rè is deleted when any other formative follows it.

4.3.2.5. The Protasis Extra-high Tone

If the protasis, or subordinate clause, of a conditional sentence ends in a word which has a final high tone, the final high tone is said with a pitch slightly higher than normal. For example, in 117 and 118:

117. òzó !ghà rré, ɔ̃ ghá kpòlò

"If Ozo comes he will sweep"

118. àmè kpá !kpòlò, òzò ghà rré

"If Amẹ had swept, Ozo would have come"

the final high tones of rré and kpòlò are higher in the protasēs (underlined) than in the apodosēs (cf. 3.3.1.5.1.; fn. 19).

4.3.2.6. Classification of Verbal Constructions

Verbal constructions can be grouped into two according to the way they behave when they take object pronouns. The two groups are made up of the simple completive construction (SCC) on the one hand, and the non-simple-completive constructions (NSCCS; i.e. all the other constructions) on the other. The need for this classification of verbal constructions will become clear when we consider in chapter V the phonological processes which take place when verbs collocate with objects.

4.3.2.7. The Structure of Negative Verbal Constructions

In Edo (Bini) a verbal construction is negated by the use of one of the three negators *í*, *má* and *gbé`*,

and a clause-final low tone vowel.⁷

The negator *gbé`* is used to negate those constructions which may be referred to as the "imperative" constructions, namely, the simple imperative, the continuous imperative and the exhortative. The negators *í* and *má* are generally used to negate non-past and past actions respectively. A negator always occurs before the auxiliary marker, or the verb stem where there is no auxiliary marker. Generally it is the incomplete AM that is used in both the negative incomplete construction and its negative completive counterpart.

7. The use of a clause-final morpheme to mark negation is also attested in at least one other Edo language - Isoko. In Isoko negation is marked by a clause-final morpheme- *hV* (or *hV̄V̄*) whose final vowel completely assimilates to the final vowel of the last word of the clause. E.g.

- 1 (a) ɔ̄ kpó "he went"
 (b) ɔ̄ kpó hǒ "he did not go"
- 2 (a) ɔ̄ rùé hérǒdò "he saw Herod"
 (b) ɔ̄ rùé hérǒdòhǒ "he did not see Herod"

The only difference between Isoko and Edo (Bini) is that the use of the clause-final morpheme seems to be the only way of marking negation in Isoko.

We are grateful to Carl Hoffmann for bringing the presence of this phenomenon in Isoko to our attention. Data was elicited from Mr. S. Onibere.

The following examples will illustrate the use of the negators:

119 Present Continuous

- (a) òzó !ghá ! kpòlò "O. is sweeping"
 (b) òzó í kpòlòd "O is not sweepint"

120 Past Continuous

- (a) ò ghá!á kpòlò "he was sweeping"
 (b) ò má ghá kpòlòd "he wasn't sweeping"

121 Simple Imperative

- (a) gbè "dance"
 (b) ghé !gbéè "don't dance"

When the third person pronoun ò occurs immediately preceding the negator í, the pronoun assimilates to the negator in backness, i.e. it becomes a front vowel é. This rule is stated as PR 22.

PR 22: Subject Pronoun Backness Assimilation (SPBA)

This rule states that the third person pronoun *o* which occurs immediately before the negator *f* assimilates to the negator in backness.

The clause-final low tone vowel which also marks negative constructions also assimilates to the final vowel of the clause. There are, however, two conditions under which the vowel is not realized phonetically — if the clause ends in a low tone vowel, and at the end of the protasis.

The absence of the low tone vowel phonetically after a clause-final low tone vowel clearly arises from the contraction of the two vowels which are tonally and segmentally identical.

As an illustration of the absence of the clause-final marker of negative constructions in protasis constructions consider 122.

122. *òzò !ghà yó, ò ghá !kpòlò*

"if Ozo goes, he will sweep"

If the apodosis of this sentence is negated as in 122(a), the low tone vowel will be realised phonetically, whereas if it is the protasis that is negated, as in 122 (b), the vowel will not be realized:

122 (a) òzò !ghà yó, è í kpòlòò

"if Ozo goes, he will not sweep".

122 (b) òzò má yó, ò ghá !kpòlò

"if Ozo does not go, he will sweep".

The low tone negative construction marker is retained even when the apodosis occurs first in the sentence, while it is still not realized in the protasis even when the protasis, occurs sentence-finally, as in 122 (c).

122 (c) è í kpòlòò, dégh-ó ,á yó

"he will not sweep if he doesn't go"

The obvious explanation for the non-realization of the clause-final negative construction marker in protasis constructions is the fact that a final high tone in a protasis construction always has an extra-high pitch. This extra-high pitch is maintained even when the construction is negated.

Another feature of negative verbal constructions is that downstepped tones generally do not occur within the construction (i.e. between the subject of the sentence and the verb stem), even where downstep occurs in the affirmative counterpart of the construction.

There are, however, two exceptions to this general statement. The first is that when an auxiliary marker which bears a low tone in the affirmative is used in the negative, it bears a downstepped high tone. E.g.

123 (a) àmèé ghà kpòlóló

"Amẹ would have swept"

(b) àmè í !ghá kpòlólóò

"Amẹ would not have swept"

The second exception is that the tone of the syllable following the negator ghé` is downstepped. This downstep derives from the structure of the negator itself. The instances of downstep arising from these two factors are relatively few.

4.3.3. Exemplification of Verbal Constructions

The Edo (Bini) language makes use of a vast number of verbal constructions. Thirty-five verbal constructions have been identified so far and there is every likelihood that a few more are yet to be discovered.

In listing verbal constructions we give the name of the construction and the formulae abbreviating the structures of the affirmative and negative types. Examples are then given of the affirmative and negative

types.

As pointed out in 4.3.2.2., many verbal constructions occur in pairs which contrast completive action with incomplete (usually habitual or continuous) action. In such cases we list the construction which expresses incomplete action directly after its completive counterpart.

The following is the list of the constructions.

1. Simple Habitual: $S\grave{C}M + VS$; $S\grave{C}M + í + VS + \grave{V}$
 - 124. òzó !kpòlò "Ozo sweeps"
 - 125. òzó í kpòlòò "Ozo does not sweep"
2. Simple Continuous: $S\grave{C}M + ghá\grave{`} + VS$; $S\grave{C}M + í + VS + \grave{V}$
 - 126. ò ghá !rhùlě "he is running"
 - 127. è í rhùléè "he is not running"
3. Past Continuous: $S\grave{C}M + ghá\grave{`}á + VS$;
 $S\grave{C}M + má + ghá + VS + \grave{V}$
 - 128. òzo !ghá!á bí "Ozo was vomiting"
 - 129. òzó má ghá bí "Ozo was not vomiting"
4. Future: $S\grave{C}M + \left. \begin{array}{l} rá\grave{`} \\ ghá\grave{`} \end{array} \right\} + VS$; $S\grave{C}M + í + rá + VS + \grave{V}$

130 (a) ɔ rá !dɔlɔ "he will scrub (the floor)"

(b) ɔ ghá !dɔlɔ

131 ɛ í rá dɔlɔɔ "he will not scrub (the floor)"

We cannot use ghá in the place of rá in the negative construction.

5. Ingressive : S^{CM} + $\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{rá} \\ \text{khȳá} \end{array} \right\} + \text{VS};$

132 (a) úgbó ! rá kpɔlɔ "Ugbo is about to sweep"

(b) úgbó ! khȳá kpɔlɔ

This construction can only be negated in an indirect way; the copula ré (be) is negated and related to the affirmative construction with tV (that). E.g.:

133. ɛ í rɛ t-úgbó khyá kpɔlɔɔ

"it is not the case that Ugbo is about to sweep".

6. Simple Completive: S^{CM} + VS=rɛ; S^{CM} + má + VS=rɛ + V̇

134. ɔ dɛɛ "he bought"

135. ɔ má dɛɛ "he did not buy"

7. Completive Reservative: S^{CM} + té + VS;

S^{CM} + má + té + VS + V̇

136. ɔ té !kpɔlɔ "he swept (but it doesn't appear as if he did)"

137. ð má té kpòlòò "he didn't sweep (but it doesn't appear as if he didn't)"

8. Habitual Reservative: S[̀]CM + té + VS ;

138. ð té yó "he usually goes (but it doesn't appear as if he does)"
S[̀]CM + í + té + VS + ð̂

139. è í té yóò "he usually doesn't go (but it does not appear as if he doesn't)"

9. Simple Conditional: S[̀]CM + ghà + VS ;

S[̀]CM + má + VS + ð̂

140. ð ghà yó, ð ghá !myé òzó

"if he goes, he will see Ozo"

141. ð má yó, ð ghá !myé òzó

"if he does not go, he will see Ozo"

10. Continuous Conditional: S[̀]CM + ghàá + VS;

S[̀]OM + má + ghá + VS + ð̂

142. àmè ghàá rhòó, ó ghì ghá gbé èkhé!kì

"if it is raining, it drenches the traders"

143. àmè é má ghá rhòó, è í gbé èkhé!kì

"if it is not raining, it doesn't drench the traders"

11. Completive Temporal: SCM + ghí` + VS;
 ùgbě + vbV + S`CM + má + VS + ì`

144. ò ghí`!dé, ó ná !v`àá ùhúvbù

"when he fell, he broke his head"

145. ùgbě vb-ó má dé, ó ná ! v`àá ùhúvbù

"(even) when he did not fall, he broke his head"

12. Past Continuous Temporal: S`CM + ghí + VS;

ùgbě + vbV + S`CM + mé + ghá + VS + ì`

146. òzó !ghí k`pá, ibiékà hyá ná !l`éé

"as/when O. was vomiting, all the children fled"

147. ùgbě vb-òzó má ghá k`pá, ibiékà hyá ná !l`éé

"when O. was not vomiting, all the children fled"

13. Completive Consecutive

S`CM + k`é`

k`é` ghí + VS; S`CM + má + VS + ì`

S`CM ná`

148 (a) òbó !ghí ! mwihà gbé, óghiná!bè k`é !ghà dé

"when the diviner consulted the oracle,

ogbinabe appeared"

(b) òbó !ghí !mwinà gbé, ògbiná!bè ké !ogé

(c) òbó !ghí !mwinà gbé, ògbiná!bè ná !ogé

149. òbó !ghí !mwinà gbé, ògbiná!bè má déé

"when the diviner consulted the oracle, ogbinabe
did not appear"

14. Past Continuous Consecutive:

$$\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{SCM} \\ \text{SCM} \end{array} \right] + \left[\begin{array}{c} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{ké` ghá} \\ \text{ké` ghi ghá} \end{array} \right\} \\ \text{ná` ghá} \end{array} \right] + \text{VS}; \text{SCM} + \text{má} + \text{ghá} + \text{VS} + \text{V}$$

150. (a) òzó !ghí kpòlò, ikỹã ná !ghá tìnó kwá

"as O. was sweeping, houseflies were flying
away"

(b) òzó !ghí kpòlò, ikỹã ké !ghá tìnó kwá

(c) òzó !ghí kpòlò, ikỹã ké !ghí ghá tìnó kwá

151. òzó !ghí kpòlò, ikỹã má ghá tìnó kwá

"as O. was sweeping, the houseflies were not flying
away"

15. Habitual Resultative: SCM + ghi + VS;

SCM + í + VS + V

152. ògbiná!bè ghà dé, á ghi rhùlé ...

"when/if ogbinabe appears, one runs ..."

153. ógbíná!bè ghà dé, à í rhùléè ...
 "when/if ogbinabe appears, one does not run ..."
16. Anticipative: S[́]CM + tè + VS
154. U tè rré, í ghá mwègbé
 "before you come, I will be ready"
 This construction cannot be negated.
17. Completive Unfulfilled Conditional:
 SCM + kpá[̀] + VS; á + w-S[́]CM + má + VS + ÷
155. òzó !kpá !rré, í ghà ghògbó
 "if O. had come, I would have been happy"
156. á w-ó!zó má rré, í ghà ghòghó
 "if O had not come (literally, if one were to say that O. did not come) I would have been happy"
18. Habitual Unfulfilled Conditional:
 SCM + kpá + VS; á + w-S[́]CM + í + VS + ÷
157. ò kpá rré, í ghà kpòló
 "if he were in the habit of coming, I would have swept".
158. á w-é í rré, í ghà kpòló
 "if he were not in the habit of coming, I would have swept".

19. Completive Unfulfilled Resultative:

(t-) + S^{CM} + ghà + VS; S^{CM} + í + `ghá + VS + ÷

159. ð kpá !kpòlò, t-í' ghà d̀l̀s

"if he had swept, he would have scrubbed the floor)"

160. ð kpá !kpòlò, é í !ghá d̀l̀s̀̀

"if he had swept, he would not have scrubbed (the floor)"

20. Continuous Unfulfilled Resultative:

(t-) + S^{CM} + ghàá + VS; S^{CM} + í + ghàá + VS + ÷

161. Èdè !kpá d̀l̀s, t-ámèé gha kpòlò

"if Èdè were in the habit of scrubbing (the floor), Ame would have been sweeping"

162. Èdè !kpá d̀l̀s, é í ghàá kpòlò̀̀

"if Èdè were in the habit of scrubbing (the floor), he would not have been sweeping"

21. Completive Concessive:

S^{CM} + rhé + VS; S^{CM} + má + rhèé + VS + ÷

163. ð rhé !dé, s mú òkàrò

"even though he fell, he still came first"

164. ò má rhèé dé, ó mú òkàrò

"even though he did not fall, he still came first"

22. Incompletive Concessive:

S̀CM + rhèé + V̇S; SC̀M + í + rhèé + VS + V̇

165. ò rhèé d̀l̀s̀, ìkpó!l̀ ò hòó

"even though he is scrubbing, it is sweeping that he wants"

166. è í rhèé d̀l̀s̀, ìkpó!l̀ ò hòó

"even though he is not scrubbing, it is sweeping that he wants"

23. Completive Previous Performance:

S̀CM + ká` + VS; S̀CM + má + kàá + VS + V̇

167. òzó !ká !rré

"Ozo had (has) come before"

168. òzó má kàá rréè

"Ozo had (has) not come before"

24. Habitual Previous Performance:

S̀CM + kàá + VS; S̀CM + í + kàá + VS + V̇

169. òzó !kàá kp̀l̀ó

"Ozo used to sweep"

170. òzó í kàá kp̀l̀óò

"Ozo used not to sweep"

25. Completive Emphatic:

S̀CM + wá'í VS; S̀CM + má + wàá + VS + ṽ

*of Isoho
'exclamatory'
'gashim'*

171. òzó !wá !kpòlò

"Ozo really swept"

172. òzó má wàá kpòlòò

"Ozo didn't really sweep"

26. Incompletive Emphatic:

S̀CM + wàá + VS; S̀CM + í + wàá + VS + ṽ

173. ò wàá wíná

"he really works (hard)"

174. è í wàá wínáà

"he doesn't really work hard"

27. Completive Intensive: S̀CM + $\left. \begin{array}{l} ká !kàb́s \\ kàkà!b́s \end{array} \right\} +$ VS;

S̀CM + má + kàkàb́s + VS + ṽ

175. àmè kàkà!b́s kpòlò

"Amẹ swept intensely"

176. àmè má kàkàb́s kpòlòò

"Amẹ did not sweep intensely"

28. Incompletive Intensive: S[̀]CM + kàkàbó + VS;

S[̀]CM + í + kàkàbó + VS + V̂

177. òzó !kàkàbó khwòvbí

"Ozo is very ill"

178. òzó í kàkàbó khwòvbíí

"Ozo is not very ill"

29. Completive Punctuality:

S[̀]CM + rhèrhé + VS; S[̀]CM + má + rhèrhé + VS + V̂

179. òzó rhèrhé !rré

"Ozo came early"

180. òzó má rhèrhé rrée

"Ozo did not come early"

30. Habitual Punctuality: S[̀]CM + rhèrhé + VS;

SCM + í + rhèrhé + VS + V̂

181. òzó !rhèrhé rré

"Ozo habitually comes early"

182. òzó í rhèrhé rrée

"Ozo does not habitually come early"

31. Completive Additional: S[̀]CM + vbé + VS;

S[̀]CM + má + vbèé + VS + V̂

183. úgbó !vbé !kpòlò

"Ugbo also swept (in addition to some other activity)"

OR

"Ugbo, as well as some other persons, swept"

184. úgbó má vbèé kpòlòò

"Ugbo did not sweep too"

32. Incompletive Additional: S[̀]CM + vbèé + VS;

S[̀]CM + í + vbèé + VS + V̇

185. èdèdè vbèé kpòlò

"the old woman also sweeps (in addition to some other activity)" OR

"the old woman, as well as some other persons, sweeps"

186. èdèdè í vbèé kpòlòò

"the old woman does not sweep too"

33. Simple Imperative: (S[̀]CM) + VS; S[̀]CM + ghé + VS + V̇

187. wà kpòlò

"you (pl.), sweep"

188. wà ghé !kpòlòò

"don't you (pl.) sweep"

34. Continuous Imperative: (S[̀]CM) + ghá + VS;
S[̀]CM + ghé + ghi + VS + ÷

189. wà ghá kpòlò

"be sweeping"

190. wà ghé !ghi kpòlòd

"do not be sweeping"

35. Exhortative: S[̀]CM + ghi + VS

191. ú ghi kpòlò

"you should sweep"

192. ghé !kpòlòd

"do not sweep/you should not sweep"

As 192 shows, this construction is negative negated by the simple imperative construction.

CHAPTER V

GRAMMATICALLY CONDITIONED PHONOLOGICAL PROCESSES

5.0. In the process of describing the underlying phonological representations of the sentence constituents in chapter IV we encountered a number of grammatically conditioned phonological rules. These rules have to do either with the determination of the underlying structure of an element which functions in the sentence (such as PR 15: 3p IV Quality, 4.2.2.3.2.) or the surface realization of some underlying element (such as the rules for the derivation of the SCM, 4.3.2.1.4.). These rules had to be introduced in chapter IV for clarity of exposition.

In this chapter we shall describe those grammatically conditioned phonological processes which operate in the noun phrase and the verb phrase; specifically, those phonological processes which are triggered off by the collocation of a noun with a qualifier and the collocation of a verb with an object. The description will be carried out under three broad headings — tone rules, segmental rules and the exceptions to some of the phonological rules.

In describing the phonological processes which operate when verbs collocate with objects we need to classify verbal constructions into two - the simple completive construction (SCC) and the non-simple completive constructions (NSCCs) (cf. 4.3.2.6). Our classification of verb stems into the C(G)V and CVV types (cf. 4.3.2.3.2.) is also crucial in describing phonological processes in verb plus object collocations.

5.1. Tone Rules

5.1.1. Tone Shifting

Consider the following examples from the associative construction. The underlying representations to the left of the arrows are realized as the phonetic representations to the right of the arrows.

1. ðwè + ' + òzò → ðwó 'zò
 "leg" "Ozo" "Ozo's leg"

2. èkùyé + ' + àmè → èkùyá'mè
 "spoon" "Amè" "Amè's spoon"

3. àkòbè + ' + úyí → àkóbúyí
 "iron trap" "Uyi" "Uyi's iron trap"

4. úkpòkpò + ' + úgbó → úkpòkpúgbó
 "stick" "Ugbo" "Ugbo's stick"

The high tone resulting from the collocation of FV with IV in all cases can be analysed as resulting from the influence of the floating high tone between FV and IV.

Similarly, consider the following examples from the possessive pronoun construction.

5. òwá + ' + vbé → òwà vbé
 "house" "my" "my house"

6. úgbó + ' + rùé → úgbò rùé
 "farm" "your" "your farm"

7. èbé + ' + éré → èbèéré
 "book" "his" "his book"

Here again the lowering of the FV high tone can be seen as resulting from the influence of the floating low tone. When a verb occurs with a first or second person pronoun object, in non-simple completive constructions, the FV high tone is also lowered. E.g.

8. (ò) gbé + 'vbé → (ò) gbè vbé
 (he) "beat" "me" "(he) beats me"

9. (àmè) ghèé + `rùé → (àmè) ghè rùé
 (Amè) "look at""you" "(Amè) looks at you"

We shall postulate that a floating tone raises or lowers a preceding segmental (or FV) tone through the process of tone shifting. By this process a floating tone shifts on to an FV tone and literally replaces the FV tone¹.

The effect of the tone shifting rule is evident in the phonetic representation when the FV tone and the floating tone are not identical; when the two tones are identical the tone shifting rule does not alter the phonetic realization of the underlying segmental tone. Thus the tone shifting rule also applies in 2, and 10, for example.

10. òwè + ` + vbé → òwè vbé
 "leg" "my" "my leg"

The tone shifting rule is formalized as PR 23.

1. Although Hyman and Schuh (1974:94-95) see tone shifting as involving the movement of a segmental tone on to a following segment, there is no reason to restrict this process to segmental tones.

PR 23: Tone Shifting (TSH)

SD: [V] [∅ structure]
 [α tone] [β tone]
 1 2
 Assoc., Pro.

SD: .1 2 → [1] [2]
 [V] [∅]
 [β tone]

(where α and β may or may not stand for the same value of tone).

This rule states that the floating tone which occurs in the associative construction or when a pronoun occurs after another word shifts on to the preceding segmental tone and completely replaces it.

The effect of the tone shifting rule can be illustrated with the following intermediate stages in the derivation of 1 and 5.

1 (a) òwè + ' + òzó → òwé + òzó

5 (a) òwá + ' + vbé → òwà + vbé

5.1.2. Tonal Segmentalization

Consider the following examples from the adjectival construction.

11. èvbè + `dè → èvbèédà
 "word" "bad" "a bad word"
12. òghèdè + `kèkà → òghèdèékèkà
 "plantain" "ordinary" "ordinary plantain"
13. òwá + `nà → òwá nà
 "house" "this" "this house"
14. òwá + `hyá → òwá !hyá
 "house" "all" "the entire house"
15. èghè + `hyá → èghè hyá
 "time" "all" "all the time"

In 11 and 12 the underlying floating high tone has clearly acquired the segmental features of the FV in the phonetic representation. In 13-15 the floating tones also acquire the segmental features of the FVs, but in these cases other rules further apply before the phonetic representation is reached; vowel

contraction takes place in 13 and 15 while 14 is derived through the application of high tone spreading, tonal simplification, and contraction, in that order.

Another instance of the segmentalization of a floating tone was encountered in 4.3.2.1.4.2. where the floating SCM tone acquires the segmental features of an FV. We shall therefore revise the tonal segmentalization rule (PR 17) to cater for both the SCM floating tones and the adjective floating tones.

PR 17 (Revised): Tonal Segmentalization (TSeg.)

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \emptyset \text{ stricture} \\ \alpha \text{ tone} \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{l} V \\ \beta \text{ F} \end{array} \right] / \left[\begin{array}{l} V \\ \beta \text{ F} \end{array} \right] + \text{---} \\ \text{SCM, Adj.} \qquad \text{NP}$$

This rule states that an SCM or adjective floating tone acquires the segmental features of the FV of the preceding NP.

5.1.3. Low Tone Raising

We have seen in 5.1.1. that in the associative construction the FV tone is raised through the shifting of the construction floating high tone on to it. However,

if the head noun in an associative construction has an all low tone pattern (e.g. àkòbè "iron trap", òzùkpògyèwà "second-in-command") all but the initial low tone of the noun are also raised. E.g.

2. àkòbè + ' + úyì → àkóbúyì
 "iron trap" "Uyi" "Uyi's iron trap"
16. ùgbàlètò + ' + àyì → ùgbálétáyì
 "head-tie" "Ayi" "Ayi's head-tie".
17. òghèdè + ' + úgbó → òghédúgbó
 "plantain" "Ugbo" "Ugbo's plantain"

Therefore, in addition to the tone shifting rule we shall require a rule which can iterate the raising of all but the initial low tone of a head noun with an all-low tone pattern. This rule will have to be constrained to raise only a low tone which occurs preceding a high tone derived from an underlying low tone. It is this constraint on the low tone raising rule that prevents the non-initial low tones in words such as àkàsá "corn pudding", èdèdé "an old woman", and ògèdègbé (a personal name) from being raised.

The low tone raising rule is formalized as PR 24.

PR 24: Low Tone Raising (LTR)

[4 tone] → [2 tone] / + [4 tone] X - [2 tone]

| Derived from
[4 tone]

(where X = 0 or any number of low tones).

This rule states that a low tone which occurs immediately preceding a high tone derived from an underlying low tone will become high. This rule keeps reapplying until all low tones, except the word-initial one, are raised (cf. 3.1.2, PR 2 and fn. 2.). This rule provides another example of the need for permitting rules with derivational constraints in generative phonology (cf. 3.2.1.1.).

The low tone raising rule does not need to be constrained to apply only in the associative construction. It so happens that it is only in the associative construction that an FV low tone can become high. Presumably low tone raising would apply in some other construction if the FV low tone of a noun with an all-low tone pattern could become high in such a construction.

5.1.4. High Tone Lowering

When a Polysyllabic head noun which has an all-low tone pattern or which ends in a HL tone pattern collocates with a nominal qualifier which has a low tone IV, the tone resulting from the contraction of FV and IV is low. E.g.

18. àbábè + ' + òzó → àbábòzó
 "witchcraft" "Ozo" "Ozo's witchcraft"
20. àkòbè + ' + òfě → àkóbòfě
 "iron trap" "rat" "iron trap for catching rats"
21. íghú!húvbũ + ' + ùgò → íghú!húvbũgò
 "tax" "Ugo" "Ugo's tax"
22. ùgbàlètò + ' + àmè → ùgbálétàmè
 "head-tie" "Amẹ" "Amẹ's head tie"

In collocations involving other types of nominals in the associative construction the tone resulting from the contraction of FV and IV is always high. The following examples contrast with 18-22.

23. úkpòkpò + ' + òzó → úkpòkpó!zó
 "stick" "Ozo" "Ozo's stick"

24. $\text{ímí'ná} + ' + \text{ámè} \rightarrow \text{ímí'ná'mè}$
 "dream" "Amè" "Amè's dream"

25. $\text{ùgbàlètò} + ' + \text{áyì} \rightarrow \text{ùgbàlétáyì}$
 "head-tie" "Ayì" "Ayì's head-tie"

Thus we see that for the juncture tone to be low the head noun must have an all-low or a final HL tone pattern, even if it is only in its underlying structure. A high tone juncture is realized in 24 because of the penultimate underlying floating low tone.

In deriving the juncture low tone in 18-22, we assume that the tone shifting rule first applies to raise the IV tone, as in all other kinds of collocation in the associative construction. Thus 18 and 22, for example, will have the following intermediate stages in their derivation.

18 (a) $\text{àbábè} + ' + \text{òzò} \rightarrow \text{àbábé} + \text{òzò}$

22. (a) $\text{ùgbàlètò} + ' + \text{ámè} \rightarrow \text{ùgbàlètó} + \text{ámè}$

In 22 the iterative low tone raising rule (PR 24) further applies to give $\text{ùgbàlétó} + \text{ámè}$.

The derived FV high tone then changes into a low tone if (i) it is immediately preceded by a high tone and (ii) the IV tone is low. Thus 18 and 22 will be further derived as in 18 (b) and 22 (b).

18. (b) àbábé + òzó → àbábè + òzó

22. (b) ùgbálétó + àmè → ùgbálètò + àmè

The vowel assimilation, word boundary deletion and vowel contraction rules then apply to derive the phonetic realizations - àbábòzó and ùgbálètàmè .

The rather tight constraints on the lowering of the FV high tone are essential for the derivation of the correct phonetic output. The high tone which changes to low has to be one which is derived from an underlying low tone, otherwise the FV high tones in words like ùkéké (stick) and úgbó would also be lowered. The constraint that the derived high tone has to be immediately preceded by another high tone prevents the derived FV high tones in cases such as 23 and 24 from changing into low tones. Moreover, this rule has to be ordered to apply after the iterative low tone raising rule (PR 24). Otherwise cases such as 20 and 22 cannot be accounted for.

The derived high tone lowering rule can be formalized as PR 25.

PR 25: Derived High Tone Lowering (DHTL)

$$[2 \text{ tone}] \rightarrow [4 \text{ tone}] / [2 \text{ tone}] \text{ --- } + [4 \text{ tone}]$$

Derived
from [4 tone]

Nom.

This rule states that an FV high tone derived from a low tone becomes a low tone if it immediately follows a high tone and precedes a nominal IV low tone. We do not need to specify the FV as belonging to a noun (and not a verb because it is only nouns that can have a final derived high tone when collocating with a nominal).

The low tone resulting from the collocation of FV and IV could alternatively be derived by assuming that the high tone spreading, tonal simplification and vowel contraction rules apply, as in all other cases, yielding a H^s. This high which results from the contraction of FV and IV then changes to low. The following alternative derivation of 18 will illustrate.

- (a) (b)
18. (c) àbábè + ' + òzó → àbábé + òzó →
- (c) (d) (e)
- àbábó + òzó → àbábóòzó → àbábóôzó →
- (f) (g) (h) (i)
- àbábóó`zó → àbábó`zó → àbábò`zó → àbábòzó

There are at least two reasons why we should reject this analysis in favour of our previous one. Firstly the constraint that high tone lowering takes place only where the FV high tone is a derived tone would be difficult to state in any clear terms if we were to assume that the FV contracts with IV before the resultant high tone is lowered. We would then have to add a rather clumsy constraint that the high tone resulting from the contraction of FV and IV is lowered only if the FV high tone is derived from a low tone. Secondly, it is much simpler to assume that the derived FV high tone is lowered before contraction takes place. Apart from the clumsiness that results from applying the contraction rule (and all the rules which apply before it) first, we go through far fewer stages if we directly lower the derived FV high tone. In the alternative

analysis (as in 18 (c)) we would even require a new rule which merges a floating low tone with a preceding segmental low tone.

5.1.5. High Tone Postponement

When a verb collocates with a LH object (i.e. a word which begins with a low tone and has one or more high tones anywhere else in its structure) in the non-simple completive constructions (cf. 4.3.2.6) the vowel resulting from the contraction of FV and IV bears a low tone. E.g.

26. (̀) ká + èdèdé → (̀) kèdèdé

"count" "old woman" "(he) counts the old woman"

27. (̀ rhèé) kòkó + àgbá!kà → (̀ rhèé) kòkàgbá!kà

"feed" "crocodile" "(even though he is) feeding the crocodile"

28. (̀) kpèé + ògó → (̀) kpògó

"beat" "bottle" "(he) beats the bottle"

29. (̀) gbé + èkpàkpàhùvbàgǎ → (̀) gbèkpàkpàhùvbàgǎ

"kill" "scorpion" "(he) kills scorpions"

number of low tones followed by a high tone. We do not need to state that the LH word could have any number of high tones because the first high tone is all we need to trigger off the high tone postponement rule.

5.1.6. Tonal Absorption

Consider the following examples of the collocation of verb stems with objects which have an all low tone pattern.

30. dé + àmè → dámè [- \]

"buy" "water" "buy water"

31. (ò) dé + òghèdè → (ò) dóghèdè [(-) - \ _]

"buy" "plantain" "(he) buys plantain"

32. (ò) ghèé + èkì → (ò) ghèékì [(-) - - \]

"look at" "market" "(he) is looking at the market"

33. (ò) ghèé + èrè → (ò) ghèérè [(-) - - \]

"look at" "him" "(he) looks at him"

In verb plus object collocations such as these the second low tone of the noun occurs immediately after a high tone in the phonetic representation and this low tone is realized phonetically as a high fall.

However this phonetic representation cannot be derived with the rules so far encountered, by which 30, for example, would be derived in the following stages:

	(a)		(b)		(c)	
30	dé + àmè	→	dá + àmè	→	dáàmè	→
	(d)		(e)		(f)	
	dáàmè	→	dáá`mè	→	dá`mè	

After stage (f) the downdrift rules apply and the tone of mè gets a level pitch; then the floating low tone deletion rule deletes the floating low tone before mè. Thus the tonetic representation would be * [~ _], which is not the correct tonetic representation of 30.

It would appear that something different from what we have just postulated happens after stage (f). Before the downdrift rules begin to apply, the floating low tone in dá`mè is absorbed into the following low tone, so that by the time the downdrift rules begin to apply the floating low tone is no longer there to condition the tonetic realization of the low tone of -mè.

The tonal absorption rule can be stated as PR 27.

only move a floating tone on to a vowel segment whose tone is identical with the floating tone.

Presumably tonal absorption can affect a floating high tone followed by a segmental high tone. However, since this type has not been encountered in Edo (Bini) we make the tonal absorption rule specific to low tones.

5.1.7. Simple Completive Low Tone Raising

In the simple completive construction when a CVV verb stem collocates with a LH noun (cf. 5.1.5.) the low tone of the verb stem is raised to high. This raising of the VS low tone does not happen when a verb in the simple completive construction occurs with other noun objects. Thus contrast 33 and 34 with 35 and 36:

33. (ò) bùú = rè³ + àmè → (ò) bùámè
 "went to meet" " Amẹ " "(he) went to meet Amẹ"

34. (ò) hêé = rè + ókà → (ò) hòókà
 "packed" "maize" "(he) packed maize"

3. Although the simple completive suffix is deleted whenever a verb occurs with an object (cf. 4.3.2.4.3.), it is represented here in the underlying structure to indicate that we are dealing with the simple completive construction.

35. (ò) bùú = rè + òzó → (ò) bwó!zó
 "went to meet" "Ozo" "(he) went to meet Ozo"
36. (ò) ghèé = rè + òbó → (ò) ghó!bó
 "looked at" "hand" "(he) looked at the hand"

The CVV low tone is also raised when the VS collocates with any object pronoun in the simple completive construction. E.g.

37. (ò) ghèé = rè + `vbé → (ò) ghé!vbé
 "looked at" "me" "(he) looked at me"
38. (ò) khèé = rè + `rùé → (ò) khé!rùé
 "waited for" "you" "(he) waited for you"
39. (ò) yèé = rè + òrè → (ò) yó!ré
 "attracted" "him" "(it)attracted him)"

The pronouns in 37 and 38 have a LH tone pattern (taking the initial floating tone into account), just like the nouns before which a CVV VS low tone is raised.

The pronoun 39 has an underlying LL tone pattern and we would normally not expect the low tone raising rule to apply here. However, the raising of the final low tone of the pronoun suggests that this final low tone

is raised before the CVV low tone raising rule applies. The raising of the final low tone of the pronoun creates the proper input to the CVV low tone raising rule.

Therefore in deriving the phonetic representation of 39 we shall first apply the rule which raises the final low tone of a LL pronoun when the pronoun occurs with a verb stem in the simple completive construction. This rule is formalized as PR 28.

PR 28: Pronoun Final Low Tone Raising (PFLTR)

$$[4 \text{ tone}] \rightarrow [2 \text{ tone}] / \begin{array}{l} \text{V S} + \text{VC} - \\ \text{SCC} \quad \text{Pro.} \end{array}$$

After this the CVV verb stem low tone raising rule, PR 29, applies.

PR 29: CVV Low Tone Raising (CVVLTR)

$$[4 \text{ tone}] \rightarrow [2 \text{ tone}] / \begin{array}{l} \text{C} - \text{V} + [4 \text{ tone}]^n [2 \text{ tone}] \\ \text{VS, SCC} \quad \text{object} \end{array}$$

This rule states that the low tone of a verb stem in the simple completive construction is raised to high when the VS occurs preceding a LH object.

We shall illustrate these rules by providing the full derivation of 39.

- (a) (b)
39. (a) (ò) yèé=rè + òrè → yèé + òrè →
- (c) (d) (e)
- yèó + òrè → yòó + òrè → yòó + òré
- (f) (g) (h)
- yóó + òré → yó + òré → yóòré →
- (i) (j) (k)
- yóòré → yóó`ré → yó`ré

The pronoun final low tone raising rule applies at stage (e) to raise the final tone of òrè and the CVV low tone raising rule applies at (f) to raise the low tone of the verb stem.

5.2. Segmental Rules

The segmental rules that will be discussed here concern the derivation of the reduced forms of the second person pronoun, `rùé.

When the second person pronoun collocates with a C(G)V verb stem, the pronoun loses its initial consonant.

This leads to further changes resulting from the interaction of the FV with the derived IV. However, when the second person pronoun interacts with a CVV verb stem the pronoun does not lose any of its segments. Thus in 40 and 41:

40. (ò) ghèé + `rùé → (ò) ghè rùé
 "look at" "you" "(he) is looking at you"

41. (ò) rhàá + `rùé → (ò) rhà rùé
 "steal from" "you" "(he) steals from you"

the pronoun retains all its segments whereas it is reduced in 43-49:

43. (ò) sí + `rùé → (ò) syòó
 "pull" "(he) pulls you"

44. (ò) sú + `rùé → (ò) sùé
 "escort" "(he) is escorting you"

45. (ò) lèlè + `rùé → (ò) lèlùé
 "follow" "(he) follows you"

46. (ò) kòkó + `rùé → (ò) kòkùé
 "feed" "(he) feeds you"
47. (ò) dè + `rùé → (ò) dòó
 "buy" "(he) is buying you"
48. (ò) lèghó + `rùé → (ò) lèghòó
 "be difficult" "(it) is difficult for you"
49. (ò) bàbá + `rùé → (ò) bàbàá
 "watch" "(he) is watching you"

It is however possible to retain all the segments of the pronoun even in collocations such as 43-49, but the reduced forms are far more common.

A similar reduction of the second person pronoun also happens when the pronoun occurs with some nouns. E.g.

50. íyé + ` + rùé → íyùé
 "mother" "your mother"
51. àrò + ` + rùé → àrùé
 "eye" "your eye"

52. òbò + ` + rùé → òbòó
 "hand" "your hand"

53. érhá + ` + rùé → érhàá
 "father" "your father"

However, the nouns with which the second person pronoun contracts are very few in number and are therefore regarded as the exception rather than the rule in noun plus second person pronoun collocations. Our rules for deriving the contracted form of the second person pronoun will therefore refer specifically to the very plus object collocation only.

We shall now discuss the rules required to derive the various phonetic representations when the second person pronoun collocates with a C(G)V verb stem.

5.2.1. r Deletion

The consonant *r* is deleted under exactly the same conditions both in the simple completive suffix (SCS) and in the second person pronoun; namely, when the simple completive suffix or the second person pronoun occurs with a C(G)V verb stem. We shall therefore revise the *r*

deletion rule, PR 19 (cf. 4.3.2.4.1.).

PR 19 (Revised): r Deletion (RD)

$r \rightarrow \emptyset / C(G)V + \text{---} X$
 SC8, 2p.

The use of + after C(G)V implies either a word boundary or a formative boundary since a stronger boundary always coincides with a weaker boundary but not vice versa (cf. 1.4.5.).

Following the application of PR 19, 43, 45 and 46, for example, will have the following stages in their derivation.

	(a)	(b)	(c)
43. (3)	si + `rùé	→ si + rùé	→ si + ùé

	(a)	(b)	(c)
45. (3)	lèlé + `rùé	→ lèlè + rùé	→ lèlè + ùé

46. (3)	kòkó + `rùé	→ kòkò + rùé	→ kòkò + ùé
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The tone shifting rule (PR. 23, 5.1.1.) applies at

(b) and the r deletion rule applies at (c) .

5.2.2. Mutual Vowel Assimilation

An FV e or o assimilates to the derived pronoun IV (i.e. u) by the vowel assimilation rule (PR 7), as 45 and 46 will illustrate.

45. lèlè + ùé → lèlù + ùé

46. kòkò + ùé → kòkù + ùé

After the deletion of word boundary the two identical vowels contract, thus yielding lèlùé and kòkùé.

However, if the FV is e, o or a, i.e. if it is unexpanded, the vowels ùé of the pronoun mutually assimilate to each other. That is, e assimilates the backness of u while u assimilates the height of e, yielding òó. If we assume the prior application of tone shifting and r deletion, the mutual assimilation rule will apply to 47-49 as follows.

47. dè + ùé → dè + òó

48. lòghè + ùé → lòghè + òó

49. bàbà + ùé → bàbà + òó

The mutual assimilation rule can be formalized as PR 30.

PR 30: Mutual Vowel Assimilation (MVA)

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \text{ height} \\ 3 \text{ back} \\ 1 \text{ exp.} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 3 \text{ height} \\ 1 \text{ back} \\ 0 \text{ exp.} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 3 \text{ height} \\ 3 \text{ back} \\ 0 \text{ exp.} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 3 \text{ height} \\ 3 \text{ back} \\ 0 \text{ exp.} \end{bmatrix} / [0 \text{ exp}] + -$$

vs -

After the application of PR 30, FV ϵ and $\circ$ assimilate to the derived IV $\circ$ (vacuously in the case of FV $\circ$). The two tonally identical vowels then contract after the deletion of word boundary. Thus 47 and 48 will be further derived in the following stages:

47. $d\acute{\epsilon} + \circ\acute{\circ} \rightarrow d\grave{\circ} + \circ\acute{\circ} \rightarrow d\grave{\circ}\circ\acute{\circ} \rightarrow d\grave{\circ}\circ$

48. $l\grave{o}gh\grave{\circ} + \circ\acute{\circ} \rightarrow \text{---} \rightarrow l\grave{o}gh\grave{\circ}\circ\acute{\circ} \rightarrow l\grave{o}gh\grave{\circ}\circ$

In the case of FV a , the vowels of the pronoun assimilate to it.

49. $b\grave{a}b\grave{a} + \circ\acute{\circ} \rightarrow b\grave{a}b\grave{a} \acute{\circ}\acute{\circ} \rightarrow b\grave{a}b\grave{a} + \acute{a}\acute{a} \rightarrow$

$b\grave{a}b\grave{a}\acute{a}\acute{a} \rightarrow b\grave{a}b\grave{a}\acute{a}$

The irregular assimilation involving FV a is not uncommon (cf. 5.3.2.).

The surface realizations resulting from the collocation of the second person pronoun with unexpanded FVs could be derived differently. We could assume that in the case of FV ϵ and σ FV assimilates to the IV, yielding $\grave{u} + \grave{u}\acute{\epsilon}$. After boundary deletion the two identical vowels contract, yielding $\grave{u}\acute{\epsilon}$. It is this derived $\grave{u}\acute{\epsilon}$ that is affected by the mutual vowel assimilation rule.

The mutual assimilation rule still has to be posited, otherwise we would not be able to account for the assimilation and contraction of $\grave{\epsilon} + \grave{u}\acute{\epsilon}$ to $\grave{o}\acute{o}$.

In the case of FV a, the vowels of the pronoun assimilate to it.

There is one good reason why this alternate analysis has to be rejected. By this analysis the conditioning of the mutual assimilation rule cannot be stated in any clear manner. After the FV has contracted with the IV we can no longer separate those instances where the pronoun collocates with FV ϵ and σ from those in which

it collocates with FV e and o . Thus there would be no principled way of separating those cases of ûé which undergo mutual vowel assimilation from those which do not.

The analysis so far leaves one case unexplained; that is, the application of MVA to ûé when it occurs after the apparently expanded vowel i, as in 43. This case is being treated as an exception which could have arisen historically from the merger of *i with i ; in which case the i in a word like si is possibly historically an unexpanded vowel (cf. 5.3.1. for details).

5.2.2.1. Avoidance of Surface Homonymy

The mutual vowel assimilation (MVA) rule is natural only to the extent that it yields unexpanded vowels after unexpanded FV. But it is a costly rule in that it is highly restricted. The rule does not apply to any vowel sequences other than ûé , and even then it is not all instances of ûé that undergo it. In other words the rule would have been more natural if it could also change ûé to oo after expanded FVs.

It would appear that MVA has arisen from a need to avoid as much homonymy as possible in the phonetic representations of the collocation of FV with the second person pronoun⁴. The collocation of *ûé* with FV e, o and u already yields *ûé* in the phonetic representation, a situation which brings about surface homonymy when we have verb stems in which e, o and u occur after the same consonant, as in *sé* (sew), *só* (hit) and *sú* (escort). If the normal vowel assimilation rule were to also apply when *ûé* collocates with FV e, o and a, then more underlying contrasts would be obliterated in the surface representations. We can therefore hypothesize that MVA is motivated by the need to avoid too many instances of surface homonymy.

4. R.W. Wilkinson, currently the chief exponent of the homonymy avoiding principle in phonology, has in two recent papers, (1975 (a) and 1975 (b)), shown that many "phonologically unexpected or inexplicable rule applications and interactions" (1975 (a): 527) can be explained by the need to preserve as many underlying contrasts as possible in phonetic representations.

5.3. The Exceptions

In a number of cases some phonological units do not behave in the way predicted by the rules so far presented in this study. There are at least two reasons why we have to treat such cases as exceptions. Firstly, those cases which cannot be accounted for by the rules are far fewer than those which the rules can account for. Secondly, it would not be natural, even from a universal point of view, to treat such cases as the norm rather than the exception.

Most of the exceptions involve the process of vowel assimilation; either some FV which is expected to assimilate to an IV fails to do so or the assimilation process in a particular instance is different from the general one. We treat the exceptions in three sub-groups; those whose deviance have possibly arisen from historical vowel mergers, those in which vowel assimilation is partial and those which involve tonal inversion.

5.3.1. Vowel Harmony and Historical Vowel Mergers

5.3.1.1. Nouns

In a few nouns FV o changes to u and FV e and ē change to i and ĭ respectively when the FV occurs with an IV. E.g.

52. àrò + ókpá → àrùókpá
 "eye" "one" "one eye"
53. èvbò + ' + òzò → èvbwólzò
 "town" "Ozo" "Ozo's town"
54. èkòò + ' + ésí → èkwésí
 "stomach" "horse" "a horse's stomach"
55. àrò + ' + Vrè → àrùórè
 "eye" "his" "his eye"
56. òsè + ókpá → òsìókpá
 "friend" "one" "one friend"
57. òtḗḗ + ' + áyì → òtṽṽyì
 "relative" "Ayi" "Ayi's relative"

It would appear that those instances of o which change to u, and of e and ě which change to i and ĭ were not historically o, e and ě. Most probably the deviant o's developed from original *o while the deviant e and ě developed from original *i and *ĭ.

This hypothesis about the origins of these deviant vowels is supported by studies carried out by Elugbe (1973)

and Hoffmann (1973). Elugbe reconstructs a nine-vowel system for proto-Edo, and postulates that these vowels were organized into two harmonic sets grouping the expanded vowels and the unexpanded ones into two separate sets; i.e.

<u>Expanded Set</u>		<u>Unexpanded Set</u>	
i	u	ɪ	ʊ
e	o	ɛ	ɔ
			a

Elugbe further observes that

If the nine-vowel system is reduced to a seven-vowel system, the two vowels most frequently "lost" — the two vowels which lose their identity — are *ɪ and *ʊ.

(P. 336).

In such cases the vowel *ɪ could merge with i, e or ɛ and *ʊ could merge with u and o. Actually Elugbe (p. 389) reconstructs PE *ɛ-dhʊ (pl. a-dhʊ) "eye" (Edo (Bini) àrò, cf. exx. 52 and 55).

Hoffmann (1973) reports a case of historical vowel merger in Okpe, an Edo language. Okpe phonetically operates

a seven-vowel system (like Edo (Bini)), but with synchronically productive vowel harmony. However, two of the vowels, e and o, can each belong to the expanded and the unexpanded vowel harmony sets. Hoffmann then postulates that in all those cases where e and o behave like members of the unexpanded set, we should regard them as "recent developments from some other vowels, probably *ɨ and *y"⁵.

Apart from the corroboratory evidence from proto-Edo and Okpe, there is some internal evidence in Edo (Bini) to lend further support to the hypothesis about the historical origins of deviant o, e and $\tilde{e}$. All the deviant vowels in 52-57 occur with unexpanded prefix vowels, apparently reflecting the unexpanded origins of o, e and $\tilde{e}$. We therefore see that the deviance of these vowels arises most probably from their historical origins.

5.3.1.2. Verb Stems

In all CVV verb stems and in all monosyllabic verb stems which have the vowel o (i.e. Coo or Co) this vowel (the FV₂ in the case of CVV verb stems) changes to u when the verb stem collocates with an IV. E.g.

5. ɨ and y are equivalent to ɪ and o respectively in our transcription.

58. (ò) dó + éwù → (ò) dwe'wù
 "knit" "shirt" "(he) is knitting a shirt"
59. (ò) só + òsàzè → (ò) sòsàzè
 "hit" "Osaze" "(he) is hitting Osaze"
60. (ò) hòó + èfè → (ò) hùéfè
 "seek for" "riches" "(he) is seeking for riches"
61. (ò) lòó + íghó → (ò) lùíghó
 "use" "money" "(he) uses money"
62. (ò) lòó + èrè → (ò) lùérè
 "use" "it" "(he) uses it"

This vowel does not, however, change to u when it occurs in disyllabic C(G)V verb stems. E.g.

63. (ò) kpòlò + èkì → (ò) kpóléki
 "sweep" "market" "(he) sweeps the market place"
64. (ò) kòkó + òmó → (ò) kòkòmó
 "look after" "child" "(he) looks after the child"

One could be tempted to postulate that, like the deviant o's in nouns, all the o's which change to u in

verb stems came from original *ə . However, the number of verbs involved in this change is so large that one cannot plausibly account for their deviance by postulating original *ə in all cases.

Possibly, a detailed diachronic and comparative investigation of this class of verbs will reveal the cause or causes of the deviance of these verbs. But since that kind of investigation is beyond the scope of this study, we cannot do more here than draw attention to the problem.

5.3.2. Partial Vowel Assimilation

When CVV verb stems with the vowels ϵ and $\circ$ (i.e. C $\epsilon\epsilon$ and C $\circ\circ$) collocate with IV, the FV₁ completely assimilates to the IV but the FV₂ only assimilates the backness of the IV. E.g.

65. (ə) khèé + úyi → (ə) khòúyi
 "wait for" "Uyi" "(he) is waiting for Uyi"

66. (ə) vèé + òwá → (ə) vòowá
 "scatter" "house-hold" "(he) is scattering the household"

67. (ò) vb^éé + íghó → (ò) vb^éíghó
 "have" "money" "(he) has money"
68. (ò) rhòó + édò → (ò) rhèédò
 "pick" "termite" "(he) is picking termites"
69. (ò) rhòó + íghó → (ò) rhèíghó
 "pick" "money" "(he) is picking money"
70. (ò) sòó + ùkpò → (ò) sòùkpò
 "tear" "cloth" "(he) is tearing the cloth"

The FV₂ however completely assimilates to IV a, presumably because a is neither back nor front.

We also find that in CVV verb stems FV₂ a fails to assimilate to IV. E.g.

71. (ò) làá + úgbó → (ò) làúgbó
 "enter" "farm" "(he) enters the farm"
72. (ò) ghàá + èbé → (ò) ghàèbé
 "share out" "book" "(he) is sharing out books"
73. (ò) tàá + ébú → (ò) tàébé
 "imitate" "Ebu" "(he) imitates Ebu"

The failure of a to assimilate can be seen as a kind of backness assimilation, since a is neither front nor back; it has no backness to give up, and therefore retains its central position.

The cases of partial assimilation just discussed are the only ones so far encountered in the language (except that the mutual vowel assimilation rule could be considered a special kind of partial assimilation). Here again, given our present state of knowledge of Edo (Bini) and the Edo languages generally, there is no way we can explain these "deviant" assimilations. Only detailed investigations of a kind beyond the scope of the present study can, hopefully, yield any clues.

5.3.3. Tonal Inversion

The final HL tone pattern of the nouns èvbíí "thing" and òvbáá (pl. èvbáá; "person") change to LH when they collocate with high tone initial numerals (ókpá, éhá "six" and ógbá "thirty") and with adjectival qualifiers which have initial floating high tones ('nà, 'nif, 'kékà, and 'dà . E.g.

74. èvbíí + 'dǎ → èvbíídǎ
 "thing" "bad" "bad thing"
75. èvbíí + ókpá → èvbíókpá
 "thing" "one" "one thing"
76. òvbǎǎ + 'nà → òvbǎǎnà
 "person" "this" "this person"
77. òvbǎǎ + 'kèkǎ → òvbǎǎkèkǎ
 "person" "ordinary" "an ordinary person"

This tonal inversion does not take place when the nouns collocate with other types of qualifiers. E.g.

78. èvbíí + ùgyé → èvbíyú!gyé
 "thing" "twenty" "twenty things"
79. èvbǎǎ + 'hyá → èvbǎ!hyá
 "person" "all" "all persons"

In cases such as 78 and 79, the derivation is normal. Before the head nouns èvbíí and èvbǎǎ collocate with their respective qualifiers, their complex FVs get simplified through high tone spreading, tonal simplification and vowel contraction. E.g.

èvbāā̃ → èvbāā̃̃ → èvbāā̃̃̃ →

èvbā̃̃̃ (cf. 3.3.2.2.2.)

If the final HL had changed to LH in 78 and 79, their surface tonal representations would have been similar to that of 80.

80. òkhòó + `hyá → òkhòó ! hyá
 "evil deed" "all" "all evil deeds"

Here again we have no explanation to offer for this deviant phonological behaviour.

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A P P E N D I X

LIST OF PHONOLOGICAL RULES

- PR 1: Nasalization of e and o (N-e-o):
3.1.2.
- PR 2: Vowel Nasalization (VN): 3.1.2.;
revised, 3.2.2.
- PR 3: Oral Consonant Nasalization: 3.1.3.
- PR 4: Nasal Stop Formation (NSF): 3.1.3.
- PR 5: Intensive Suffix Vowel Assimilation
(ISVA); (in three parts): 3.1.3.1.
- PR 6: Nasal Release (NR): 3.1.4.
- PR 7: Vowel Assimilation (VA): 3.2.1.
revised 3.2.1.1.
- PR 8: Vowel Contraction (VC):
part (a): 3.2.3.1.
parts (a) and (b): 3.2.3.3.
- PR 9: Boundary Deletion (BD): 3.2.4.
- PR 10: High Tone Spreading (HTS): 3.3.2.2.1.;
revised, 3.3.2.2.3.
- PR 11: Tonal Simplification (TS): 3.3.2.2.2.
- PR 12: Initial Pitch Assignment (IPA): 3.3.2.2.3.

- PR 13: Downdrift (DD): 3.3.2.2.3.
- PR 14: Floating Low Tone Deletion (FLTD):
3.3.2.2.4.
- PR 15: 3p. IV Quality: 4.2.2.3.2.
- PR 16: SCM Segment Deletion (SCMSD):
4.3.2.1.4.1.
- PR 17: Tonal Segmentalization (T Seg.):
4.3.2.1.4.2.; revised 5.1.2.
- PR 18: Simple Imperative High Tone
Lowering (SIHTL): 4.3.2.3.1.
- PR 19: r Deletion (RD): 4.3.2.4.1.
revised 5.2.1.
- PR 20: Simple Completive Suffix Assimilation
(SCSA): 4.3.2.4.2.
- PR 21: Simple Completive Suffix Deletion
(SCSD): 4.3.2.4.3.
- PR 22: Subject Pronoun Backness Assimilation
(SPBA): 4.3.2.7.
- PR 23: Tone Shifting (TSH): 5.1.1.
- PR 24: Low Tone Raising (LTR): 5.1.3.
- PR 25: Derived High Tone Lowering (DHTL): 5.1.4.
- PR 26: High Tone Postponement (HTP): 5.1.5.

- PR 27: Tonal Absorption (TA): 5.1.6.
- PR 28: Pronoun Final Low Tone Raising
(PFLTR): 5.1.7.
- PR 29: CVV Low Tone Raising (CVVLTR):
5.1.7.
- PR 30: Mutual Vowel Assimilation (MVA):
5.2.2.

